

DEVELOPING REAL TIME TECHNOLOGY TO SUPPORT AUTISTIC EMOTION REGULATION: AN INTERDISCIPLINARY EXPLORATION

*A thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of
the West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Philosophy*

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Declaration

I declare that, except where explicit reference is made to the contribution of others, that this thesis is the result of my own work and has not been submitted for any other degree at the University of the West of Scotland or any other institution.

Lauren Margaret Gillies-Walker

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Table of Contents

DECLARATION	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	3
PUBLICATIONS AND CONFERENCE PRESENTATIONS	7
LIST OF TABLES	8
LIST OF FIGURES	10
APPENDIX LIST	11
ABSTRACT	12
KEY DEFINITIONS	15
1. INTRODUCTION	18
1.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION	18
<i>Prevalence of Autism</i>	18
1.2 AUTISM THEORY.....	19
<i>The Medical Model</i>	20
<i>Autism as a Difference: The Double Empathy Theory</i>	21
<i>The Neurodiversity Paradigm</i>	22
<i>Autistic Emotion Regulation and Anxiety</i>	23
1.3 ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAM (EEG) BASED EMOTION RECOGNITION.....	26
1.4 PREVIOUS LITERATURE ON REAL TIME TECHNOLOGY BASED ON PHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNALS (EEG) TO SUPPORT AUTISTIC EMOTION REGULATION	28
1.5 THESIS AIMS	32
THESIS STRUCTURE	35
2 METHODOLOGY	37
2.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION	37
2.2 THESIS OVERVIEW.....	37
<i>Mixed Methods Approach</i>	38
<i>Exploratory Sequential Mixed Methods</i>	40
<i>Adopting a Pragmatic Approach</i>	41
<i>Participatory Design</i>	42
2.3 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS.....	43
<i>Power differentials and consent processes</i>	46
2.4 THE INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACH	48
2.5 REFLEXIVE STATEMENT	48
3 TECHNOLOGICAL INTERVENTIONS TO SUPPORT AUTISTIC SOCIAL AND EMOTIONAL COMMUNICATION: A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW	51
3.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION	51
3.2 BACKGROUND LITERATURE AND RATIONALE.....	52
3.3 METHOD	55
<i>Search Method</i>	55
<i>Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria</i>	57
<i>Data Extraction & Synthesis</i>	58
<i>Quality Assessment</i>	59
3.4 SUMMARY OF STUDIES AIMED AT SUPPORTING AUTISTIC SOCIO-EMOTIONAL COMMUNICATION VIA TECHNOLOGY.....	59

3.4.1 Participant Characteristics.....	60
Virtual Reality.....	61
Computer Based/Serious Game.....	64
Robotics.....	70
Mobile Applications.....	74
3.5 CONCLUSION	78
4 “YOU FEEL LIKE YOU KIND OF WALK BETWEEN THE TWO WORLDS”: A PARTICIPATORY STUDY EXPLORING HOW TECHNOLOGY CAN SUPPORT SOCIAL AND EMOTIONAL COMMUNICATION FOR AUTISTIC PEOPLE	81
4.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION	81
4.2 BACKGROUND LITERATURE AND RATIONALE.....	82
4.3 METHOD.....	86
Design.....	86
Participants	86
Procedure	87
Focus Group Questions.....	87
Qualitative Analysis.....	89
4.4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION	91
4.4 THEME 1: COMMUNICATION CHALLENGES	92
Sub-theme: Emotion Processing Challenges.....	93
Sub-theme: Person-centered Technologies are needed	96
4.5 THEME 2: VIEWS ON EMOTION REGULATION TECHNOLOGY	99
Sub-theme: Benefits of Emotion Regulation Technology	99
Sub-theme: Challenges of Emotion Regulation Technology.....	101
4.6 THEME 3: ‘HOW’ TECHNOLOGY IS IMPLEMENTED	108
Sub-theme: Training is Needed.....	108
Sub-theme: Defining Individual Goals and Needs.....	110
4.5 LIMITATIONS.....	113
4.6 CONCLUSION AND IMPLICATIONS	114
5 “IF IT IS TO MAKE OUR BRAINS REACH A NORMAL STATE OR AN OPTIMAL STATE, THAT IS A RED FLAG”: CONSIDERING THE ETHICS OF WEARABLE TECHNOLOGIES BASED ON PHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNALS	116
5.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION	116
5.2 AIMS.....	117
5.3 ARE REAL TIME TECHNOLOGY BASED ON PHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNALS ACCURATE?	119
5.4 DATA PRIVACY	122
5.4 INFORMED CONSENT AND ENSURING THE PURPOSE IS CLEAR	124
5.5 CONCLUSION	128
5.6 CHAPTER SUMMARY.....	129
6. DETECTING AFFECTIVE STATES VIA PHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNALS IN AUTISTIC AND NON-AUTISTIC ADULTS..130	
6.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION	130
RESEARCH QUESTIONS AND AIMS	131
6.2 BACKGROUND LITERATURE AND RATIONALE.....	131
Emotion Recognition	134
The Circumplex Model of Affect	135
The role of the autonomic nervous system (ANS) in emotion regulation and cognitive mechanisms.....	136
The Benefits of Emotion Regulation Technology (Brain-Computer Interfaces)	137
6.3 METHOD.....	139
EEG Cap Sensor (EPOC(+)).....	139

<i>The Modified Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Scale</i>	139
<i>Participant Demographics</i>	140
<i>Inclusive Study Design</i>	141
6.4 EMOTION ELICITATION	142
6.5 PROCEDURE FOR EMOTIONAL STIMULI SELECTION	144
6.5 IMAGE SELECTION VALIDATION	145
6.5 EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL	145
<i>Images Order</i>	146
<i>Timing of Emotional Stimuli Elicitation</i>	147
.....	148
6.5 SIGNAL PROCESSING AND ANALYSIS.....	148
<i>Pre-processing</i>	148
<i>Feature Extraction</i>	149
<i>Dimensionality Reduction/Principle Component Analysis</i>	150
<i>Classification Results</i>	151
<i>Analysis of Self-reported & Expected Responses</i>	155
6.6 LIMITATIONS	156
6.7 DISCUSSION	157
6.8 CONCLUSION	160
7. OVERALL DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION	161
7.1 CHAPTER INTRODUCTION	161
7.2 AIM 1.....	161
7.3 AIM 2.....	164
7.4 AIM 3.....	166
7.5 CONTRIBUTIONS TO KNOWLEDGE.....	167
7.6 RECOMMENDATIONS FOR PRACTICE	168
7.7 OVERALL LIMITATIONS	169
7.8 FUTURE DIRECTIONS.....	170
7.9 OVERALL CONCLUSION	172

Publications and Conference Presentations

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List of Tables

Table 1: General recommendations for inclusive research (Chown et al, 2017) and how they were adhered to in the current research

Table 2: Search Strategy for Each Database

Table 3: Systematic Review Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Table 4: Age Range and Gender Across Selected Studies

Table 5: Summary of VR Studies to aiming Support Autistic Social and Emotional Communication

Table 6: Summary of Computer Based/Serious Game Studies Aiming to Support Autistic Social and Emotional Communication

Table 7: Summary of Robotics Studies aiming to support Autistic Social and Emotional Communication

Table 8: Summary of mobile app studies aiming to support Autistic social and emotional communication

Table 9: Autistic Group Participant Demographics

Table 10: All Participant Characteristics (n=34)

Table 11: Thematic Analysis Systematic Framework (Braun et al., 2019)

Table 12: Main Themes and Sub-themes

Table 13: Differences in Views of Real Time Emotion Regulation Technology via Physiological Signals

Table 14: EEG Signal bands, frequencies & Characteristics

Table 15: Autistic and Non-Autistic Participant Demographics

Table 16: Summary of GAPED & OASIS Databases

Table 17: Expected Emotions to be Induced in Each Quadrant (Rahman & Sarkar, 2021).

Table 18: Support Vector Machine Classification Performance for Valence and Arousal

Table 19: Ensemble of Trees Classification Performance

Table 20: k-nearest neighbors (KNN) Classification Performance

List of Figures

Figure 1: Chapter Structure

Figure 2: The PRISMA flow diagram: The search process and the inclusion and exclusion of studies at each stage

Figure 3: Technology Types (Computer-based, Mobile Apps, Virtual Reality, Robotics) across selected studies

Figure 4: Selected studies published by year

Figure 5: Thematic Map of The Focus Group Themes & Subsequent Ethical Considerations of Real-Time Wearable Technologies

Figure 6: Electrode placements and inputs on the recording device

Figure 7: The Circumplex Model of Affect

Figure 8: Emotiv EPOC(+)

Figure 9: Image Selection Method

Figure 10: Images before and after selection

Figure 11: Timing of Emotional Stimuli Elicitation

Figure 12: Emotion Self-assessment: Self-Assessment Manikin scale

Figure 13: Overview of Pre-processing & Analysis Procedure

Figure 14: Dimensionality Reduction Procedure

Appendix List

Appendix 1: Quality Appraisal Guidance, The McMaster Critical Review Form (Study 1)

Appendix 2: Information sheet (Study 2)

Appendix 3: Consent form (Study 2)

Appendix 4: Focus Group Schedule (Study 2)

Appendix 5: Information sheet (Study 3)

Appendix 6: Consent form (Study 3)

Appendix 7: Debriefing sheet (Study 3)

Appendix 8: Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (Study 3)

Appendix 9: RAADS Questionnaire (Study 3)

Appendix 10: SAM Scale (Study 3)

Abstract

As technology advances in the modern era, the potential for emotion regulation technology based on physiological signals to support physical and mental health is becoming increasingly popular. Technologies that support emotional self-awareness (e.g. brain-computer interface devices, wireless monitoring and mobile apps) may help individuals manage their mental health, leading to improvements in overall health and well-being. This could be particularly beneficial for Autistic people who report high levels of anxiety. Whilst this emerging area of research is exciting and innovative, real time emotion recognition from physiological signals is an extremely challenging and complex task, with many cognitive, affective, and environmental factors yet to be investigated within the literature. To date, there has been no qualitative exploration consulting the Autistic community to identify experiences and expectations of such technologies. Furthermore, despite a growing body of studies showing promise, the accuracy and reliability of such technology has been debated in the literature and there is currently no consensus for a universal method for affect identification.

In order to gain insight into current developments, a systematic review of intervention studies was carried out, focusing on digital technologies (mobile applications, robotics, computer based/games and virtual reality) that specifically aim to support Autistic socio-emotional communication. Five databases were used to search for articles published between 2014-2022, resulting in 28 studies that met the inclusion criteria. Results provide evidence that, as technology advances, there is increasing potential for the use of technology to support Autistic socio-emotional communication. However, challenges are also highlighted (e.g many studies were based on outdated theoretical models, lack of robust methodology/objective measures, lack of follow up evaluation methods or co-participatory methods). Findings emphasise the need for technology to be developed and implemented alongside the Autistic community.

To this end, focus groups with Autistic people and their allies (parents of Autistic people, health-care professionals and educational staff) were conducted to explore a wide range of experiences, expectations and opinions on technologies based on physiological signals. Thirty-four participants were recruited in total and Reflexive Thematic Analysis generated three themes: (1) Communication Challenges (2) Views on Emotion Regulation Technology (3) 'How' technology is implemented. Results provide meaningful insight into the socio-emotional communication challenges faced by Autistic people, and explore the expectations of technology aimed at supporting emotion regulation. These findings further our understanding of how such supports may improve overall well-being and quality of life. Ethical considerations that arose within the focus groups are also explored and a conceptual framework based on a thematic map of the focus group data is presented. This provides a basis for exploring the ethics of autonomous technologies based on physiological signals (EEG) that aim to support Autistic emotion regulation

In the quantitative phase of the thesis, machine learning methods are used to provide insight into both the neurophysiological basis underlying emotion processing and the feasibility of EEG techniques for the detection of affective states, ultimately providing a basis for automatic emotion regulation in therapeutic support strategies. The aim was to provide an indication of accuracy for affect identification within Autistic and non-Autistic populations. Results from three separate classifiers are reported for each group (Autistic and non-Autistic, Autistic only, non-Autistic only). In the Autistic and Non-Autistic groups which included all participants, Support Vector Machine with Gaussian Kernel produced the highest accuracy rates (Arousal 66% and Valence 59%). In the Autistic group, Ensemble of Trees produced the highest accuracy rate (Arousal 71%) and SVM produced the highest accuracy rate for valence (70%). In the Non-Autistic group, Ensemble of Trees produced the highest accuracy rate for Arousal (70.7%) and SVM produced the highest accuracy rate for Valence (57%). Overall, results suggest that EEG signals have discernible patterns that can be classified to identify different affective states. Taken together, the empirical findings extend the literature in wearable technology research and provide a basis for investigating ethical considerations which

must be prioritised if the area is to progress. Importantly, this thesis has practical implications for Autism researchers, technology developers, health and social care professionals and policy makers alike.

Key Definitions

Autism

Autism, historically known as Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is defined as a complex neurodevelopmental condition characterised by social interaction and social communication difficulties, as well as repetitive behaviours and focused interests (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Recent changes to this definition recognize Autism as part of a neurodiversity continuum, rather than a disorder (Lyall et al., 2017). Autism has been viewed as part of a neurodiversity movement that promotes Autism as a difference rather than a deficit (Kapp et al., 2013). Individuals diagnosed with Autism may have typical or above-average intelligence with at least 50% also having additional learning needs. Therefore behaviours in each core domain are unique to each individual depending on level of ability and stage of development (Lodge et al., 2019).

Social Communication

Social communication can be defined as the use of verbal (language processing skills and pragmatics) and non-verbal skills (gestures, body movement and eye contact) in social situations, including taking the perspective of others. Social communication behaviors are influenced by sociocultural and individual factors (Curenton & Justice, 2004; Inglebret, Jones, & Pavel, 2008).

Emotional Communication

Emotions can be defined as physiological, behavioral, and/or communicative reactions to stimuli that are cognitively processed and experienced as emotional (Planlap et al, 2006). Emotions are usually experienced internally via physiological changes e.g increased heart rate, a tense stomach, sweating. Such physiological reactions aren't always noticeable to other people and are therefore

intrapersonal unless an individual changes their behaviour or verbally communicates their internal state.

Emotion Regulation

Emotion Regulation (ER) can be defined as the process of effectively managing and responding to the emotions of one's self and others (Aldao et al, 2010). Poor ER is reported by many Autistic people and has been found to result in increased anxiety, depression, anger and physical health outcomes (Mazefsky et al., 2013; Cai et al, 2018). Support strategies targeting ER in Autistic people have been shown to be effective (Cai et al, 2017). Thomson et al, (2015) found that by supporting emotion regulation in Autistic children, parents reported significant improvements in child emotional lability, behavioural dysregulation, internalising symptoms, and adaptive behaviour.

'Challenging behaviours'

"Behaviour can be described as challenging when it is of such an intensity, frequency or duration as to threaten the quality of life and/or the physical safety of the individual or others and is likely to lead to responses that are restrictive, aversive or result in exclusion" (Emerson et al., 1988).

It is important to note that, in recent years, Autism researchers have sought to change the narrative that Autistic people are aggressive due to displaying challenging behaviours such as hitting others, self-harm, extreme emotional 'outbursts', and instead suggest that all behaviours are a form of communication. Consequently, 'challenging behaviours' is fast becoming an outdated term due to its negative connotations. Therefore throughout this thesis, the term 'behaviours of concern' will be used.

Participatory Design

Participatory Design (in the context of technology development) refers to approaches that view end users as a source of innovation and insight, focusing on how individual needs can be met. Previously within technology development, end users were recruited to test and evaluate products or devices. In contrast to this, participatory design actively involves end users in the design process, from the initial research idea through to prototype testing (Robertson & Simonsen, 2012). There is emphasis on empowering individuals to contribute to and steer research that is about them (Brosnan & Parsons, 2016). One of the benefits of adopting participatory research methods is the reduced power imbalance between participant and researcher (Nelson & Wright, 1995) and the inclusive adaptations to the environment, method or dissemination (Zervogianni & Fletcher-Watson, 2020). Such adaptations, allow groups to participate who may otherwise never be involved in research e.g. individuals with complex/additional needs or those who are non-speaking.

Affective technology

Affective technology can be defined as systems and devices that are able to recognise, interpret and process human affect (emotional states). According to Picard (2015) 'affective technologies are systems which can sense and/or generate human emotions such as happiness, anger or fear'. Advances in affective computing are increasingly developing new ways for technology to interact with humans (Grond et al, 2019) e.g brain-computer interfaces (Garcia-Molina, & Tsoneva et al, 2013), intelligent robotics and wearable technologies for healthcare interventions (Tavakoli et al, 2020).

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Chapter Introduction

This chapter covers five key topics that are central to the thesis: (1) Prevalence of Autism¹ (2) Autism Theory (3) Anxiety and Autistic emotion regulation (4) Electroencephalogram (EEG) based emotion recognition (5) Previous literature on real time technology based on physiological signals to support emotion regulation. Following this, the overall thesis aims and contributions to knowledge will be discussed.

Prevalence of Autism

The prevalence of Autism appears to be increasing worldwide (Zeidan & Fombonne, 2022). In the 1940's Autism was thought to be extremely rare, with only the most 'severe' individuals being formally diagnosed; around 1 in 2000 (Rice et al, 2012). However recent years have seen a dramatic rise, with around 1 in 100 individuals being diagnosed (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). The UK census reports that 1.1% of the population is Autistic (Office of National Statistics, 2016). Autism is now thought to be the most common neurodevelopmental condition in children. The ratio of male-to-female diagnosis is not four to one, as previously assumed; rather, it is closer to three to one (Loomes et al, 2017). Several studies have suggested a bias in terms of gender, concluding that

¹ The terms 'Autistic person' and 'Autism' will be used throughout this thesis. This use of identity first language, is known to be preferred by the Autistic community, as opposed to person first terminology (Botha & Hanlon et al, 2021; Bury et al, 2020).

Autistic girls have a greater chance of not receiving a clinical diagnosis (Loomes et al, 2017; Haney, 2016; Tsirgiotis et al, 2022).

An explanation for the increase in people receiving an Autism diagnosis may be due to changes in the diagnostic criteria, including the broadening of the scope of diagnosis and lowering the age an individual can be diagnosed from (Fombonne, 2018; Williams et al, 2006). A further explanation may also be the increase in Autism awareness and advocacy in the last decade (Zeidan & Fombonne, 2022). However, Fombonne (2009) pointed out that due to the challenging nature of comparing prevalence studies over time, it is possible that there has been an actual increase in prevalence. Buescher et al, (2014) reviewed data on the economic effect of Autism, taking into account prevalence, level of functioning and place of residence. Results showed that the cost of supporting an individual with Autism and intellectual learning needs during his/her lifespan was £2.4 million in the USA and £1.5 million in the UK. This significant direct and indirect economic effect, combined with increasingly scarce societal resources highlights the need for more effective and low-cost support.

1.2 Autism Theory

Autism has historically been defined very differently from what the world is now beginning to understand it as. The past three decades have seen Autism research increasingly rise, and with it a new understanding of how Autistic people experience the world. Autism was once viewed as a rare disorder, more common in males than females. Whereas now it is well known as being more prevalent in females than previously thought and numerous studies have explored how it may present in females differently i.e being more likely to mask². This could explain why so many Autistic

² Many Autistic women report challenges in the diagnosis process/being diagnosed with other conditions. Such barriers have been linked to significant mental strain (Zener (2019); Lockwood & Milner et al, 2021).

women are now diagnosed in adulthood. The way that Autism has been defined throughout history has had, and continues to have a profound impact both on how Autistic people view themselves and how they are treated and supported within society (for a deeper consideration of this please see - Botha & Cage, 2022). The following section will outline theories of Autism, focusing on how Autism has been conceptualised within the medical and social models of disability (i.e theories that have defined Autism as a disorder and those that view Autism as a difference) before providing an overview of the neurodiversity paradigm. Implications of these theoretical frameworks and how the social model of disability underpins the current thesis will also be discussed.

The Medical Model

The conceptual framework for this thesis is rooted within the social model of disability. In order to fully understand the reasons for this, it is important to firstly consider the medical model of disability. Both the medical and social models of disability have driven very different discourses about Autism through history and thus have had a significant impact on global health policies and care standards. Considering the medical model of disability is also extremely useful in understanding the importance of inclusion and the Neurodiversity movement.

The Medical model (also known as the biomedical model) of disability was first established in the mid-1800s and took over from religious models as science advanced (Retief & Letšosa, 2018). Within this model, disability is viewed as being objectively negative and a personal tragedy for both the individual and their family. This negative narrative and conception of disability has unfortunately led to traumatic medical treatments and in many societies has meant disabled people have been socially excluded (Anderson-Chavarria, 2022). According to (Rosqvist et al, 2020) the medical model of disability has two key aims: to ensure individuals live a life as close to an 'ideal state' as possible and to improve those deficits that arise from socially constructed assumptions of an ideal neurology.

One major disadvantage of the medical model is that the locus of disability is within the person i.e the individual must be 'fixed' or 'cured' via medical treatment, as opposed to society making inclusive adaptations to support the individual (Hogan, 2019). Consequently, this depicts disabled people as being 'abnormal' rather than 'normal' and emphasises the narrative of disabilities and/or Autism being something that is negative.

Autism as a Difference: The Double Empathy Theory

In contrast, the social model of disability aimed to overcome the limitations of the medical model, presenting an opposing view of disability. A key feature of the social model of disability is that disability is socially constructed and ultimately aims to 'address barriers to participation'. Recent advances within Autism research and the neurodiversity movement e.g 'The Double Empathy Theory' are situated within the social model of disability.

'The Double Empathy Theory' developed by Milton (2012) has been one of the most influential Autism theories of the past decade. This theory places emphasis on the two-sided nature of Autistic/Non-Autistic communication and suggests that communication breakdown is not solely due to Autistic 'impairment', instead, a mutual misunderstanding between two people. The Double Empathy theory challenges the view that Autism is something to be fixed or cured and instead supports the view that Autistic people have a different way of seeing the world and thus, different communication styles. According to Milton, just as Autistic people may lack insight into neuro-typical norms and culture, neuro-typical people also may lack insight into Autistic norms and culture. Where previous Autism theory (such as The Theory of Mind) has placed fault on the Autistic person within social interactions, The Double Empathy Theory does not. In his new editorial paper, Milton (2022) provides an updated account '10 years on', in which he states, "Instead of focusing on perceived social deficits and normative remediation, the concept suggests a position of humility in the face of

difference, the need to build rapport and understanding and not assume lack of capacity for understanding.”

The value of The double Empathy Theory is that it avoids biases about social norms³ in the interpretation of a lack of mutual understanding. There is a common misunderstanding, rather than problematic social behaviour of one individual. This theoretical concept is invaluable not only to guide Autism research and practice (e.g support strategies within social care settings), but also in relation to how Autistic people view themselves within society.

Mitchell et al (2021) point out the consequences that being misperceived can have on Autistic mental health. 72% of Autistic people experience suicidal desire (Cassidy et al, 2014; Cassidy et al, 2018) and as such are significantly more at risk of suicide compared with the general population. Since it is well known that social belonging plays is an important protective factor against mental health difficulties (Mitchell et al, 2021), this new way of viewing Autism as a difference, rather than a deficit, holds the potential to protect against social rejection/isolation and improve Autistic self-worth.

The Neurodiversity Paradigm

The term ‘neurodiversity’ originated from work by Judy Singer (Australian Sociologist) and was based on the notion of biodiversity. The term refers to perceived variations in affective, cognitive and sensory processing that differ from what is considered the ‘norm’ or ‘predominant neurotype’ (Rosqvist et al, 2020). Through the years the concept of neurodiversity grew increasingly popular and the ‘neurodiversity movement’, developed by Autistic self-advocates in the 1990’s eventually gained huge momentum. Led by both Autistic people and other neurodivergent people e.g those with attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) and dyslexia, this paradigm takes a strengths

³ Social norms refer to perceived rules that constrain behaviour (Bicchieri & Mercier, 2014).

based approach, drawing on key principles of the social model of disability and ultimately viewing any type of neurodiversity as a difference, rather than a deficit. The neurodiversity paradigm has been hugely influential in activism for the human rights of disabled people, for health/social care professionals, parents of neurodivergent children, policy makers and for neurodivergent people themselves.

In contrast the medical model of disability, a key motivation of the neurodiversity movement or 'paradigm' is to challenge assumptions that neurodivergent people need to be 'fixed' or 'cured'. Instead, emphasis is placed on the inclusivity of the environment and how social barriers can be overcome. Owen & Stenhammer (2015) propose that the greatest barriers are societies expectations of what it is to be 'normal'. Despite challenging the key components of the medical model, Rosqvist et al (2020) note that an anti-cure/prevention approach does not mean to eliminate interventions that may be beneficial for neurodiverse individuals. Instead, it is only those interventions that aim to 'fix' or 'change' a person to make them 'normal' that are rejected.

One point of criticism has been that the neurodiversity paradigm does not take into account that some people may view themselves as having a disability. Some critics have suggested this as a weakness since many Autistic people do view their diagnosis as a disability. However such criticism is unfounded, as Houting (2019) argues; neurodiversity advocates generally view Autism to be both a difference and a disability. Whilst intervention research has historically been aimed at 'reducing/eliminating core deficits' (French & Kennedy, 2018), the neurodiversity movement suggests that research should aim to improve quality of life and well-being. Consequentially, there has been a call to situate Autism research within a neurodiversity paradigm, as opposed to the historically accepted medicalised model of disability (Pellicano & Houting, 2022).

Autistic Emotion Regulation and Anxiety

Emotion regulation can be defined as ‘the ability to modulate arousal and emotional responses in the service of adaptive and socially appropriate behaviour’ (Gross & Thompson, 2006). The ability to regulate emotions play a key role in human functioning and day to day life and involves reflection, planning and self-regulation (Calkins & Leerkes, 2004). Autism has been associated with atypical functioning of the Autonomic nervous system (for a review see Benevides & Lane, 2015) which is believed to result in emotional, physiological and behavioral difficulties (Benevides & Lane, 2015). Recent research suggests that around 40-50% of Autistic individuals also have co-morbid alexithymia which impacts the ability to identify and describe emotional states (Berthoz & Hill, 2005). This finding has important implications as it suggests that socio-emotional difficulties reported by Autistic people may be in fact due to co-morbid alexithymia. Studies have shown that many Autistic people tend to use fewer emotion regulation strategies and instead tend to use more unhelpful strategies such as avoidance, rumination or denial (Mazefsky et al, 2014).

This may explain why Autistic people tend to experience more social isolation, depression and anxiety than non-autistic peers (Lai et al, 2017), which can lead to poorer quality of life (DaWalt et al, 2019). For instance, around 50% of Autistic individuals experience higher levels of anxiety and social anxiety than non-autistic people (Gillott & Standen 2007; Maddox & White 2015) and many report sensory difficulties (Rodgers & Ofield, 2018; Fernandez-Prieto et al, 2021). The prevalence of mental health issues within the Autistic population is concerning; Eves & Holmes (2007) noted that 77% of their sample had additional diagnoses such as depression, anxiety and bi-polar disorder. Rates of mood disorders in Autistic people have been found to be between 53% and 70% (Lugnegard et al, 2022). These social and emotional communication difficulties within the Autistic population can vary greatly depending on the stage of development and across a wide range of contexts (Simmons et al 2009; Cage et al, 2018). This indicates an urgent need for improved care and effective strategies that aim to support Autistic emotion regulation (McGuire & Hagopian, 2016).

The idea that humans can self-regulate emotions (as opposed to experiencing them inertly) can be traced back thousands of years. Over time, many psychologists and philosophers have sought to understand psychological defences and how individuals deal with stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984). The process model of emotion regulation (Gross 1998, 2015) has been the most dominant theory within the emotion regulation field and has made a huge impact on both psychology and neuroscience. It suggests that emotions progress over time and that different strategies can be put in place either before, during or after the experience of an emotion. Emotions may be regulated via one of four key aims: (1) Situation selection – changing whether or not an individual is exposed to certain emotional stimuli. (2) Situation modification – changing the nature of such stimuli. (3) Attentional deployment – changing how much/what attention is focused on it. (4) Cognitive Appraisal – Changing how the situation or emotion inducing stimuli is evaluated.

This model provides a framework for several different applications within several different domains, including: clinical, social, developmental, cognitive and crucially support and intervention design. However, a key challenge that remains, is defining how emotion regulation is related to self-regulation (Gross, 2015). This theoretical challenge is particularly pertinent when developing technologies aiming to support autonomy/promote independence and should be an important consideration in future work. Overcoming such issues would require successful collaboration from both psychology, neuroscience and computer science disciplines.

Tarver & Pearson (2021) carried out qualitative interviews to explore how anxiety impacts the quality of life of Autistic people and their families. Participants included parents of Autistic children who use few words or are non-speaking. Results showed parents experience difficulty in recognising anxiety in their child and how it had significantly impacted their health, well-being and overall quality of life. Parents also reported a number of anxiety management strategies. Likewise, in a recent synthesis of parental management strategies, results showed the most common were environmental modification, structure, routine and reward systems (O’Nions et al, 2018).

Anxiety has also been linked to social camouflaging. Social camouflaging can be defined as trying to mask 'autistic characteristics or traits' to non-autistic people during social interactions (Hull et al, 2017). Although some benefits of camouflaging have been reported by Autistic people (Hull et al, 2007), it has also been linked to loss of identity and poor mental health such as higher rates of suicide (Cassidy et al, 2018; Livingston & Colvert, 2019). If these challenges faced by autistic people are viewed from a context-based approach, then interventions aimed at improving person-environment fit should be of utmost importance. However, the vast majority of intervention research has placed more emphasis on changing or 'curing' the individual, without adapting the environment (Wong et al, 2015). Mandy et al (2016) suggests that greater importance must be placed on adapting the environment, thus improving person-environment fit. Real time affective technology may have a vital part to play in such interventions. For instance, in allowing care givers insight into affective states, they'd be able to adapt the environment (e.g lighting, temperature, noise) accordingly, thus improving person-environment fit.

1.3 Electroencephalogram (EEG) Based Emotion Recognition

The link between human emotions and the brain has been well documented and in recent years the use of physiological signals such as electroencephalogram (EEG) has been commonly used for emotion recognition research (Mehdizadehfar et al. 2020; Ackermann et al, 2016). Emotions can be viewed as functions of the brain and are the central point of all nervous systems (LeDoux, 2009). In recent years, Neuroscience, psychology, and computer science disciplines have seen a huge surge in studies exploring the neural basis of emotions and in many recent theories of emotion the Autonomic Nervous System (ANS) plays a key role in emotional responses (Kreibig, 2010; Levenson, 2014). Although Emotions are linked with the entire nervous system, the limbic system within the brain especially plays a major role in human emotions. It includes thalamus, hypothalamus, hippocampus, amygdala, and several other nearby areas.

EEG signals are a direct measurement of neuronal activity, have excellent temporal resolution and are therefore the most reliable measurement since physiological signals can't be imitated to produce false emotions (Torres & Torres, 2020). Other methods of measuring brain activity include functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI), and magnetoencephalography (MEG) however EEG has been the most popular method for data collection and is particularly useful for brain-computer interface research as fMRI and MEG methods cannot be used out with a lab setting. Furthermore, both these methods are more costly, require more intense training/specialised licenses (Sharon & Hämäläinen et al, 2007).

A further benefit of using EEG methods is that (unlike the use of other modalities for emotion recognition such as facial expression, speech, low-pass filtered speech, body movement, gestures to classify emotions) it overcomes the challenge of subjectivity and is not sensitive to social masking (ref here). Furthermore, strong correlations have been found between EEG signals and stress (Liao C-Y & Chen, 2018; Vanitha & Krishnan, 2017) suggesting that wearable monitoring devices based on EEG acquisition may be an important avenue for emotion regulation and stress reduction methods.

The amplitude of EEG signals varies across the range 2–100 μ V, with frequency ranging between 1 and 100Hz but falling into five frequency sub-bands that are conventionally named delta (below 4Hz), theta (4–7 Hz), alpha (8–13 Hz), beta (14–30Hz), and gamma wave (31–100 Hz). These different frequencies are measured by placing electrodes on the scalp which are able to record large amounts of data (Abhang & Gawali et al, 2016).

One major challenge of EEG signal measurement is that such extensive amounts of data can be difficult to interpret due to the presence of different frequency bands and noise. Signal processing techniques (pre-pre-processing, feature extraction and feature classification) provide a solution to this problem (Saxena et al, 2020; Loconsole et al, 2014).

1.4 Previous Literature on Real Time Technology Based on Physiological Signals (EEG) to Support Autistic Emotion Regulation

Given the high rates of anxiety, mental health issues and poorer quality of life discussed in the previous sections, urgent action is needed to improve support for Autistic people. As discussed, one new and innovative approach to support Autistic emotion regulation may be real time technology based on physiological signals. This section will review and evaluate previous empirical research in this area to understand where the gaps and limitations lie, thus, providing a rationale for the current thesis.

With technology being one of the driving forces in society and the preferred tool for many Autistic people (Mineo et al, 2009), the use of technological solutions as support strategies or to aid support strategies seems a logical step for individuals, parents and care organisations (Bosseler & Massaro, 2003). It is well documented that Autistic people report a 'natural affinity' to technologies (Valencia & Rusu, 2019). This may be due to interactive technologies⁴ being more predictable than humans, in that they do not require direct social interaction, and can give feedback or consistent rewards (Rapp et al, 2018; Grynszpan et al, 2014). One benefit of this for Autistic children is that parents and children can learn from each other when engaging with and interacting using assistive technology (Jeffs et al, 2005). Some researchers have suggested that EEG-based technologies will improve dramatically within the next 5-10 years and eventually could be widely used for emotion monitoring in healthcare, education, workplace performance and entertainment (Konar & Chakraborty, 2015).

Sensor interfaces which are able to identify physiological signals (such as EEG) may play a vital role in enabling emotion regulation strategies for Autistic people. It has been suggested that such devices may help in decreasing 'challenging behaviors' in Autistic people (Goodwin et al 2018; Laurent et al,

⁴ Interactive technologies allow interactions/communication between the user and a computer via an interface. Examples include robotics, computer based systems, smart phones, wearable/sensor interfaces and serious games (Kientz & Hayes et al, 2019).

2018). For instance, Zantinge et al (2017) found that lowered physiological arousal can have a positive effect on emotion regulation and social behavior. Therefore, if some challenging behaviors are mediated by a heightened state of physiological arousal, the reduction of this arousal state should reduce challenging behaviors at least in the short term (McDonnell et al, 2015).

As such, a physiological approach to detecting emotions may provide a unique and alternate means of supporting emotion regulation for Autistic people who report difficulties in knowing what emotions they are feeling or how to respond to the emotions of others . It may provide invaluable cues for parents, care-givers and teachers for continuous daily social behavior monitoring. Taj-Eldin, et al, 2018; Koo (2018) suggest that increasing parents or carers awareness of the individual's emotional state via technology, has the potential to allow the caregiver to take necessary actions to alleviate the symptoms of stress or frustration which can lead to challenging behaviours. Although several studies have proposed that real time technologies based on physiological signals to detect emotions may be useful for parents and carers to track affective states/intervene appropriately to reduce environmental stressors or to alter sensory triggers, such strategies may compromise autonomy of the individual (for a fuller consideration of the ethical implications please see Chapter 5). Furthermore, the majority of these studies have been conducted with little knowledge of Autistic needs or preferences. This seems to be a result of a scarcity in meaningful collaborations between disciplines and as such there has been little qualitative input from end users in many of these studies.

The detection of physiological signals for self emotion regulation (also known as neuro-feedback) is becoming increasingly popular. Pineda et al, (2003), trained participants to manipulate the SMR in a 3D first person shooter video game. Right and left-hand movements in the game were controlled by high and low μ^5 respectively. The authors concluded that the element of a brain computer

⁵ Mu can be defined as a type of brain wave commonly measured using electroencephalography (Landau & Puzis et al, 2020).

interface in Neuro-feedback training accelerates the learning curve in neuro-feedback training goals as it is more engaging. Similarly, Seo et al, (2018) investigated smartphone based neurofeedback to improve participants concentration. A portable EEG headband that was able to record activity over FP1 and FP2 was used. Participants were presented with an archery game that involved neurofeedback. Results showed that as concentration increased the aim moved closer to the target on the screen. Thus, neurofeedback was successful in improving participant's concentration index. There was also some evidence of preserving these effects after the completion of training. This shows that portable devices may be useful to produce Neuro-feedback training effects without the constraints of a lab. However, to our knowledge, no previous studies have explored views from the autistic community regarding the benefits or challenges such devices may present in practice, nor have any devices like this been implemented or used in daily practice.

Eldeeb et al (2021) used EEG methods to monitor real time changes in Autistic emotion regulation. The aim was to develop a brain-computer interface that would be able to differentiate between distress and non-distress conditions within a game environment. Part of the rationale for this was that neurofeedback technologies have been known to provide support strategies that are safe, portable and easy to use with no need for verbal or physical intervention (Eldeeb et al, 2021). Results showed high accuracy rates in identifying both distress and non-distress states and authors propose that the next step in this work would be to input visual cues within the BCI that would prompt emotion regulation strategies in real time. In line with these results, several other studies have also suggested EEG-based neurofeedback strategies as an effective way to improve Autistic social and emotional communication (Pineda & Juavinett, 2012; Kouijzer & Van Schie, 2010).

Similarly, Fan et al (2015) developed an EEG based, novel virtual reality (VR) driving simulator as a first step towards a Brain Computer Interface (BCI) for detecting emotional state, engagement level and mental load. This type of system (if developed with high accuracy rates) may be useful for Autistic people who are anxious drivers and would prefer to practice in a simulated environment.

Results showed accuracy rates of over 80% for mental load and engagement and over 75% for emotional states. Although these results are promising, the authors note that further work is needed to improve classification results (Fan et al, 2015).

Despite the clear potential of technology in improving autistic lives and the rapid “uptake” of technology as an intervention by the autism community (Berggren et al 2017; Pennington 2010; Odom et al, 2015; Kintsch and DePaula, 2002) the overall success of technological solutions has been varied. Additionally, the lack of methodologically robust evaluation methods for such technologies may also explain the varied results; with only a minority of studies assessing technological interventions in Autism being well controlled (Grynszpan et al., 2014). More specifically, the potential of autonomous real time technologies based on physiological signals (e.g EEG signals) remains restricted due to many unanswered questions around acceptability, design, ethics, accuracy and data privacy. Artificial intelligence and machine learning may have important contributions for Autistic healthcare; however these challenges must be addressed if there is to be any meaningful success. Addressing this problem places high demands on these technologies as differing levels of ability and varying rates of development must be taken into account.

Furthermore, there has been very limited research placing focus on developing autonomous real time affect detection technologies. In a systematic review of wearable technologies aimed at Autism interventions, Williams & Gilbert (2020) found that in studies aiming to support Autistic emotion regulation via physiological signal detection, only one study proposed presenting the emotional state to the individual themselves.

In summary, technological advances in artificial intelligence and machine learning systems have shown huge potential in allowing humans to become more emotionally self-aware. Such emotional self-awareness may help individuals manage their mental health, leading to improvements in overall health and well-being. This could be particularly beneficial for Autistic people who report high levels

of anxiety and are more likely to experience suicidal ideations as a result. Whilst this new and emerging area of research is exciting and innovative, real time emotion recognition from physiological signals is an extremely challenging and complex task, with many cognitive, affective, and environmental factors yet to be investigated within the literature. As yet, there is no universal consensus on an optimum system for real time affect recognition. More importantly, (to our knowledge) there has been no qualitative research to determine the acceptability, usefulness and direction for such technology in autistic communities.

1.5 Thesis Aims

As outlined in the sections above, research on real time technology based on physiological signals (e.g. brain-computer interfaces and wireless monitoring devices) aimed at supporting Autistic emotion regulation has showed great potential. However many challenges are yet to be overcome if it is to be successful. The aim of the research presented in this thesis is to explore experiences, opinions and expectations of technology (any type) and real time emotion regulation technology from the Autistic community and to assess the feasibility of such technology based on physiological signals (EEG signals) using machine learning methods.

Our overall aims and related research questions for this thesis include:

Aim 1: Systematic review of the literature on the use of technology aiming to support Autistic social and emotional communication

RQ1.1: What studies have developed technologies (Robotics, Virtual Reality, Computer-based, Mobile Apps) aimed at supporting Autistic socio-emotional communication?

RQ1.2: What are the advantages and challenges in technology development aimed at Autistic socio-emotional communication?

RQ1.3: What are the directions for future research in this area?

Aim 2: Explore experiences, perceptions and expectations of technology aimed at supporting socio-emotional communication, including real time affect detection technology based on physiological signals (EEG)

RQ2.1: What are participants experiences and expectations of technology (any type) aimed at supporting Autistic socio-emotional communication

RQ2.2: What are participant's views on the benefits and challenges of real time emotion regulation technology via physiological signals?

RQ2.3: What are the participants view on how these challenges might be overcome?

Aim 3: Investigate the feasibility of physiological signals (EEG) to detect affective states in Autistic and Non-Autistic people

RQ3.1: Can physiological signals (EEG signals) be used to detect affective states in Autistic and Non-Autistic adults?

RQ3.2: Are there differences in physiological responses to emotional stimuli in Autistic people compared to non-Autistic people?

- What is the association between self-report and expected ratings of the emotional stimuli?
- Is higher emotional intelligence correlated with self-report and expected ratings of the emotional stimuli?

RQ3.3: How can insight into the feasibility of physiological signals to detect affective states in Autistic and non-Autistic people be useful for the development/co-participatory design of autonomous emotion regulation technology?

The contributions of this thesis include:

- (1) Systematic literature review focusing on four key technology types (robotics, computer-based, mobile apps, virtual reality)
- (2) To our knowledge, the focus groups are the first study to qualitatively explore Autistic experiences and expectations of real time technology based on physiological signals (EEG)
- (3) A conceptual framework based on a thematic map of the focus group data is presented in Chapter 5. This provides a basis for exploring the ethics of autonomous technologies based on physiological signals (EEG) that aim to support Autistic emotion regulation
- (4) A classification system for affect detection using machine learning techniques is presented. This provides an indication of accuracy for affect identification within Autistic and non-Autistic populations.

Thesis Structure

Study 1: Chapter 3 outlines Study 1. A systematic search method is used to provide a review of studies using digital technology that aim to improve social and emotional communication in Autistic people from 2014-2022. Insight is provided into the challenges of digital technology development for Autistic people and what factors may lead to more effective and useful devices. A discussion of directions for future research is included, focusing on combining key disciplines (psychology, computer science and health) to bridge the gap between technology design and successful outcomes for Autistic people.

Study 2: Chapters 4 and 5 outline study 2. Qualitative focus groups with Autistic people and their allies were conducted to gain insight into experiences and expectations of technological supports aimed at supporting emotion regulation. Reflexive Thematic Analysis generated three themes: (1) Communication Challenges (2) Views on Emotion Regulation Technology (3) 'How' technology is implemented. Results provide meaningful insight into the socio-emotional communication challenges faced by Autistic people, and explore the expectations of technology aimed at supporting emotion regulation. Important ethical considerations (accuracy, data privacy and clear purpose) were identified within the focus group as being vital to the success of wearable technologies based on physiological signals. Chapter 5 discusses these issues in further depth and also provides rationale for Study 3 (quantitative phase) which explores accuracy rates for a classification model aiming to detect affect states in Autistic and non-Autistic adults.

Study 3: Chapter 6 outlines study 3. Machine learning methods are used to provide insight into both the neurophysiological basis underlying emotion processing and the feasibility of EEG techniques for the detection of affective states, ultimately providing a basis for automatic emotion regulation in therapeutic support strategies. Chapter 6 presents a classification model for affect detection in Autistic and non-Autistic adults. The association between Emotional Intelligence and emotion

recognition/physiological reactions to emotional stimuli in Autistic and Non-Autistic adults are also investigated and discussed. A visual outline of chapters is presented in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Chapter Structure

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Chapter Introduction

In this chapter, the research paradigm underpinning the thesis is outlined and justification is provided for the adoption of the research methodology and design. A description of exploratory mixed methods is provided followed by an explanation of how the project is well aligned with neurodiversity. An overview of ethical considerations is also provided, followed by reflections on the interdisciplinary approach and a reflexive statement.

2.2 Thesis Overview

There has recently been a call for a change in the direction of Autism research, focusing more on the impact of the quality of daily life people experience (Happé & Frith, 2020). Many Autism researchers are striving towards the promotion of inclusive language (Bury et al, 2020), participatory methods and research which places Autistic people at the heart of the research design process (Fletcher-Watson et al, 2019). It is hoped that this shift will pave the way for a future where Autism is not seen as a deficit, but as a difference. Not as a disorder to be 'fixed', but as a way of life to be embraced. It is my hope that the current PhD project will serve as part of this important shift to improve quality of life for Autistic people.

This project takes a mixed methods approach to investigate the use of technology aimed at supporting Autistic emotion regulation. Firstly, using qualitative methods to (1) Provide meaningful insight into experiences, perceptions and expectations of technology aimed at improving social and emotional skills (2) To explore participants' views on the use of technology to detect and regulate emotions, gaining insight into how design factors may increase effectiveness (3) To provide direction for future research that aims to improve the design and implementation of affective technology.

Secondly, underpinned by findings from the focus groups, machine learning methods are used to examine both the neurophysiological basis underlying emotion processing and the feasibility of EEG and ECG techniques for affect detection, providing an indication of accuracy using classification models for automatic emotion regulation technology.

Mixed Methods Approach

Mixed methods research began in the 1950s, before being more formally employed in the 1980s and is now becoming increasingly popular (McKim, 2017). Mixed methods have been defined as an approach involving the collection, analysis, or integration of both quantitative and qualitative data during the research process in order to gain a better understanding of the research problem (O'Cathain, 2020). Some researchers have debated this definition due to ongoing disagreements regarding its justifications (Cameron, 2011), however the surge in use and a growing focus on enhancing the quality of mixed methods in recent years has justified the question of value, compared with quantitative or qualitative independently (Fàbregues, & Molina-Azorín, 2017; McKim, 2017).

Mixed method approaches offer several advantages. For example, one of the key aims of mixed methods is to draw on the strengths of both qualitative and quantitative methods (Kaur, 2016) to offer a more complete “story” of a particular research topic, thus improving understanding and providing further insight, that would not be achievable by using a single approach (Creswell & Klassen, 2011; Jackson, 2019). Hurmerinta-Peltomäki & Nummela (2006) found that mixed method studies added value by increasing validity of the findings by addressing an overall question at different levels and informing the collection of the second data collection phase. Furthermore, the use of mixed methods allows the researcher to integrate a variety of theoretical perspectives (Creswell & Klassen et al, 2011).

Conversely, some researchers have criticized the mixed methods approach due to limits in statistical techniques in qualitative data that has been quantitized, e.g data can be susceptible to collinearity (Roberts 2000). Additionally, the collection and analysis of qualitative data may result in a reduced sample size, which may limit statistical procedures that might otherwise be useful. Furthermore, the process of integrating data from both approaches may be time consuming and expensive, requiring additional time and a variety expertise (Driscoll et al, 2007).

Taking both the advantages and disadvantages into account, a mixed methods approach was the most suitable and pragmatic approach, in order to answer the research questions in the current thesis. Since the current inter-disciplinary project spans across the fields of psychology, computing and health, this approach allowed the use of a combination of key methods from each discipline which best suited the research questions. This meant that for the current study qualitative methods could be used to gain insight into how affective technology could meet individual needs and be best implemented into practice, whilst also obtaining vital quantitative data that aims to make such innovative solutions possible. In this way, the different data collected could be converged to compliment the other. A key advantage of this was that not only were we able to answer complex research questions, which one method alone could not, but we were able to use qualitative inquiry to validate and inform the development of a technological intervention (O’Cathain et al, 2010), therefore gaining a richer and more complete view of the use of technology to support Autistic emotion regulation.

Creswell et al (2018) propose that there are three main types of mixed methods design. Firstly, a convergent parallel design which involves gathering both quantitative and qualitative data and using the results of one to confirm or disprove the findings of the other. The second is an explanatory sequential design, which involves a two phase design where the quantitative phase has more importance/weight. During this stage, the research questions from the second phase of the project depend and build on the first phase; the research questions are interconnected and sometimes

evolve during the study Schoonenboom & Johnson (2017). Thirdly, an exploratory sequential design involves using results from the qualitative phase to develop or inform the quantitative phase. This design was thought to be most suitable for the current project and is outlined below.

Exploratory Sequential Mixed Methods

An exploratory sequential mixed methods design was chosen in the current thesis as qualitative data was used to underpin and justify further quantitative investigation. We wanted to know if technology able to detect and regulate emotions in real time would be accepted by the Autistic community and if so, from a user's point of view and how it could be best designed and implemented. Thus, in the quantitative phase, we investigated the feasibility of EEG signals to detect affective states.

A key advantage of adopting an exploratory sequential mixed methods is that the data collected from both qualitative and quantitative phases could be used to confirm and corroborate the other, also known as concurrent triangulation (Creswell, 2017). For example, data collected from EEG signals is important in informing the machine learning models that underpin such interventions – however the success, practicality and usefulness of such technology is extremely limited without the input from stakeholders (qualitative phase). In carrying out the qualitative phase first, not only were we able to determine whether or not the development and design of such technology was warranted, but also gained insight into how this technology could meet individual needs and be implemented into practice. Furthermore, insight into some of the key challenges in this area (ethical considerations) were explored.

In order to answer the research questions the focus group questions were split into two main areas, first of all focusing on the use of technology in a broader sense; (1) the use and experience of any kind of technology aiming to improve social and emotional communication (2) perspectives and

expectations of the use of real time emotion regulation technology. The results of the focus groups formed a strong foundation and rationale to assess the accuracy of EEG-based affect detection (since this was a key concern of the Autistic community).

Adopting a Pragmatic Approach

Mixed methods are often associated with the philosophical assumptions of pragmatism (Creswell & Plano, 2011). A pragmatic approach is based on the notion of doing 'what works' valuing both objective and subjective knowledge and placing focus on the research problem (Morgan, 2007). In the current research, taking a pragmatic approach allowed for ambiguity, in the sense that qualitative and quantitative approaches were not viewed as competing methods, instead, focus was placed on whether the underpinning concepts would succeed in meeting the overall research aims.

One of the key features of pragmatism is a focus on shared meaning-making and communication in order to investigate research problems and provide practical solutions (Shannon-Baker, 2016). The objectives of the research are closely aligned with this principle i.e to involve autistic people (who have been historically excluded from research) in the research design process, with the vision of directing the research in such a way that will answer the most pertinent questions and provide solutions to the most life limiting communication challenges faced by autistic people. Designing inclusive research that allows for varying abilities and communication needs was of upmost importance when working with and recruiting Autistic participants. This decision to ensure inclusive methods is in line with the prominence of communication in pragmatism (Kember & Corbett, 2018) and was vital in creating a 'mutual understanding' between the researcher and participant. Adopting such inclusive approaches was also influenced by Milton's (2012) double empathy theory (for a recent overview see; Milton, 2020) that proposes the potential for a misunderstanding of how it is to be the other and highlights the importance of shared meaning in communications between autistic and non-autistic individuals.

Participatory Design

A participatory design was essential throughout the current thesis. Participatory research involves including autistic people in the research process to determine what research should be carried out and how it is implemented (Robb et al, 2020). The benefits of taking a participatory design approach have been particularly acknowledged for the development of technologies, specifically those that aim to aid communication in daily life (Van der Velden et al, 2014; Grond et al, 2019). Schuler & Namioka (1993) suggest that participatory design has several benefits in comparison to traditional technology design approaches: (1) The participants are viewed as 'experts' in the design processes as opposed to the developers/designers. This is especially important when recruiting participants such as minority groups, children and people with disabilities as there may be power dynamic and/or cultural gaps between the designers and these populations (Hussain, 2010). (2) Participants perceptions of and feelings towards the technology are viewed as equally important as how the technology functions/how well it works (3) The software and technology evaluated within the context of the environment they will be used in, allowing insight into the most appropriate way to implement the technology.

Furthermore, the focus on providing an inclusive research methods and environment, allows for a wider and more accessible engagement, specifically for those with more complex needs e.g people who are non-verbal or who may have intellectual disability (Long & Clarkson, 2017). While participatory design has been increasing in affective technology research, challenges remain concerning how technical and complex algorithms based on real time recognition systems are used in practice (Grond et al, 2019). Such challenges highlight important, ethical, and practical issues that make stakeholder input essential during the design stage and through to implementation (Robb et al, 2020).

It was therefore ensured that a neurodiversity affirmative design was at the heart of the current project. This was achieved in several ways, for example, the aims and selection of research questions of the quantitative phase were informed by the experiences, perceptions, and expectations of the Autistic community within the qualitative phase. The focus groups shaped the second quantitative phase of the project by allowing in depth insight into perspectives and experiences of affective technology, whether or not real time emotion regulation technology would be useful/accurate and how it could be best implemented into practice.

2.3 Ethical Considerations

The following section outlines vital ethical considerations, ethical challenges and how these were overcome. In the past decade, autism researchers have made a shift towards including autistic people within research that is for them and about them. This participatory research has been greatly approved of by the autistic community, and an important change which emphasizes the important of an inclusive society. Daley & Singhal et al, (2013) argue that a greater focus on ethics in Autism research will result in studies which are more relevant to Autistic people and their families. Likewise, many researchers argue that including the Autistic voice in Autism research enhances the research design process and increases validity (Milton, 2017).

Ensuring the current project was ethically sound and fully inclusive was of utmost importance. Taking into account the heterogeneity of Autism, with individuals having different abilities, often involving physical and social challenges that have created misconceptions about their ability to communicate and engage in research (Hills et al, 2019) thorough attention to research design is imperative when considering ethics and practicalities, for example when determining if the individual has capacity to give their own consent. Designing ethical and inclusive research requires an understanding of differences in communication, sensory and information processing abilities.

Therefore the current project was adapted appropriately to ensure inclusion, respect, and empowerment of participants.

Embedded throughout the current project is an adherence to the Draft Framework for inclusive research (Chown et al, (2017). This framework (see Table 1 below) is in line with and validated by the draft Code of Practice for researchers developed by the Shaping Autism Research project (Hampton & Fletcher-Watson 2016), of which the current project also strived to adhere to.

Table 1: General recommendations for inclusive research and how they were adhered to in the current research

Draft Framework for Inclusive Research (Chown et al, 2017)	Actions taken in the current project
A researcher with autism either identifies and defines the matter(s) requiring investigation or confirms the identification and definition of the problem by others	To ensure that the autistic perspective was considered in terms of the validity of the project, qualitative focus groups were carried out to assess if the development of real time affect detection technology was warranted/needed. Participants expressed that such technology must be reliable/accurate and consequently the quantitative phase aimed to assess both the feasibility and accuracy of using physiological signals (EEG) to identify affective states. In this way, the direction of the second

	phase of the project was determined by the Autistic community.
Social model of disability at the heart of the project ethos	The thesis is firmly situated within the social model of disability
Projects are either owned or jointly owned by representatives of the autism community	The current project was in collaboration with The National Autistic Society and ENABLE Scotland (Scotland's leading disability charity). Both of these organisations were involved in assisting with participant recruitment, although they did not directly sponsor the project.
Research outcomes are focused on improving the lives of people with autism	The over-arching goal of the project was to inform the design and implementation of EEG-based affect detection technology aimed at supporting Autistic emotion regulation. This goal was focused on informing technology design that is autonomous, promotes independence and provides support rather than 'fixing'.

The current research strived to meet all of the above recommendations if possible. The Draft Code of Practice for researchers developed by the Shaping Autism Research project (Hampton and Fletcher-Watson 2016) aims to cultivate more inclusive and ethical practice within Autism research, advocating that such guidelines are likely to result in improved outcomes for autistic individuals and their care givers. The current research is ethically based on both the Draft Code of Practice (2016)

and The Draft Framework for Inclusive Research (2017). Future work should also base any development of technological interventions on the framework of evidence-based practice for digital support outlined by Zervogianni & Fletcher-Watson et al, (2020).

Power differentials and consent processes

Concerns regarding power differentials and consent processes are reported in the literature (Phelan & Kinsella 2013; Richman, 2019). Every effort was made to ensure that power differentials were reduced. For example, one of the main benefits of carrying out focus groups (particularly with Autistic individuals) is that the power dynamics that usually occur between the researcher and participant are reduced in a focus group setting. A key principle of participatory research is the recognition, and attempt to reduce the power imbalance conventionally known to be between researcher and participant (Nelson & Wright, 1995).

By reflecting on the key ‘topics in participatory autism research’ outlined in the Draft Code of Practice (Hampton & Fletcher-Watson, 2016) the current research sought to reduce any perceived differences in power between the participants and the researcher. The framework outlines solutions to barriers which may present during participatory research, these include assumptions, respect, authenticity, infrastructure and empathy. This framework was considered when obtaining consent from participants. Research guidelines suggest that informed consent should help participants understand ‘the process in which they are to be engaged, including why their participation is necessary, how it will be used and how and to whom it will be reported’ (BERA 2011). Information sheets for all phases of the project were given to participants and included a combination of different formats (words, pictures) to accommodate for varying abilities and information processing styles. Participants were also verbally briefed about what each study would involve, via email, in person and in a group setting – this allowed participants to communicate their decision to different

people and in different contexts before signing a consent form. This is in line with recommendations set out by Loyd (2013)⁶. Furthermore, discussions were had between the researcher and people who know the autistic individual well e.g parents, carer or support staff to ensure the individual would be fully able to understand what would be involved and be able to give their own consent (Scott-Barrett et al, 2019).

It was beneficial to reflect on Milton's 'Double empathy theory' (Milton, 2012; Milton, 2020) during the research process and specifically when interacting with Autistic individuals to ensure they felt comfortable participating in the research. In line with The Draft Code of Practice (Hampton and Fletcher-Watson 2016), Milton places focus on empathy during the research process and conceptualizes it as 'a two way street' – in this sense, any communication challenges between the researcher and autistic participant should be seen as shared. Fletcher-Watson & Bird (2020) also suggests that there has previously been a mis-characterisation of Autistic people lacking empathy, when in fact the perceived lack of empathy is more likely to be due to reacting in a different way than what would be expected of a neurotypical individual. In the current project, inclusive adaptations were put in place to cater to different communication styles (e.g easy read information sheets and pictures). This ensured any participants who may have had any additional learning needs were fully informed about what each study would involve, in a respectful and empowering way. Additionally, it was important for the researcher to be introduced to participants prior to the experiments taking place, this further reduced any power differentials as it ensured participants felt more comfortable in interacting with the researcher and allowed extra time for any questions to be answered.

Furthermore, protocols were put in place to 'avoid the risk of coercion and exploitation while maximizing autonomy and inclusion' (Nicolaidis et al, 2019). Both qualitative and quantitative phases of the research involved protocols outlining the procedure for each phase of the research. This

⁶ Loyd (2013) outlines considerations and recommendations for obtaining consent from Autistic young people for the purpose of participating in Autism research

ensured a high standard of ethical practice and were reviewed and refined by each member of the research committee.

2.4 The Interdisciplinary Approach

The interdisciplinary nature of the project involved adopting methods from two distinct disciplines (psychology and computer science) which are rarely employed together. Developing real time technology based on physiological signals is a multifaceted challenge and this thesis attempts to draw on the strengths of each field to address such challenges. The unique advantage of this interdisciplinary approach is that insight was provided into not only the qualitative lived experiences of Autistic people, but also the practical and technical implications that real time technology present.

Historically, the fields of psychology and computer science (specifically Human Computer Interaction) have been underpinned by different fundamental paradigms, philosophical perspectives, theoretical frameworks and methodological approaches. It is therefore not surprising that communication and collaboration between the two has been lacking (Hannibal & Weiss, 2020).

One of the challenges of this work has been that it is not situated solely within one discipline with well established procedures and protocols for research design. As MacKay & Fayard (1997) state in their paper outlining a framework for triangulation across disciplines: “We work at both applied and theoretical levels and select methods that seem most appropriate for the problem at hand. At the same time we must conduct our work that is fundamentally sound at the level of each discipline we draw from and viewed as legitimate by our academic colleagues”.

2.5 Reflexive Statement

Reflexivity within the research process places importance on the researchers own interpretation of the data and emphasises how research rigour and integrity may be improved by adopting a reflexive

approach (Palaganas et al, 2017). The following section will outline a reflexive statement, including how my own life experiences may have impacted the research.

Prior to starting the PhD and during the first two years of it, I worked in community care settings supporting people with both physical and mental disabilities including Autistic people. I specialised in training health/social care staff to manage 'challenging behaviours' (developing support strategies for Autistic people, often with co-existing diagnoses and who often required 24hr care). This work sparked my passion for improving the quality of care for Autistic people. Since I had a great deal of experience within service provision, the PhD provided an ideal opportunity to pursue my interest in bridging the gap between academic research and practice.

The idea that technology could be used to help identify frustration and stress far enough in advance to incorporate strategies to alleviate emotional distress seemed like it could have so much potential. I especially related to this idea since I had seen how individuals and staff sometimes struggled to manage these situations. I was interested to know whether or not this could actually be beneficial in practice and more importantly – I wanted to know what Autistic people thought about it.

The interdisciplinary nature of this PhD allowed me to answer these questions as I was able to explore (from a computer science perspective) whether or not such emotion detection systems are reliable and (from a participatory qualitative view) opinions from the Autistic community on whether or not this type of technology is wanted/needed and if so, how it could be of maximum benefit. Combining these methods from two very different disciplines was a unique approach that to my knowledge, is highly original. It also allowed me to answer complex questions that one discipline alone could not. On reflection, it was an exciting time to be embarking on an Autism focused project, with so many new ideas and theories that challenge what has previously been thought about Autism coming to light.

As my PhD progressed, so did the rise of the neurodiversity movement and a huge change in narrative about how Autistic people should be viewed in society. This confirmed for me that my

ideas and direction for my thesis was in line with current empirical research and well situated within a social model of disability. The use of language and terminology became an important area of debate (with many researchers arguing for identity first language). Due to my previous experiences within service provision, I was already aware of the power and importance of language, however this debate and change in how researchers referred to Autism (as opposed to Autism Spectrum Disorder) was a chance for me to re-evaluate my own language use and adapt it accordingly. I have therefore used inclusive and respectful language throughout this thesis and intend to always reflect on how I can improve. As Vivanti (2020) states:

'Far from being mere semantics, this distinction has practical implications, as the words that we use to describe individuals with an autism diagnosis influence societal perceptions, public policy, clinical practice, and research directions',

During the research design and pilot stages of the quantitative phase I was keen to adopt a participatory approach and sought feedback from Autistic participants regarding the experiment design, set-up and protocol. This is something I hadn't planned on implementing from the start of the PhD, however as my knowledge of inclusive Autism research progressed, I decided that it was important to determine how the experiment design, set-up and protocol may impact sensory differences. This enabled me to make some changes to the experiment set-up/protocol, for instance – ensuring to ask whether or not the individual would like the lighting turned off or if the sound of the computer would be an issue. Adapting the sensory environment to individual needs was important to me to ensure participants felt comfortable.

3 Technological Interventions to Support Autistic Social and Emotional Communication: A Systematic Literature Review

3.1 Chapter Introduction

As outlined in the previous chapters, the past two decades have seen huge advances in technologies that aim to support Autistic social and emotional communication. Although this is a positive step as society is becoming more aware of what Autism is and how people can be supported, there is a need for such developments to become more in line with Autistic needs, preferences and priorities. While many other forms of behavioural support strategies such as positive behaviour support (PBS) and applied behavioural analysis (ABA) have proved to be unsuccessful/unpopular for Autistic people, technology may provide unique opportunities for more autonomous and individualised support. However, due to the heterogenous nature of Autism one of the key challenges for technology developers has been to develop person-centered designs which are able to meet a wide variety of needs.

The aim of this Chapter is to provide a broad review of previous literature on Autistic technology use. In order to understand the rationale for focusing on real time technology based on physiological signals in the subsequent Chapters, it is first important to understand and explore how Autistic people have used and use technology more generally. Therefore, this chapter will focus on four main types of technology use: Robotics, Virtual Reality, Computer Based and Mobile Apps.

This chapter provides (1) a review of studies using digital technology that aim to support social and emotional communication in Autistic people from 2014-2022. (2) Insight into the advantages and challenges in technology development aimed at Autistic socio-emotional communication is also

explored. (3) Direction for future research is also provided, focusing on combining key disciplines (psychology, computer science and health) to bridge the gap between affective technology design and successful outcomes for Autistic people.

3.2 Background Literature and Rationale

As discussed in previous chapters, Autism is a neurological condition defined by diagnostic criteria including difficulties in social and emotional interactions (Baio et al, 2018). Varying cognitive processes in Autism (attention, memory and information processing) are intertwined in complex ways with language and communication functioning, resulting in varying needs and abilities (Rice et al, 2012). Around three-quarters of Autistic people are reported to have below average IQ (< 70), however Autistic individuals can also have average and above average IQ (Joseph et al, 2002). Autism can also be characterized by sensory processing challenges that can mean avoiding or seeking-out of sensory stimuli (e.g. tactile, olfactory, visual, proprioceptive, auditory, gustatory), altering the individuals' perceptual experience (Tracey, 2018). This includes the sensory processing of aesthetic experiences, noise, smell, pain, and other people's moods or feelings (Grimen & Diseth, 2016). The prevalence of sensory processing difficulties may be as high as 90% in Autistic people (Baker et al, 2008) and have been linked to poor mental health (Suzuki & Takagai, 2019). Variations in interpretation and organization of sensory information may produce differences in development, informational processing, communication and behaviour. Indeed, Autistic people often report frustration as a direct result of social and emotional communication issues. This needs to be taken into account when considering how affective technology design can be most beneficial for individuals of varying levels of both sensory and socio-emotional functioning.

Increased anxiety levels and emotion regulation difficulties have been linked to autonomic nervous system activation (ANS) as many Autistic people experience an outward appearance of being calm and relaxed whilst experiencing heightened arousal internally (Picard, 2009; Goodwin et al, 2006)

Emotion regulation (ER) can be defined as the ability to modulate emotion (experienced and expressed) to allow goal directed or value based behaviour (White et al., 2014). ER therefore impacts the duration, intensity and types of emotions we experience (Gross & John, 2003) and plays an essential role in all facets of the emotional experience, from the appraisal of emotional stimuli to emotional reactions. Autistic individuals present more emotion regulation problems than their typically developing peers (Cai et al, 2018). Empirical evidence suggests that Autistic individuals are less able to emotionally regulate both in terms of experiencing and expressing emotions (Bruggink et al., 2016). Impaired ER may underpin some of the behavioural problems for example, (Samson et al, 2015) found that Autistic children and adolescents were more likely to hide emotions and show less reappraisal than non-autistic peers. The combination of internal biological state with compromised experience of emotion and issues in communication can lead to frustration and 'challenging behaviours' (Zantinge et al, 2017).

'Challenging Behaviours' in Autism

'Challenging behaviours' is an umbrella term which encompasses acts such as restricted behaviours, aggression to others and self-injury (McClintock et al, 2003). 'Challenging behaviours, usually caused by frustration and stress are experienced by around 10-20% of Autistic people, and are reported to be more prevalent in adolescence (Emerson et al, 2001; Oliver et al, 1987).

Historically, the term 'challenging behaviours' has resulted a common misconception that Autistic people may act aggressively for no reason. However, recent advances in Autism research take account of the bidirectional issues in Autistic/Non-Autistic interactions and place importance on external adaptations to support and meet needs. The double empathy theory proposed by (Milton, 2012; Milton, 2018) suggests that there is a mutual misunderstanding between Autistic people and non-autistic people in social communications rather than an autism-specific 'deficit'. Recent research

has found that skills previously labelled as Autistic 'deficits', are instead a result of communication challenges that are experienced by both autistic/non-autistic people in their interactions with each other. These findings have important implications and must be considered in the design and implementation of affective technologies aiming to support social interactions for autistic people (Fletcher & Bird, 2019).

In the past two decades, many new and innovative technologies (e.g games/robotics/virtual reality/mobile apps) have been piloted and trialled as interventions to support Autistic social and emotional communication (Alabdulkareem, & Alhakbani, 2022). Howard, & Sedgewick (2021) found that online technology use was a key mode of communication for Autistic adults & had a positive impact on their lives. Several studies have also found positive benefits of technology use, e.g the use of robotics to assist in therapy sessions for Autistic children (Alabdulkareem & Alhakbani, 2022) and serious games to improve social and emotional skills (for a systematic review see: Ahmed & Pinkwart, 2021) . However, the promise of these interventions has not been reflected in successful social and emotional outcomes for Autistic people in practice.

Despite the increasing promise of new and innovative technological solutions to support Autistic social and emotional communications, success remains varied. Several previous systematic reviews exploring Autistic social and emotional communication have focused on solely one specific technology type, e.g mobile applications, robotics, computer, sensor technology based or virtual reality (see the following for examples; Alabdulkareem & Alhakbani (2022), Mesa-Gresa et al, 2018; Kowallik & Schweinberger, 2019; Noor et al, 2012; Ploog et al, 2013; Wainer & Ingersoll, 2011). Likewise, a recent systematic review focused on technology for Autistic people, however only in educational contexts (Valencia et al, 2019). This study therefore aims to expand on previous research by considering a wider variety of technologies across a variety of contexts.

The contributions of this chapter include:

- A systematic search method is used to provide a review of studies using digital technology that aim to support social and emotional communication in Autistic people from 2014-2022.
- We provide insight into the advantages and challenges in technology development aimed at Autistic socio-emotional communication
- Direction for future research is provided, focusing on combining key disciplines (psychology, computer science and health) to bridge the gap between affective technology design and successful outcomes for Autistic people.

3.3 METHOD

This review followed the guidance for Systematic Reviews (PRISMA) statement, outlined by Liberati, Tetzlaff, Altman, & Prisma Group (2009).

Search Method

Five databases, Science direct, EBSCOhost: CINAHL Complete, MEDLINE, APA PsycArticles and IEEE affective computing (2014-2022) were searched individually and a separate search for each technology type was carried out in order to identify a wider variety of studies. Searches for each database were carried out e.g: Robotics: (Autism* or ASD*) AND (Improved social skills* or improved emotional skills*) AND (communication*). (For a full outline of the search strategy please see Appendix A).

The PRISMA flow diagram (figure 2) shows the search process and the inclusion and exclusion of studies at each stage and Table 2 outlines the search strategy for each database.

Identification of studies via databases

Figure 2. PRISMA flow diagram of studies included and excluded

Table 2: Search Strategy for Each Database

A separate search was carried out for each technology type	Search Term
Robotics	(Autism* or ASD*) AND (Improved social skill* or improved emotional skill*) AND (communication*) AND (Technolog*)
Computer Based	(Autism* or ASD*) AND (Improved social skills* or improved emotional skills*) AND (communication*) AND (Technolog*)
Virtual Reality	(Autism* or ASD*) AND (Improved social skills* or improved emotional skills*) AND (communication*) AND (Technolog*)
Mobile Applications	(Autism* or ASD*) AND (Improved social skills* or improved emotional skills*) AND (communication*) AND (Technolog*)

All studies identified were exported to reference management software Mendeley, for duplicates to be removed. Titles and abstracts of the remaining studies were read in order to identify articles according to the inclusion and exclusion criteria (See Table 3 outlined below).

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Table 3: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Implement an intervention with the primary intervention component delivered via technology	Studies published prior to 2014 were excluded so as to focus on studies involving technology still relevant to the present day
The type of technology used must be computer based, mobile apps, robotics or virtual reality	Studies that do not use non-invasive technology
The study must aim to improve social or emotional skills in children or adolescents with Autism.	Studies in which computers were used solely as a means to deliver a video model
Participants must have a pre-existing diagnosis of autism	Qualitative studies will not be included

Data Extraction & Synthesis

Data extracted from studies included: authors, year of publication, participants information (age range, gender, sample size) intervention information (type and aims, target behaviour, duration and setting, control group characteristics), findings/effects on lived experience of the user, study limitations and technology type. An overview of sample characteristics for each identified article is provided in Table 3. Types of technologies were categorized into one of four groups: 1) Computer-based, which included interventions on a computer or laptop including serious games. 2) Robotics, which included studies using a humanoid robot as the primary intervention. 3) Virtual Reality, which included computer simulated reality interactive systems. 4) Mobile/Tablet Applications, defined as any hand held wireless device.

Quality Assessment

The McMaster Critical Review Form for Quantitative Studies was used to assess methodological quality of studies. This was originally developed by Law et al, (1998) and revised by (Letts et al, 2007). This tool has been widely used in other systematic reviews for intervention studies and has good inter-rater reliability (Wells et al, 2014). Selected questions were based on three recent systematic reviews that also appraised the quality of studies involving Autistic individuals (Sutto et al, 2019; Westerveld et al, 2016; Wiese et al, 2016). Studies were rated numerically with Yes = 2, Partially = 1, No or N/A = 0. Questions that assessed the methodological quality of each study are outlined below. (For the full quality assessment table please see Appendix 1, for the quality assessment guidelines please see appendix 3).

1. Is the study design relevant to address the study aim?
2. Is the sample size described in detail?
3. Is the sample size justified?
4. Is there identified potential sample/subject selection bias?
5. Is the intervention described in detail?
6. Are the outcomes measures valid and reliable?
7. Are the results reported in terms of statistical significance (including effect size)?

3.4 Summary of studies aimed at supporting Autistic socio-emotional communication via Technology

A key aim of the systematic review was to identify studies using digital technology that aimed to support social and emotional communication in Autistic people from 2014-2022. The search identified 546 studies following the removal of duplicates. Of these, there were 28 studies that met

the inclusion and exclusion criteria. The 28 studies included 705 participants (age range 4-63 years).

Summaries of each of these studies are presented in the table below.

3.4.1 Participant Characteristics

Three studies failed to report the gender of participants in their sample. Table 4 below outlines the age range, gender and how many autistic participants were recruited across all the selected studies.

Figure 3 below outlines Technology type across selected studies and Figure 4 below outlines selected studies published by year.

Table 4: Age Range and Gender Across Selected Studies

Total Participants	748
Age Range	Age range in all studies was 2-16years, with the exception of Cassidy, Stenger, Dongen et al (2016) with an age range of 19-63 Overall age range = 2-63 years
Overall Gender (M/F)	M=559 F=146
Autistic Gender (M/F)	M=541 F=119

Figure 3. Technology Type Across Selected Studies

Figure 4. Selected Studies from 2014-2022

Virtual Reality

Of the three selected studies focused on using virtual reality to improve socio-emotional communication (summary in Table 1) 82 participants took part. The age range was 7 to 16 years old. Two studies included an experimental group and control group. An advantage of using VR in interventions is that it can be used to mimic social or emotional real life environments in order for the user to participate in role play and allowing them to rehearse social or emotional situations (Parsons et al, 2000). Didehbani et al (2016) highlight the value of using real-time feedback in interventions that involve emotional skills in order to improve social cognition. A summary of selected studies using VR is outlined in Table 5 below.

Table 5: Summary of Selected Studies using VR Technology

Author	Type of intervention	Target Behaviour	Participants	Findings/Effects on lived experience of user	Limitations
Lorenzo, Lledo & Pomares et al (2016)	Immersive VR reality environment aiming to improve emotional skills in Autism	Emotional Skills	Autistic children (N=40), aged 7-12 Experimental group: (N=34) Control group: (N=20)	Increased 'appropriate emotional behaviours' in immersive virtual reality environments compared with desktop virtual reality systems. Suggests that skills learned in VR can be transferred to real life settings.	Participants in experimental & control groups were not matched on social/sensory profiles, which may have influenced results
Wong & Chan (2018)	VR social cognition training to enhance social skills	Social Skills	Autistic children and adolescents (N=30) aged 1-16	Improvements in emotion recognition, social attribution, executive functioning and analogical reasoning	The VR technology was not able to interact in real time. Results could have been due to stimulation or attention rather than the intervention
Lahiri, Bekele & Dohrmann (2015)	Using meaningful, close to real life scenarios and dynamic range of social interactions with immediate feedback	Social Skills	Autistic adolescents (N=12) Intervention group (N=8) Control group (N=4)	Results showed that physiological informed technologies have potential to be accepted by Autistic adolescents.	The method used for conversation with avatar used a drop down menu, which does not reflect real life. Only children with above average intelligence could take part.

The findings reflect a major limitation of current VR interventions, which is that scenarios used in most studies are too specific to be generalised (Horace et al, 2018). For example, most VR technologies will be limited to training particular subskills of social competency e.g, spatial awareness, problem solving, emotion recognition resulting in repetitive practicing of the same subskill; a training environment which is less likely to reflect real life social interactions. Only a few studies have investigated performance in social interactions in which Autistic people would normally encounter in typical daily life. However research in this area is progressing as technology advances; some recent studies have used more advanced VR technology which allows for a more vivid and interactive virtual environment creating a more immersive experience for the user. Results showed that after the intervention, social competences and executive functions had improved. Several studies have used VR to investigate facial recognition (Ben Ammar et al, 2010; Madsen et al, 2008); whereas others have attempted to improve facial recognition by investigating eye gaze or brain changes (Harms et al, 2010). Furthermore, the majority of virtual reality interventions are focused solely on a specific age group without considering the potential implications of designing a universal VR system that would be suitable and adaptable for all ages, needs and abilities. Although interventions should consider different stages of development, the design of a single system would benefit a wider population.

In summary, many VR studies have been aimed at 'practicing and improving' social skills for Autistic individuals. Whilst interventions that provide opportunities to support Autistic people in daily life may be beneficial, a large number of these studies have not been situated within a social model of disability or within a neurodiversity paradigm, and as such may not be relevant to Autistic needs, wants or preferences. Challenges also remain, such as clarifying the usefulness and effectiveness of VR interventions due to limited sample size and lack of generalizability and single user design (Didibahni et al, 2016). Furthermore, many questions still remain and should be a focus for future studies, for example, it is not clear how these VR interventions implemented in such controlled environments

would transfer into real life situations or how the benefits would last over time. Additionally many VR studies focused on eye-gaze technology involve wearable eye trackers and use of a computer mouse, therefore may not be so suitable of children or adolescents who have more complex needs.

Computer Based/Serious Game

Table 6: Summary of Selected Studies using Computer-based/Serious Games

Author	Type of intervention	Target Behaviour	Participants	Findings/Effects on lived experience of user	Limitations
Rice, Wall & Schick (2015)	FaceSay' intervention involves games to teach social skills. Activities are based on face recognition, eye gaze, emotional cognition & attention.	Improved social skills (eye gaze, joint attention & facial recognition)	Autistic school children aged 5-11 (N=15) Total participants: (N=31) Male:28, Female: 3	Significant difference in post-test affect recognition. Significant increase in affect recognition and mentalizing abilities. Teacher-observed social impairment was reduced.	Does not use dynamic facial expressions or more complex emotions. Since it was conducted in a lab, results may not transfer to real life.
Kossyvakis & Curran (2020)	Technology based intervention combined with music	Aimed to improve social communication	Autistic children (N=5) aged 5-7 years	Results showed positive outcomes particularly for social communication	No control group
Matsuda & Yamamoto (2014)	Computer based MTS 'matching to sample training method'	Improved emotion recognition (facial expression)	Autistic children (N=2) aged 4 and 7. Both with complex needs. Males: 2	The relationships between situations involving socio-emotional interactions and facial expressions can be trained	No follow-up evaluation. Although training showed improvement, no participants had 100% correct answers indicating that further training would be needed

Bernardini Porayska-Pomsta & Smith (2014)	ECHOES' Serious game to improve social skills. Large scale multi-site intervention	Improved social skills	Autistic children/Adolescents aged 4-14 (N=29).	One of the first studies to evaluate a serious game. Input from teachers and practitioners. Some evidence of children benefiting as a whole.	No control group. No significant increase in real life social skills were observed.
White, Abbott & Wieckowski (2018)	Prototype system (pilot study) game	Improved emotional skills (facial emotion recognition).	Autistic children (N=70) aged 9-12. Autistic group (N=20), typically developing (N=50).	Technology proved feasible with Autistic children. Satisfaction ratings were high.	Prototype only. No follow-up evaluation to assess improvement in social or emotional skills
Malinverni et al (2017)	Game aimed at improving social initiation. Exploratory intervention study.	Improved social skills	Autistic children (N=10) All males aged 9-10 years.	Results showed increased behaviours associated with social interaction e.g smiling, eye contact, talking to the other child, imitation, sharing of emotions.	Ages of participants were not the target users. Does not include evaluation of how transferable the skills are to everyday life.
Mairena et al (2019)	Game based intervention that aimed to compare the amount of social initiation during free play and during a video game.	Improved social skills	Autistic children (N=15) aged 4-6 years	Results showed higher social initiation, reduced repetitive behaviours and increased gestures in the videogame category compared with free play.	Raters who coded the observational scale may have been influenced by subjective perceptions. No control group or evaluation of transferrable skills.

Petrovska & Trajkovski (2019)	RCT evaluating a computer based intervention for improved emotional understanding	Improved emotional skills	Autistic children, both with and without intellectual disability (N=32) aged 7-15 years. Intervention group (N=16) Control group (N=16)	Positive effects were found in emotion recognition from real face photographs and pictograms and improved understanding in situation based emotion.	Does not explore if improved skills are transferrable to everyday life.
Beaumont & Walker (2021)	Parent-supported adaption of the computer game-based social skills program Secret Agent Society (SAS)	Improved social skills	Autistic children (N=70) Males=60 Females=10	SAS group improved more than control group in parent-rated/teacher-rated social skills & 'problem behaviours'.	Parent/Teacher Self-report measures may be susceptible to bias
Dantas & Nascimento (2022).	Game to help Autistic children recognise emotions & express 6 basic emotions: sadness, anger, joy, disgust, surprise, fear.	Improved emotional skills	Autistic children aged 6-12 (N=8) Males=4 Females=4	An improvement in emotion identification scores was observed when compared to baseline data. Loss of focus decreased throughout the 'maintenance stage' apart from 1 participant.	It is unknown if the results would be applicable to real life scenarios. No real-time feedback to participants.

Serious games can be defined as a game with a primary purpose other than entertainment (Susi et al, (2007). Empirical evidence to date suggests that computer based/Serious games are indeed effective in training social and emotional skills in Autistic children and adolescents (Grynszpan et al,

2014). Furthermore, technology that seems to be more for entertainment, may in fact also play a vital role in calming or relaxing Autistic individuals (Lawire & Warreyn et al, 2019). This may explain why the highest % of selected studies in the current review were computer based/games. Rice et al (2015) developed an intervention known as 'Facesay' which used games to teach social skills to Autistic children. This was a computer based intervention practising simulated activities, targeting eye gaze, joint attention, emotional cognition and facial emotion recognition skills. Results showed a significant difference in post-test emotion recognition in Autism compared to non-autistic peers. However, despite showing potential in helping Autistic children recognise emotions, generalisability of the results was limited as these improvements did not transfer to the class room environment. Likewise, although Dantas & Nascimento (2022) found that emotion recognition improved following the intervention, it is unknown if such results would be applicable to real life situations. A common issue with the reviewed studies is that they are aimed at 'improving' social or emotional skills. Although many studies are intended to support Autistic people and may be beneficial, devices may have higher success if they are situated within a neurodiversity framework.

It is also important to note that although technology design is crucial in the success of interventions, the implementation process must also be considered i.e. where and how. Huijnen et al, (2017) highlight the importance of personalised intervention plans co-created by parents, educators and professionals. Additionally, children with more complex needs may find that interventions introduced at a slower pace over a period of time will result in improved outcomes. Likewise, some children may need to practice using the intervention in different places (home, school, activities) in order to gain benefit.

Furthermore, Matsuda & Yamamoto (2014) aimed to improve socio-emotional communication in young Autistic children through the use of a computer based matching to sample (MTS) training

system. Children were asked to match movies of socio-emotional situations and corresponding pictures of facial expressions via a computer based system. Results showed that Autistic children succeeded in matching four emotions (sad, surprised, angry and happy). Results transferred to improved performance in untrained relationships, which suggests that observing social situations is not enough for improved performance, but that MTS training was necessary. However, no follow-up sessions were carried out. Bernardini et al, (2014) designed a serious game aimed at improving social communication skills in young Autistic children through the use of an interactive game. A digital social partner was created to act as both a peer and to teach children, interacting in real-time. Bernardini et al (2014) contend that although individuals may intend to use technology, actual use does not always reflect this.

Additionally, Smitha & Vinod (2015) also developed a system to give real-time feedback to Autistic children. A portable device which detects facial emotions from Autistic children and is able to give feedback when communicating with parents/care takers. However, a limitation was that there was no evaluation or follow up methods put in place. Silva et al, (2014) provide insight into the design of multi-user games with collaboration patterns created with the specific requirements of individuals with Autism. Future research should focus on this type of multi-user design combined with real-time feedback, in order to develop interventions which better reflect real life and are able to meet specific individual requirements of Autistic children and adolescents.

Overall, most previous research has focused on 'teaching' these skills in a fun and interactive manner. More recent research has introduced real-time feedback which creates a more personalised experience, increasing control and independence for the user. However, this approach is still in early stages and future research should focus on more robust evaluation methods and place more

emphasis on 'how' and 'where' interventions are implemented/if they are being implemented according to individual needs.

Robotics

There were 8 studies selected (summarised in Table 7) that focused on technology involving the use of robotics in interventions aimed at supporting Autistic socio-emotional communication. Only one of these studies was specifically aimed at emotional skills (i.e improving emotion recognition) with the remaining 7 studies focused more on social interaction or both social and emotional communication (e.g improved eye contact, social behaviours, functional play). All studies in this category included control groups, however in most cases it would be difficult to determine if improved communication skills would be permanent. All studies included low sample sizes, although this tends to be common in Autistic digital intervention research.

Table 7: Summary of Selected Studies using Robotics

Author	Type of intervention	Target Behaviour	Participants	Findings/Effects on lived experience of user	Limitations
David et al (2020)	Five single subject experiments were carried out to assess a robot enhanced intervention on turn taking abilities.	Improved social skills	Autistic children (N=11) aged 3-5 years. Males = 3 Females = 2	Children showed similar level of performance on both standard intervention and intervention including the robot. However participants found robotic partner more interesting/had more eye contact than a human partner	Does not include any follow up evaluation or assessment of transferrable skills to everyday life.
Wing-Cheeso et al (2020)	Robot based play drama intervention to assess social skills (joint attention & play behaviours)	Improved social skills	Autistic children (N=23) Intervention (N=12) Control Group (N=11)	Significant improvements in joint attention initiations and functional play behaviours in the intervention group. Parents also reported improved social skills	Challenges with social skills are heterogeneous, therefore there may have been differences in target outcomes. Children were high functioning, therefore unclear if the intervention would be suitable across the spectrum
Srinivasan, Eigsti & Gilford (2016)	Comparison of robotics, movement based and rhythm interventions aimed at improving social skills.	Improved social skills	Autistic children (N=36) aged 5-12 Robot group (N=12) Comparison group (N=12)	The post intervention measures showed that children in the rhythm and robot groups had more social verbalization.	Effect sizes are not correct. Large confidence intervals. No follow up measure

Yun, Choi & Park et al (2017)	Robot assisted interventions to facilitate social skills for Autistic children.	Improved social skills	Autistic children aged 4-7. (N=15) Included Control group	Improved eye contact and emotion recognition. Similar positive effects in both groups	
Cassidy, Stenger, Dongen et al (2016)	Xpressive Talk (Near video realistic avatar)	Improved emotional skills	Autistic children aged 3-6 (N=8) Control group (N=3)	Both groups were significantly more accurate when inferring sad emotions from Xpressivetalk. Autistic group rated more preferred and realistic	Actress was used to investigate emotion recognition accuracy which may not reflect real life emotional expressions
Bonccanfus o, Scarborough h & Abramson et al (2016)	Multidisciplinary pilot study using socially assistive robot (game included) aiming to increase speech and social skills	Improved social skills.	Autistic children aged 3-6 (N=8). Control group (N=3, aged 3-6).	Significantly improved social and communication skills (Improvements in subscales of coping and interpersonal skills were found).	Low sample size. Skewness in control group for communication post-test and socialization pre-test
Ghiglini & Chevalier et al (2021)	Investigated effects of including robotic toy within therapy sessions	Improved social skills	Autistic children (N=24) Males= 19 Females = 5	Combination of robot assisted training was more effective than therapy alone (improved ability to respond to requests. make non-verbal requests, initiating/maintaining social interactions with adults).	Small sample size, high dropout rate. The use of ESCS may have reduced strength of results.
Laurie & Manches et al (2021)	Explored digital features (robotic toy) and joint attention in fostering social interactions.	Improved social interaction	Autistic children (N=7) Males=7 Females=0	Technology may intrinsically support more socially interactive play	Small sample size. Groups were not matched on social profiles; this may have impacted

					results more than technology
Pinto-Bernal & Cespedes et al (2022)	Investigated the use on a social robotic platform based on soft actuation to encourage physical interaction (participatory design)	Improved social skills	Autistic children (N=35) Intervention group: Males 14, Females 4 Control group: Males, 14, Females, 3	No significant differences in social/emotional response, however healthcare staff noted a more positive influence on physical interaction in the intervention group. Overall, a social robot may improve therapist-child interaction.	A short-term study and therefore the longer term impact is unknown.

In summary, progress in advancing robotic interventions as clinically valuable and worthwhile in interventions for individuals with Autism has been limited (Begum et al, 2016). This could be due to many studies aiming interventions towards ‘improving’ socio-emotional skills, as opposed to ‘supporting’ socio-emotional communication. A further explanation for this could be methodological limitations within human-robot interaction (HRI) studies; many HRI studies lack a robust or standardised research design, therefore data produced is less appealing to clinicians. Clinical research on Autism intervention is generally based on a systematic evaluation of evidence and geared towards rigorous research design such as randomised control trails (RCTs) (White et al, 2007; Kouijzer et al, (2013). These results suggest that robots may be useful in supporting social communication, however more research is needed to ascertain whether or not such interventions would be accepted by the Autistic community. All of the identified studies were aimed at social communication which is in line with Kouroupa & Laws, et al (2022). Kouroupa & Laws, et al (2022) carried out a meta-analysis on interventions involving social robots with Autistic children and young people and results showed that robot-mediated interventions significantly improved social functioning but not emotional functioning.

Mobile Applications

Table 8: Summary of Selected Studies using Mobile Applications

Author	Type of intervention	Target Behaviour	Participants	Findings/Effects on lived experience of user	Limitations
Zhang, Xia & Li, (2019)	Aimed to improve facial expression recognition and emotional understanding	Improved emotion recognition	Autistic children with (Total participants: 3, Male:1, Female:2; Age M = 4.94)	All participants showed significant improvements in social acuity. Results showed improvements on emotion distinguishing and understanding	Intervention was carried out in a lab setting, unclear if results would transfer to real life environments
Fletcher-Watson, Petrou, Scott-Berrett et al (2016)	A trial of an iPad™ intervention targeting social communication skills in children with autism (2016).	Application for ipad aiming to provide an early intervention for social skills and Improved social skills	Autistic children under age 6. (N=54) Intervention: (N=27) Control (N=27)	Results suggest touch- screen mobile devices should continue to be investigated. No significant differences between groups, both in parent report measures and measure of parent- child play at follow up	new measure was used as the primary outcome. No immediate post-intervention follow up was carried out
Chen, Lee & Lin (2016)	Tablet based training intervention which aimed to improve emotion recognition in social interactions	Improved social and emotional skills	Autistic adolescents aged 11-13 (N=6)	Through augmented reality based video modelling, children showed improved ability to recognise and understand emotions from facial expressions	Only used basic emotions. Low sample size. Only participants with no intellectual disability were included. No control group.
Gal et al (2016)	Storytable™ 3 week (11 session) Intervention	Improved social skills	Autistic children (high functioning)	Post intervention there were significantly	Low sample size. No control group

	using a multi touch interface		aged 7-12 years (N=14)	higher rates of positive social interaction with improvement maintained 3 weeks later	
Parsons, Cordier, Lee, Falkmer & Vaz (2019)	Exploratory RCT using a tablet based information communication technology (TOBY app) intervention app. 3 month intervention,	Improved social skills (also visual motor, imitation & language skills).	Autistic children (N=59) aged 2-6.	Results showed benefits in expressive language skills, significant gains in overall social skills.	Participant usage and time period of use of the app in the study was less than previous research (Whitehouse et al, 2017).
Smith & Constantin et al (2021)	A digitally mediated support strategy (SOFA-app) for 1 week. Explored the use of a social stories app for supporting users to adapt to change, during a summer camp	Social and emotional skills	Autistic children (N=10) Male=8 Female=2	Teacher ratings of anxiety, understanding and closeness to the goal of the support strategy were recorded pre and post intervention. Results showed improvements in all measures.	No objective measures of behaviour change, teacher ratings may be susceptible to bias

Interest in the use of mobile applications has grown massively in recent years, e.g iPhones, iPads and Android phones for individuals with ASD (Mintz, 2013). However, most of the research on apps for children with Autism focus on educational attainment e.g (Kalyani & Reddy, 2018) with a lack of focus on emotional or social skills. Many apps that use a mobile touchscreen device have been developed, e.g. Proloquo2Go (Sampath et al, 2012). Speech generating technology that involves mobile touchscreen devices and AAC Apps are extremely popular as they have the ability to include many pictures, their portable, and they are usually not expensive (Mirenda, 2009). Research has

shown that using mobile apps can allow Autistic children to make single or more complex requests (Achmadi et al, 2012) and to give responses in social interactions e.g. 'thank you' after they have made a requests (Waddington et al, 2014). These devices have expanded on more traditional methods (e.g picture cards) used by parents or health/social care workers (Bondy & Frost, 1994). As technology advances, mobile touchscreen devices with augmentative and alternative communication Apps are emerging as promising alternatives of traditional speech generating devices and picture exchange communication systems. Several studies have altered and improved the exhaustive training procedures of picture exchange communication systems for use in speech generating training with mobile devices (King et al, 2014).

For ezample, Chen et al (2016) used augmented reality (AR) based video modelling to reinforce and hold the attention of children with Autism when interacting non-verbally, as they have often have difficulties regulating their attentional focus. Results showed that AR technology was effective; Autistic children were better able to understand the facial expressions and emotions of the characters. However a major limitation with this study was that participants included children with ASD who had no intellectual disability, therefore not targeting children who would benefit most from the technology (low-functioning children with Autism) and impacting generalizability of results. Gal et al, (2015) found significantly higher rates of positive social interactions and collaborative play, rates of negative social interactions were also found to be lower following an intervention using a collaborative, multitouch tabletop interface. Similarly, Ahmad & Shahid (2015) found a positive effect on the development of socio-emotional skills of children through the use of a mobile app which was designed to be more culture specific for Pakistani children. Results showed that verbal and physical interaction among children was significantly higher when they used the app.

More recently, Krägeloh et al, (2018) carried out a review on how Autistic people use apps. Twenty-eight studies were identified which proposed the use of apps purposely created for Autistic people.

Results showed that the most commonly used app was a portable communication support app which aids speech, known as 'Proloquo2Go'. Other popular apps included life skills/social training as well as some behavioural based interventions, however there was a lack of focus on improving emotional skills.

Furthermore, Fletcher-Watson et al (2016) evaluated a technology-based (iPad app) intervention aimed at social communication skills in Autistic children. An advantage of this study was that it included both a control group and a follow up measure, however results showed no significant differences between the experimental group and control group in parent report measures after the interventions or in a measure of parent-child play in a follow up. Similarly, several other studies e.g (Golan et al., 2009; Hopkins et al., 2011; Williams et al., 2012) have found limited effect in real life social or emotional situations. Despite this, Fletcher-Watson et al. (2016) suggest that there were enough indications for further exploration. Additionally, Golan et al (2009) found that parents reported that children were more willing to talk about their emotions after the intervention. Future studies should consider that technology design and intervention implementation require more communication from stakeholders and researchers in computing, psychology and health to ultimately bridge the gap between learning in a game environment to real world interaction. Overall, it is clear that the evidence indicates feasibility of the use of mobile application to improve social and emotional skills. However many design issues remain (e.g personalisation) and methodological concerns (e.g lack of robust evaluations or randomised controlled trials). These issues must be addressed in order for this type of technology to advance.

3.5 Conclusion

Overall, in reviewing a variety of technologies across different contexts, this review provides a basis for bridging the gap between affective technology development and socio-emotional outcomes for

Autistic people. Firstly, the findings suggest that interventions to support social and emotional communication can be beneficial, however the results also highlight a lack of robust methodology/objective measures in intervention studies and found few examples of co participatory methods. Results showed many intervention studies were based on outdated models of Autism (i.e the medical model of Autism). This may explain why the usefulness of many technological supports are still currently debated and often show poor validity (for a meta-analysis see: Grynszpan & Weiss et al, 2014). In a recent study, Zervogianni & Fletcher-Watson et al (2023) also acknowledge these challenges, but argue that overall findings are positive. Indeed, although many of the technological supports discussed in the current study are not in line with current understandings of Autism, awareness of Neurodiversity and the importance of person-centered developments is increasing. Ultimately, these studies still provide a vital basis for future, more innovative designs that are co-designed alongside the Autistic community. Secondly, most studies were focused on males. An explanation for the high male to female ratio may be that historically woman have been misdiagnosed due to Autism stereotypes (Tint & Weiss, 2018). Moving forward in it is essential that there is a greater focus on Autistic woman in order to identify if they have different or specific needs.

A limitation of the current study was that the search was limited to studies published from 2014-2022 this decision was made in order to only include research based on the most recent technological advances. We also only searched five databases, therefore it's possible that some studies which may have met the criteria have been missed.

Despite these limitations important conclusions can be made. Firstly, there is a need for stronger interdisciplinary collaborations linking the methodologies adopted in Psychology and Health disciplines such as co participatory methods and advances within the neurodiversity movement (e.g double empathy theory) with the technological advances in the field of computer science. Second, it is vital that future research establishes effectiveness, efficacy and higher ecological validity across

larger samples of Autistic individuals taking into account feedback from the Autistic community at every stage of the research process i.e participatory design. This would also allow research to expand in order to create technologies that can support social and emotional communication across wider populations and variety of diagnoses. Thirdly, future work must consider 'how' technologies are being implemented, by taking into account Autistic communication preferences, environmental factors, varying sensory needs and consistency among parents/carers/teachers. Fourthly, autonomous technologies based on physiological signals may provide a unique opportunity to support Autistic emotion regulation as they would be able to give feedback in real time, as opposed to lab environments. Research in this area is currently in its infancy, however with technology advancing at speed, further exploration to ascertain the acceptability of such technology is vital. Overall, the current study provides insight and direction for improving the complex nature of technologies aimed at supporting Autistic socio-emotional communication.

4 “You feel like you kind of walk between the two worlds”: A participatory study exploring how technology can support social and emotional communication for Autistic people

4.1 Chapter Introduction

In the previous chapter, the Systematic Review concluded that (1) in order for technology to be successful and useful to Autistic people a participatory approach is vital and (2) real time technology based on physiological signals may be useful in support strategies aimed at emotion regulation. Results showed that an increasing number of technological solutions aiming to support emotion regulation are being developed for Autistic people. However, there remains a lack of understanding of user needs, and design factors which has led to poor usability and varied success. Furthermore, studies assessing the feasibility of emotion regulation technology via physiological signals for Autistic people are increasingly showing promise, yet to date there has been no qualitative exploration of views from the Autistic community on the benefits/challenges such technology may present in practice.

The current Chapter is based on these findings and takes a participatory approach to gain insight into experiences and expectations of technological supports aimed at supporting emotion regulation. Reflexive Thematic Analysis generated three themes: (1) Communication Challenges (2) Views on Emotion Regulation Technology (3) ‘How’ technology is implemented. Results provide meaningful insight into the socio-emotional communication challenges faced by Autistic people, and explore the expectations of technology aimed at supporting emotion regulation.

4.2 Background Literature and Rationale

Autism is defined as a complex neurodevelopmental condition characterised by social interaction and social communication difficulties, as well as repetitive behaviours and focused interests (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). In the past two decades, the neurodiversity movement has brought about a huge shift in Autism research, theory, and practice; viewing Autism as part of a neurodiversity continuum rather than a disorder (Leadbitter et al, 2021). Although both Autistic and non-Autistic people need and want meaningful friendships (Cresswell et al., 2019), different styles of communication often result in bi-directional issues in understanding and empathising with each other (Crompton et al., 2020; Sedgewick et al., 2019). These different ways of communicating have been referred to as the double empathy problem (Milton, 2012; Milton, 2018). Autistic socio-emotional communication is unique to each individual and dependant on multiple factors including level of ability and stage of development (Lodge et al., 2019).

High rates of anxiety in Autism have been linked to emotion dysregulation (for meta-analysis see, Van Steensel & Heeman, 2017) and the advancement of new and innovative emotion regulation technologies have resulted in great potential for use within support strategies (for reviews see: Jaliaawala, & Khan 2020; Lee et al., 2018; Boucenna et al., 2014). Real time emotion regulation technology via physiological signals has also been proposed as a feasible method of self-emotion-regulation (Williams & Gilbert, 2020). However, to our knowledge no studies have assessed views from the Autistic community regarding the benefits or challenges these devices may present in practice.

Emotion Regulation in Autism

Emotion Regulation refers to the process of effectively managing and modifying the expression or experience of emotions (Thompson, 1994). Difficulties in emotion regulation is a common issue for many Autistic people and has been found to result in increased anxiety, depression, anger and physical health outcomes (Mazefsky et al., 2014; Cai et al, 2018; Zantinge, et al., 2017; White et al., 2014). Conner et al (2020) found that emotion regulation difficulties in Autistic people significantly predicted elevated levels of anxiety and was associated with suicidal ideation. Around 50% of Autistic individuals experience higher levels of social anxiety (Benevides et al., 2020; Maddox & White 2015) and sensory overload (Rodgers & Ofield, 2018) than non-autistic people. Those with more complex needs e.g. intellectual disability, limited verbal ability and sensory overload, are particularly at risk (Samson et al., 2014). High anxiety and frustration are often evidenced by behaviours frequently termed as 'challenging behaviours' such as aggression, self-harm, harming others or running away (White et al., 2009; O'Nions et al., 2017).

Indeed, autistic people also tend to experience more social isolation and depression than non-autistic peers (Lai et al., 2017) and have reported many obstacles when trying to access support for mental health (Crane et al., 2019) which can lead to poorer quality of life (DaWalt et al., 2019). This indicates an urgent need for support strategies which not only cater to the wide variety of abilities and needs of Autistic people, but ultimately improve mental health for both individuals and their care givers (Suzuki et al., 2019; McGuire et al., 2016).

The Use of Technology to Support Emotion Regulation

Many studies have identified advantages of emotion regulation technology for Autistic people and how they can improve communication in daily life (Zhang et al., 2020). For instance, interactive

technologies can be more predictable than humans, as direct social interaction is not required and they can give feedback or consistent rewards (Rapp et al., 2018; Grynszpan et al., 2014). Jeffs et al., (2005) found that parents and children can learn from each other when engaging with and interacting using assistive technology. Common communication aids include picture communication systems via applications (apps), speech generation aids, games via mobile phones, tablets or virtual reality devices that mimic social scenarios, allowing users to 'practice' social interactions. In a systematic review, Pérez-Fuster (2017) found that handheld devices such as tablets and smartphones were the most popular technologies for enhancing daily living skills for Autistic people. Although Autistic individuals tend to use technology for entertainment more than non-autistic peers (Mazurek & Wenstrup, 2013), less is known about how Autistic people use technology for social and emotional communication and management, e.g. regulating emotion and reducing anxiety. Systematic reviews (see Benevides et al., 2020; Berggren et al., 2017) suggest that future research should aim to better understand the lived experience of technology to support socio-emotional communication in Autism.

Several studies have explored the feasibility of non-invasive wearable technologies for emotion regulation strategies via physiological signals (Puli & Kushki, 2019; Benssassi et al, 2018; Taj-Eldin et al., 2018; Koo, 2018). Results indicate that increasing awareness of emotional states via technology, may allow the individual or a caregiver to take actions that would reduce stress or frustration, ultimately having the potential to improve emotion regulation, reduce anxiety and prevent 'challenging behaviours'. However, in a survey of wearable technologies for Autism interventions, Williams & Gillbert (2020) found that 90% of identified studies viewed Autistic traits as deficits to be 'fixed' and only 10% of technologies focused on supporting sensory regulation, emotion regulation, executive function or communication. This suggests that many wearable technology studies have been based on outdated theoretical models of Autism (i.e., a disorder to be treated).

Therefore, despite showing promise (Berggren et al., 2017; Pennington 2010; Odom et al., 2015; Kintsch & DePaula, 2002), it is not surprising that the success of emotion regulation technology has been varied and usability/uptake remains poor. This may also be a result of a lack of participatory methods that consider user satisfaction and how design features can address individual needs. Fletcher-Watson et al., (2016) shed light on such inconsistencies in the reported success of technology and suggest that little work has directly connected technology design with user experience or outcomes (referred to as participatory design). Furthermore, the lack of methodologically robust evaluation methods to assess technologies may also explain the varied results; with only a minority of studies involving control groups or follow-up evaluations (Grynszpan et al., 2014; Benssassi et al., 2018). Addressing this problem places high demands on technological supports as differing levels of ability and varying rates of development must be taken into account at the design stage. Thus, a participatory exploration of views from the Autistic community regarding experiences and expectations of emotion regulation technology is essential to provide a basis for designing future ethical and inclusive technological supports.

This paper aims to:

- Provide meaningful insight into experiences and expectations of technology that aims to support emotion regulation
- Explore participant's views on the benefits and challenges of real time emotion regulation technology via physiological signals
- Provide a basis for improving individualised and interactive technology aiming to support emotion regulation for Autistic people

4.3 Method

Design

In line with the aim of understanding complex phenomena and improving quality of life (Smith, 2003), a qualitative participatory design was chosen, and 8 semi-structured focus groups were carried out. Semi-structured questions provided participants with more control over the discussions and how they voiced their experiences (Stewart & Shamdasani, 2014). These lasted around 1 hour with interviews digitally recorded for transcription, before reflexive thematic analysis was conducted on anonymized transcripts by the researcher. Most participants were not aware of questions before focus groups were carried out, however two Autistic participants requested to have some examples beforehand.

Participants

Through opportunity sampling, thirty-four participants with a wide variety of knowledge and experience of Autism were recruited. Participants included; Autistic adults, parents of Autistic children and adults, health/social care staff who support Autistic adults in a community care setting, and educational staff who support Autistic individuals at college level. The selected groups ensured multiple perspectives were obtained that reflect both the heterogeneity of Autism and technology use across a wide variety of contexts (home, education, and community care). Furthermore, health/social care staff, parents of Autistic children and educational staff had experience supporting autistic individuals across the spectrum, ranging from moderate to high IQ's, to those with highly complex needs (e.g. various levels of adaptive functioning, lower IQ, more difficulties in emotion regulation, 'challenging behaviours'). This therefore ensured insight into Autistic experiences reflecting a broad range of IQ. Ultimately, the diverse range of experiences of participants allowed insight into technology use across a wide variety of needs and abilities.

Procedure

Written and verbal consent was obtained from all participants before each focus group. Due to COVID19 two focus groups with Autistic participants were carried out online. Two participants (one who was non-speaking and another with sensory needs) chose to take part via the zoom chat box. This may have influenced amount of information provided, however online focus groups were also noted as being a preferred method by the Autistic participants' and inclusive adaptations such as this enable Autistic individuals to take part in research who otherwise may not. All participants were given contact details to review the results.

Focus Group Questions

Questions in each focus group were split into two domains: (1) any type of technology that aims to support social and emotional communication. (2) emotion regulation technology. This was to ensure participants had a chance to share more general experiences and expectations, before narrowing the discussions specifically to emotion regulation technology. Participants discussed both their own experiences and voiced opinions about emotion regulation technology for the wider Autistic community. The researcher presented some examples of how emotional regulation technology may be used in practice (e.g. real time technology that detects physiological signals and is able to prompt users to self-regulate emotions, ultimately with the potential to reduce anxiety/stress).

Table 9 below shows the Autistic group demographics and table 2 shows characteristics (gender and age range) for all participants. Table 10 below shows all participant characteristics.

Table 9: Autistic Group Participant Demographics

Participant	Age	Gender	Ethnicity	Occupation
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1	23	Female	White/Caucasian	Student
2	24	Male	White/Scottish	Student
3	42	Male	White/Scottish	Disability Campaigner
4	31	Male	White/Scottish	Disability Campaigner
5	35	Male	White/Scottish	Student
6	38	Female	White/British	
7	23	Female	White	Student
8	21	Male	White/Scottish	Student
				Student

Table 10: All Participant Characteristics (n=34)

Focus Group Sample	Total N (number of woman)	Age Range
Autistic Adults	9 (4)	21-42

Parents of Autistic Children and Adults	9 (8)	30-52
Health and Social Care Staff (supporting Autistic individuals in a community care setting)	14 (10)	25-60
Educational Inclusive Learning Staff (supporting Autistic individuals at college level)	2 (2)	25-40

Qualitative Analysis

Each focus group was facilitated by the primary researcher and was digitally recorded before being listened to and transcribed. Analysis took a data-driven approach using reflexive thematic analysis, facilitated by a systematic six phase process outlined by Braun et al., (2019). This methodology was chosen as it enables an ‘open and organic’ process rather than basing themes on theory or previous research (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Braun & Clarke, 2020). Although the analytical process was facilitated by the 6 phase process outlined below, no coding guidebook was used. Instead, themes were developed according to patterns of shared meaning. Table 11 below outlines the analytical process.

Table 11: Thematic Analysis Systematic Framework (Braun et al., 2019)

Phase	Analysis Strategy
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1	Each focus group was read several times for familiarisation and initial ideas were noted. All focus groups were transcribed.
2	Interesting features of the data were highlighted across the entire data set to produce initial codes and a table of 'key quotes' was produced for each focus group.
3	The NVivo data management program was used to input data, and a systematic process of coding the data and generating themes was undertaken. This involved categorising all focus group transcripts into "nodes" (the thematic feature in NVivo10) then organising the codes into relevant themes.
4	Themes were reviewed and refined. A thematic map of the data was produced.
5	Themes were defined before being checked by another member of the research team to confirm accuracy and consistency.
6	Final write up of the analysis and report. Data extracts were chosen to provide evidence and highlight the prevalence of each theme.

4.4 Results and Discussion

Overall, three themes were identified within the data **(1) Communication Challenges (2) Benefits/Challenges of Emotion Regulation Technology (3) ‘How’ Technology is Implemented**. The following section will discuss the shared meaning behind each theme and sub theme. In order to protect the identities of participants, pseudonyms are used throughout. Table 12 below outlines the main themes and sub-themes.

Table 12: Main Themes and Sub-themes

Theme	Sub-themes	Examples of Codes
1. Communication Challenges	Emotion Processing Challenges	Experiences of ‘challenging behaviours’, experiences of technology, experiences struggling with emotion regulation, camouflaging, socializing, positive experiences, negative experiences
	Person-centered Technologies are needed	Individualised technology, co-participation, different needs and abilities, adaptable designs
2. Benefits & Challenges of Emotion Regulation Technology	Benefits of Emotion Regulation Technology	Positive design features, positive experiences, self-emotion-regulation

	Challenges of Emotion Regulation Technology	Funding issues, usability, lack of knowledge about what technology is available, ethical issues for future developments,
3. 'How' technology is implemented	Training is needed	Experiences of lack of training, poor training, how training could be improved
	Defining individual goals and needs	Positive example of support strategies, implementation, life goals/individual needs wants/desires, promoting independence, meeting individual needs, consistent staff, co-participatory methods, focus on environment/context in implementation strategies for those with more complex needs

4.4 Theme 1: Communication Challenges

A wide range of communication difficulties typically associated with Autism and the impact on social interactions and emotional well-being was discussed extensively across all groups.

Sub-theme: **Emotion Processing Challenges**

Social and emotional challenges can vary widely for Autistic people, depending on individual ability and stage of development. Difficulties expressing and regulating emotions were discussed in detail. Parents expressed how this can impact mental health and well-being of families and carers:

“Sarah: She looks perfectly fine and she’s behaving perfectly fine..except...she’s not”

Wendy: Do you feel like you’re walking on egg shells in your own home?

Sarah: Oh Yeah..yeah, we’re at a point with Lucy where...like..she’d just come home from school n she’s contained it n then she’ll come home n she’ll just go..off her nut”

Sarah went on to explain how her daughter may seem okay outwardly, however struggles emotionally internally:

Sarah: “Now we’re at a point where..we can’t..she hides it so well, the anxiety and everything that – we haven’t got a clue! If she’s feeling a certain way or she’s at a certain point, we don’t see it. Her facial expressions, her mannerisms, everything. Sometimes the prodding can lead to a big explosion”

Sarah’s experience with her daughter is not uncommon as research has shown that an autistic person can appear outwardly calm to those around him or her, while having an unusually high resting heart rate – a common indicator of high physiological arousal (McDonnell et al., 2015;

Kaliouby et al., 2006). Sarah's experience reflects what researchers have identified as 'camouflaging', causing internal states (often in turmoil) to be masked. Several researchers have documented that camouflaging is more common in women (Lai et al., 2019; Hull et al., 2020) and that the stress of maintaining a 'public mask' can lead to more problems at home (Anderson et al., 2020). Due to emotions being hidden so well in public, emotional communication challenges may go unnoticed or without further exploration and have been linked to depression both in Autistic men and woman (Cage et al, 2018; Lai et al., 2017).

One Autistic participant shared how he currently deals with emotional challenges:

Harry: "So I'll try and shut myself away...so that when I do go into, if it's a fit of rage...I won't endanger anyone"

These experiences further stress the need for useful and effective strategies to support Autistic people in self-regulating emotions.

Educational staff shared experiences of Autistic students struggling to socialize with peers and interacting in a classroom environment. They also felt that students can be reluctant to try new technology due to lack of training or preferring to have the support of staff members.

Alice: "I would say the issues have been more about actually..em interaction with other peers in their class n things."

Jill: "A lot of the emotional support I gave last year was about social interaction"

Additionally, some Autistic participants commented on the lack of understanding from non-autistic people in social/emotional interaction:

Connor: "I was just going to say like I sometimes feel like the same kind of way, where I feel like I'm not really the one who's Autistic,, it's kind of other people and their lack of understanding".

Such challenges in social interactions between autistic students and their peers may be explained by 'The double empathy theory' proposed by Milton, (2018). This suggests that the social and emotional challenges many autistic people report (i.e. friendship and socializing) are not solely due to autistic cognition, but a breakdown in mutuality and understanding that can happen between people who communicate in different ways. Crompton et al., (2020) found that Autistic people shared information in social interaction with other Autistic people just as well as non-autistic people do with other non-autistic people, suggesting that *differences* in communication impact relationships between autistic and non-autistic people. This new approach to understanding the different communicative styles between autistic and non-autistic people is crucial for developing and designing future support strategies using technology.

Carers shared their experiences of how emotional challenges can impact behavior and how they felt technology could be integrated into support strategies to benefit people:

Ann: "he can't tell us what's going through his head..you can't tell how he's feeling. He could look really happy, but he could be ready to have a meltdown"

Jean: "Yeah one gentlemen I support is very quick. And we always know there's something causing it, but he goes from one extreme to another very quickly".

Ann: "You want to get in before the behaviour starts..before it escalates..we could go in before to offer reassurance..a distraction..or for other people its withdrawal..give them their own space"

Alison: "But then Harry's always got a trigger to make him feel these ways"

Gary: "Yup..and that might help us determine what the trigger is before.....we know there might be a pattern, but we just can't see it"

Carers discussed how technology that aims to support individuals in expressing their emotions or record patterns in the behaviours would be more beneficial than the current method of recording their emotions on paper. In line with Laurent et al., (2018), this highlights how emotion regulation technology may help parents or carers establish patterns in behaviors, key points of high anxiety and potential anxiety triggers which would be invaluable in supporting the autistic person e.g giving them space, in altering the sensory environment, or to avoid situations they may find particularly stressful.

Sub-theme: Person-centered Technologies are needed

One of the key aims of the study was to provide meaningful insight into experiences and expectations of technological supports that aim to regulate emotions. Participants across all groups expressed the need for person-centered and adaptable technology to cater to a wide variety of abilities and needs.

Autistic participants highlighted how technology is often more geared towards individuals with an intellectual disability or complex needs and rarely aimed at those with a higher IQ:

Harry: "It's as if they've put people with all Autism under the one IQ"

Harry: "All the Autism apps are geared to the one specification"

Andrew: "Yeah there was certainly an issue with products and where they were putting where it was pitched in the spectrum, if that sense?"

Alex: "You feel like you kind of walk between the two worlds almost...like you're not quite severe, so you're not at that point on the spectrum where you need a lot of support that you'd get if you were"

Kirsten: "And yeah lower support needs are often ignored (not like people with high support needs, we just kinda get left behind)"

Katie (chat box): "nice sensory technology is a big thing for me"

Indeed, IQ level will impact what technology can be used and how it is used, which further highlights the importance of adaptive designs. Participants discussed potential solutions and suggested that being able to input design preferences into technology prior to use would be useful (e.g adaptive lighting, sounds, fonts, colours on interfaces). These experiences reflect the heterogeneity of Autism and evidently, must be addressed in the design, development, and implementation of technologies.

It was also agreed across all groups that in order for technology to be successful, co-participation at every stage of the research process is vital:

Alex: "If your gonna make something for someone ask them what they want don't just spit out something and go here's what I made. And it's everywhere whether it's an app or technology or even the way events are organised or how people write up things. Like the amount of papers where people claimed to have made something for learning disabilities or you know...and it's like have you ever had it tested have you ever used it with anyone??"

Autistic participants also agreed that technological designs should promote independence, rather than try to 'mask' or 'fix' Autism.

Katie (chat box): "This can be a hard thing with technology, the more it helps and masks my autism, the less people will understand that I still struggle and the amount of difficulty I face navigating and communicating in a neurotypical world"

4.5 Theme 2: Views on Emotion Regulation Technology

Since studies assessing the feasibility of emotion regulation technology for Autistic people are increasingly showing promise, yet with varied success in practice; a key aim was to explore participant's views on this (specifically the benefits and challenges). Participants were asked about their experiences with any type of technology that has helped with regulating emotions and their views on real time emotion regulation technology based on physiological signals.

Sub-theme: Benefits of Emotion Regulation Technology

Participants considered many positive aspects of technology use:

Tom: "Even if it gets broken, there's a procedure to fix it. It doesn't wake up in a bad mood..it doesn't have a bad nights sleep....people are inconsistent (as far as you try and be consistent)".

This highlights how Autistic people enjoy and interact well with technology as it is consistent and reliable. Parents also evaluated the use of iPad and YouTube videos to regulate emotions:

Alison: "but he'll repeat the same segment, the same 30 seconds to a minute over and over again n it like ok I know what's gonna happen...he'll talk along with it. So he'll get language that way, so he uses it to help relax and calm....regulate himself ... so yeah, it's a calming, it's a comfort for him"

Here, Alison highlights how technology can be used to engage in repetitive behavior (stimming) which is often a coping mechanism, or an anxiety reduction technique instinctually employed by autistic individuals (Kapp et al., 2019). Since research on technology as a stimming aid is limited, further exploration on appropriate and effective technological supports aiming to regulate emotions and reduce anxiety is needed (Kapp et al, 2019).

Participants were asked about their views on emotion regulation technology based on physiological signals and gave examples of how such technology might be useful:

Milly: "Obviously it doesn't change anything, it doesn't fix anything, maybe if you're having a stim moment or if you're feeling anxious but I suppose it does let you know that you need to take some time out".

Norma: "I'd like something similar to what you said..emm.. something that he can self-regulate, tell people how hes feeling, something that's an app that somehow connects with a colour, so he can pick a picture that says how he's feeling, and people know without it being a big song and dance and so he's not singled out...something that connects to the phone...from the internal to the external"

David: "I don't think technology, or anything will get to the point where it will be the solution to all our problems or whatever, but I feel like you know, having the tools at my disposal and to use them however I can to make my life easier"

One participant also shared that he would use his heart rate monitor on his watch to regulate emotional well-being:

David: "It's funny you say that because I'm currently wearing my watch,,which detects my heart rate and I do periodically look at it to actually see where I am to actually try to establish whether or not I am ok"

Sub-theme: Challenges of Emotion Regulation Technology

There was consensus among participants regarding difficulties in getting access to not just emotion regulation technology but technology in general (either through lack of funding or knowledge).

Many Autistic people supported in their own homes within a community care service and who have more complex needs (e.g. non-speaking or severe learning difficulties) use technology such as door alarms, bed alarms or wall sensors. However, care staff highlighted that access to any other technology specifically focused on emotion regulation is extremely limited due to personal budgets or funding:

*Ann: "*nods* yi can try but we don't have anything"*

Jean: "We don't have anything signed off to say its accessible"

Ruth: "It's a bit of a fight to get resources"

This may explain differences across groups, e.g. why parents using technology (such as iPad, tablets, and mobiles) at home with their children expressed more positive experiences than care staff within community settings. This highlights the impact of socioeconomic factors (e.g parent education, employment status or income) when accessing technologies. The data therefore highlight the need for low cost technological supports if they are to be accessible to a wider population.

Knowledge of different types of emotion regulation technology available was also highlighted as a barrier:

Gary: "I think the barriers that tend to come up is that some of the people we support don't have access to that kind of technology and if they do it's not necessarily the people we support who use it, it's the staff members who use it on behalf of them to do certain things."

Milly (Chat box): "I don't think I'm aware of any but if I were I don't know how and when I would be able to use it"

Jean: "N its limiting the guys we support as well cause..they don't get taught a lot about different aids and adaption n how they can use some technology"

Here, it is clear that access and knowledge about emotion regulation technology can greatly impact expectations and use. Moving forward it is essential to recognize this diversity and how socioeconomic factors (such as income) can influence technology use/perceived ability to use technology, especially since Autistic people are less likely to have well-paying jobs compared to non-autistic people (Pellicano et al, 2013).

Educational staff reported experiences with students who would rather have human-human interaction for emotional support.

Alice: "I don't think it can replace human interaction"

This may also be indicative of technology that is to date implemented without being co-produced by the autism community who would be able to advise on systems that were more intuitive for autistic groups. In addition to socio-economic factors there were also concerns about media use due to the scare campaigns about the effects of screen time and lack of clear guidance on technology and media. Parents of children who already struggle with social interaction may be more anxious about their child using technology for long periods (Valkenburg & Peter 2009) since media often communicates the disadvantages of long screen time.

"Sharon: I feel like it's a need in our house as well, if they don't have restrictions, if I don't have any restrictions around using the technology, then it could become a 6 or 8 hour day on a device..."

When asked about their views on real time emotion regulation technology based on physiological signals, positive aspects were highlighted, however some participants expressed important ethical concerns which must be prioritized and addressed in order for such technology to be beneficial to Autistic people:

Emma (chat box): “Also, it freaks me out a bit that a device would be monitoring and then an intervention based on that..the ideal states seems veering into territory of a state that is optimal Vs state that is suboptimal - again, something that has been weaponised against neurodiverse people”

Emma (chat box): “I think the ethics issue is important but the only way to do that is creating with actually autistic people”

These views place emphasis on the need for emotion regulation technology that does not intend to replace Autistic traits with neurotypical ideals. Instead, focus must be placed on developing technologies that give full autonomy in order to improve emotion regulation in a way that is useful and effective based on unique abilities and needs.

A summary of differences in opinions of real time emotion regulation technology across all groups are outlined in Table 13 below:

Table 13: Differences in Views of Real Time Emotion Regulation Technology via Physiological Signals

Focus Group	Summary of Views	Evidence/Quotes
Autistic Individuals	Highlighted ethical challenges around detection of emotional state e.g consent. Some individuals might not want their internal state to be detected by others. Felt that such technology	<i>Harry: “I found that it’s geared more towards those who haven’t got a high IQ level”</i> <i>Kirsten: “I would be interested to see if it worked. I do sometimes</i>

might be more useful for individuals with more complex needs but not necessarily for those with higher IQ. Highlighted lack of focus on technological solutions for Autistic people with a higher IQ.

look for signs I'm in the 'rumble zone' for a meltdown so that I can get into a safe space (usually things are sensory but sometimes emotional dysregulation)."

Some participants said they monitor heart rate on a smart watch as a form of emotion regulation.

Conor: "okay, well emotion regulation definitely, the heart rate thing really sounds good to me, that's right up my alley, because again my biggest issue has always been, oh my gosh I'm really panicky you know but I don't realise it until I'm 30 mins in. So that does actually sound like something that would be really useful for me"

Emma (chat box): "so for me, the aspect of tracking mood has been quite useful- something that links in with my diary and also mood tracker could be good because knowing patterns for times of

		<p><i>days or things that trigger moods/meltdowns could be helpful”</i></p> <p><i>“Exactly yeah, and it kind of takes the pressure off you to identify that yourself. You know, ehm, which is one less thing to worry about. So I definitely think there would be place for it”</i></p>
Parents	<p>Generally positive about the use of technology to help their child regulate emotions. Suggested that real time technology would be useful to provide insight into physiological state in order to identify patterns in behaviour.</p>	<p><i>Sharon: “It would be really good to get patterns..for me to help learn his behaviour..yeah, that sort of thing would be helpful!...but that’s purely just in my situation”</i></p>
Support Workers	<p>Positive about the use of real time emotion regulation technology to reduce ‘challenging behaviours’. Liked idea of being able to intervene early e.g alter sensory</p>	<p><i>Gary: “So if there was something that could indicate that then we could go in really quickly with distraction or give him his space sooner..cause just now we don’t</i></p>

	<p>environment. Also placed emphasis on individuals using technology to self-regulate emotions/improve independence.</p>	<p><i>always get it right, we don't always pick the right time to intervene"</i></p>
	<p>Highlighted a potential disadvantage: although the individual or caregiver would be made aware of the internal state, they may not know the trigger and still struggle to respond appropriately, indicating that there will still be some guesswork involved in reducing anxiety/frustration.</p>	<p><i>Gary: "We've got Micheal for example, he could maybe see something and get quite distressed so that way we'd be able to pick up on patterns or triggers"</i></p>
<p>Educational Inclusive Learning Staff</p>	<p>Sceptical about real time technology replacing human emotional contact in an educational context. Felt that Autistic students prefer human-human contact due to barriers to technology use e.g lack of training/poor design features.</p>	<p><i>Ann: "How can an iPad replace me listening to someone everyday"</i></p>

4.6 Theme 3: 'How' Technology is Implemented

Participants agreed that placing more of a focus on *how* technology is implemented in the home, care settings or in education may be key in developing technological supports that are more in line with individual needs and ultimately more useful. The steps taken (e.g. training, follow-up evaluation meetings, consistency within staff teams) to ensure technology is implemented appropriately and effectively according to individual needs/life goals is often overlooked both within academic research and practice. Participants discussed ways in which they felt the overall success of technology in supporting emotion regulation could be improved:

Sub-theme: Training is Needed

Participants across all groups expressed how there is little or no training on how to use technology in general:

John: "They can't just really give you a device n say right here you go crack on now...it's down to money and making the product and its down to education and training everybody to use it then the research behind using the product aswell"

Katie (chat box): "The training was always hard because it is with a new person you do not know with a new thing and I just struggle to process a lot of it, so I feel a lot of it is about learning on your own"

Jill: "students need to be given official training....the training that we receive..I don't think is official enough, either"

*Alice: "I have to admit, my experience would be, most of the students that I work with..if you try n
introduce assistive technology they're not..their quite reluctant."*

Alice went on to explain how staff are only given 'a shot' at using technology if they have a question and only in their 'down time'. Lack of training for both staff and students may explain why students are 'quite reluctant' to use it. Thus, formal training may increase confidence in the ability to use technology and consequently improve overall success.

Care staff shared the same experiences when it came to supporting an individual with Autism to use technology:

Gary: "I think the problem that we seem to have is that putting a piece of technology in can be very complicated...if I go back to Harry – that's certainly what he felt with his equipment. Staff found it really hard because it was all set up, it was all ready to go, staff didn't know how to use it and he was getting frustrated with it"

*Gary: Very little training...when it was speaking it wasn't very loud and he had this frustration. Obviously there are other things out there that we'd be able to use it for, but I think there's a lack of knowledge, that, I'm sure there's hundreds of stuff out there that we'd be able to use but without the knowledge of what's out there we're very much restricted, like if someone says have you tried that?
No we haven't!"*

“You’re in a position where if anything goes wrong you go round in a big huge circle to get someone out to help you & actually there’s no, yeah there’s no training, there’s no quick guide on how to fix anything”

Care staff went on to discuss how funding issues create an additional barrier to training:

Jean: “that’s what we hit all the time in social care..it’s about funding everything.”

Gary: “The same as every other organisation at this moment in time, the local authority are looking at the cheapest way possible of providing that support..so what you might find or what we’ve experienced in the past is that we get something...that’s a kind of step in the right direction but they don’t go the full way because they don’t want to spend the money they just need to go through the process of trying things before they put in the technology to make it work”

These concerns regarding lack of funding reflect the current economic climate as there are increasing financial strains both on the National Health Service (NHS) and third sector organisations who provide care for Autistic individuals (Pellicano et al., 2014). Despite support staff wanting to support individuals to use technology they are limited by a lack of funding and training. So although public money is spent on the development of technology there is limited funds on the support, training and implementation methods that should coincide this advancement (Ravet, 2015).

Sub-theme: Defining Individual Goals and Needs

'How' technology is implemented can often determine whether or not it is successful and may be key in overcoming some of the barriers discussed above. Consistency in how staff implement technologies within an individual's life was highlighted as a key contributing factor to successful technology use. There was consensus that a person centered approach to implementing technological solutions and more robust strategies to 'get staff teams on board' would improve overall success (e.g. bespoke training, regular team meetings that include the person being supported, and standardized follow-up evaluations).

Ann: "N they're there 24 hours if your gonna make something work you've got to involve the team"

Paula: "There's no budgets anymore for the people we support n they are looking at the different options of technology...reducing hours n stuff n we need support staff to come on board with it to give them more positives out it"

Ann: "aye..so its staff getting on board with it I think..can be a hurdle sometimes aswell"

Participants also shared experiences of supporting Autistic individuals, who would normally receive 24hr care, however, have had their support hours cut due to a lack of funding and are therefore on their own during the night or for a period of the day. Discussions evolved to consider how technological solutions may aid safety and well-being in these circumstances if they are implemented in the correct ways.

Participants discussed how many third sector care organisations are turning to technological solutions as a means of 'cutting costs' and that in order for them to be successful, staff teams need to be on board and consistent in the delivery of such technology. This means implementing

technology in a person centered way, for example someone who isn't keen on change or trying new things should have technological interventions implemented slowly and over a period of time, allowing for formal training for both the Autistic person, families and staff to be put in place.

One Autistic participant further stressed the need for individualized support strategies:

Alex: "So often it's a case of, you know, you get given a lot of help which makes you feel babied or incompetent or you get the, just suck it up and get on with it".

These experiences emphasize the importance of defining individual goals, needs and preferences as part of the implementation process, highlighting the importance of co-production methods.

Reflexive Statement

The following section will outline a reflexive statement, providing an overview of how the research process within the focus group study may have been impacted by my own life experiences.

My previous experiences supporting Autistic people (both in healthcare and educational contexts) provided me with the skills required to carry out the focus groups. I have 6 years of experience as a support worker and staff trainer within the third sector. My experiences here meant that I was able to relate to and build good rapport with participants. For instance, I found I could relate to many of the experiences the healthcare workers faced and could empathise with the challenges as I had worked in community healthcare settings myself. I found that participants responded well to this and appreciated this. Although this was advantageous in terms of building rapport and validating participant responses, I was also conscious not to influence participants and made a conscious effort not to influence them with any of my own opinions.

Furthermore, some of my close family members and friends either have a diagnoses of or self-identify as being Autistic. This has given me in depth insight into how Autistic people experience the world and the opportunities/challenges they experience e.g. emotion regulation differences, sensory sensitivity, social exclusion and the implications of these in daily life. This meant I was also aware of how vastly different experiences of Autism can be and how support strategies must be person-centered to reflect different needs and preferences. Having Autistic people within my close family has been a huge motivating factor in carrying out Autism research focused on improving technological supports and meant that implementing inclusive adaptations within the research design was a top priority for me.

When carrying out the focus groups, I found it interesting that participants brought up topics and issues I had not considered before and that the same or similar ideas were discussed across different focus groups. Throughout the focus groups I was keen to know what participants thought about the quantitative phase of the PhD and whether or not they thought there was a need/rationale for affect detection technology based on physiological signals. The responses related to this subsequently provided a basis and rationale for exploring the accuracy of EEG-based affect detection.

4.5 Limitations

A limitation of the current study was that participants knowledge of existing technologies was not measured. Participants with more or less knowledge than, may have different experiences or expectations of emotion regulation technology. Also, the focus groups were carried out across different contexts i.e. home, community care and education. This may have caused differences in the amount of information (especially critical) that was provided to the researcher. In addition, to achieve a multi-disciplinary perspective, smaller groups of each discipline were recruited, therefore results may not extend to a wider population. Although the study did not recruit a large sample,

fewer participants resulted a more in depth analysis. Future research may wish to examine one group only to avoid too many variations of opinion and perspective. Despite these limitations however, the current study shows that there is much consensus between the groups on the benefits and issues surrounding technological supports aiming to regulate emotions for autistic people.

4.6 Conclusion and Implications

First, this study aimed to provide meaningful insight into experiences and expectations of technology that aimed to regulate emotions for Autistic people. Results show that the success of technology in helping to support emotion regulation is impacted by how adaptable, affordable, and easy to use it is. For example, participants felt that most technology is not 'easy to use'. Care and educational staff discussed how individuals are 'often reluctant to use technology' due to a lack of formal training. Parents of children with Autism expressed how they would only try new technology to support emotion regulation if it wasn't too complicated, low-cost, and specific to their child's needs. This is further confounded by socio-economic factors, resulting in limited access to technology or knowledge about availability. Moving forward, the implementation of technology could be improved so that end users have confidence in their ability to utilize the technology and feel that it is suited to their ability/development: this was highlighted extensively across all focus groups, and across the variety of contexts (i.e. home, schools, and care settings).

The second aim was to explore participant's views on the advantages and disadvantages of real time emotion regulation technology based on physiological signals. Differences in opinions between participant groups were highlighted. For example, some Autistic participants felt there is a lack of technology aimed towards Autistic individuals with higher IQ, however, did suggest that real time emotion regulation technology may be more beneficial for Autistic individuals with more complex needs e.g additional learning needs or those at increased vulnerability (i.e. self-harm, aggressive outbursts etc.). This emphasizes the importance of personalized technological support that is flexible

and can adapt to the varying abilities and needs of Autistic individuals. Data also emphasized the need for emotion regulation technology that does not attempt to overwrite Autistic traits with neurotypical ideals. Future research in this area must place Autistic people at the heart of technology development if it is to be successful.

Thirdly, the paper aimed to provide a basis for improving individualised and interactive emotion regulation technology for Autistic people. Based on the findings, a number of recommendations are proposed: (1) With regards to technology design, usability is likely to increase through participatory methods/by adopting co-design approach at every stage of both the research process and technology development. There was consensus expressed to provide simple, easy to use and adaptive technology to meet individual needs. (2) Implementation strategies that take the individuals' life goals into consideration in a more holistic and person centered way is needed, this would include bespoke training procedures for guidance for families, staff, and individuals. (3) An important and innovative direction for future research in this area would be to investigate the use of physiological signals for the development of interactive sensor technology able to support emotion regulation strategies. Whilst this area of research has many positive implications, ethical challenges must be addressed and an emphasis must be placed on co-participatory methods to develop technological supports that can adapt to a wide variety of abilities, promote independence, empower, and improve socio-emotional well-being for Autistic people.

5 “If it is to make our brains reach a normal state or an optimal state, that is a red flag”: Considering The Ethics of Wearable Technologies based on Physiological Signals

5.1 Chapter Introduction

In the previous chapter, ethical concerns were highlighted as one of the key challenges of real-time technology based on physiological signals. Autistic participants raised important ethical issues and it was concluded that these must be prioritized and addressed in order for such technology to be both accepted by and beneficial to Autistic people. Since the current thesis is co-participatory these ethical concerns voiced by the autism community should be given it's own spotlight and focus. Therefore we aim to deeper explore the ethical considerations of wearable technologies within this chapter. Additionally, since user acceptance of technology is the main deterrent of actual usage (Yi et al, 2006), this chapter explores the questions that arose from the focus groups. Results from Theme 2 (challenges of emotion regulation technology; specifically relating to ethical considerations) are discussed in depth and a thematic map outlining the main themes and subsequent ethical questions is presented. Perspectives of Autistic participants will be synthesised with literature on the ethics of real-time technology. This chapter contributes not only to a much wider debate within the literature regarding ethical considerations for wearable technologies and emotional artificial intelligence, but also provides a basis for how such challenges might be overcome.

The increase in the prevalence of Autism globally has been well documented (Zeidan et al, 2022). This places demand on improved healthcare provision, particularly in the areas of Autistic mental health and emotional well-being (Maenner et al, 2020). Recent studies assessing the impact of poor access to healthcare found increased rates of suicidality (Cassidy et al, 2018), depression and anxiety among Autistic participants (Crane et al., 2019). Joshi et al (2013) suggests that mental health provision is currently not meeting Autistic needs. Wearable monitoring technologies offer innovative solutions to improve both physical and mental well-being (Sheikh et al, 2021; Hickey et al, 2022).

Since the abilities, needs and preferences of Autistic people vary widely due to heterogeneity, wearable technologies based on physiological signals may provide new opportunities to cater to such diverse needs and abilities, as they are acquire specific data from each individual user (Williams & Gilbert, 2020).

The development of wearable technologies for emotion regulation based on physiological signals (also, referred to as emotional artificial intelligence) is a new and emerging research area, with increasing potential for successful applications in the medical field, health and social care as well as at home monitoring. As the advances in technology development continue at speed, the world is moving into a time where it is embedded within our everyday lives. It is now the norm for individuals to use tablets and smartphones/smartwatches incessantly, with many feeling dependant on them for daily living tasks such as exercise, organisation/schedules, social media. In the past decade, there has been a growing body of research aimed at revolutionising healthcare; creating real-time devices to support health and well-being, socialisation and self-tracking. Across the world, many governments are beginning to invest in wearable technologies for home monitoring solutions to tackle the rising costs of healthcare. Global healthcare systems have recently experienced mass disruption due to the COVID-19 pandemic, resulting in the rapid increase of technologies such as telehealth and at home monitoring systems (Wong et al, 2021; Li et al, 2021). However, despite showing clear potential, there remains a gap in the understanding of ethics around such wearable technologies based on physiological signals and there is a scarcity of literature focused on the ethical dilemmas they present.

5.2 Aims

This chapter aims to further our knowledge of the expectations of technology to support Autistic emotion regulation by considering three ethical considerations that arose from the autistic focus groups:

- (1) Are real-time technology based on physiological signals accurate?
- (2) What are the ethical concerns around data privacy?
- (3) What are the challenges around informed consent?

Figure 5: Thematic Map of The Focus Group Themes & Subsequent Ethical Considerations of Real-Time Wearable Technologies

Figure 5 outlines each of the themes derived from the focus groups (Chapter 3) and the subsequent questions around ethics that arose from them. The reason for outlining these considerations within a separate chapter is that Chapter 3 did not aim to explore the ethical considerations of wearable emotion regulation technology and therefore this was not discussed extensively or in great depth across all Focus groups. However, ethical considerations were discussed mainly within one of the Autistic participant groups and due to the pertinency and importance of this topic, the consideration of these issues, questions and challenges is of great value to this thesis.

The structure of this chapter will be presented according to the three questions that arose from the focus groups.

5.3 Are Real Time Technology Based on Physiological Signals Accurate?

One of the main ethical concerns highlighted within the Autistic focus groups was the accuracy of devices based on physiological signals are. Participants were unsure whether or not such devices would be accurate and raised concerns regarding false positives e.g misinterpreting exercise as a negative stress response.

“Surely those are inaccurate? like physiological signs during stress or exercise are similar? or anxiety and excitement? even if internally it is hard to identify the emotion

“I think this is good until you account for lots of comorbidities with autism too, like there are a lot of other things which could be raising heart rate too, so i think it is quite individual. also, heart rate and eeg don't discriminate between positive or negative emotion...but then again you can still get overwhelmed by positive emotions”

Since this emerging branch of artificial intelligence is in its infancy, this is a pertinent issue within recent literature (Ho et al, 2022) and many researchers are currently working to overcome this challenge. Advances in machine learning have offered various approaches that aim to make sense of large data sets derived from wearable technologies, however the majority of these studies have been focused on non-Autistic populations. For instance, Turner et al (2017) investigated the use of a smartwatch to predict aggressive behaviours via machine learning techniques within an inpatient environment. Results showed that both individual and combined prediction models were possible, however there were a large number of false alarms meaning they lacked clinical application. This may have been due to inconsistencies between physiological arousal levels and behaviour noted by staff. However false positives may cause increased anxiety for individuals and therefore result in the opposite effect. Some other challenges that arose were practicalities such as participants finding it difficult to both carry a phone around, wearing a smartwatch for long periods and inconsistent WIFI connections.

Participants also shared that not only would they want to ensure the devices would work, but they'd want to know how useful it would be prior to implementing it into routines. Implementing

technologies without prior rigorous evaluation methods to determine success may cause distress for some individuals if it turns out to be ineffective.

“Yeahh..you’d want to know it works, its one of the things with autism..as soon as you get routine you don’t want to put something in place that’s not gonna work cause you don’t wanna touch that routine unless its gonna be beneficial...although I don’t know how you’d test it otherwise”

“I would be interested to see if it worked...I do sometimes look for signs that I’m in the rumble zone for a meltdown so I can get into a safe space – usually things are sensory but also emotional dysregulation..there are behavioural signs that you can get used to recognising, I have alexythimia too and my cat helps me identify that I’m not ok. And then it’s about reflecting like everyones saying”

This highlights the need for more knowledge and information around what technologies are available. One participant also noted that they currently look for signs prior to being in the ‘rumble zone’ or having a ‘meltdown’. Emotion regulation technology based on physiological signals may provide a unique way of digitalising this process. Based on this data, it would be beneficial for future work to consider how monitoring devices may also include opportunities for reflection.

Despite current concerns around the accuracy of wearable technologies for emotion regulation, several studies have produced promising accuracy rates. For instance, Ahn et al (2019) proposed a novel wearable device aimed at monitoring daily distress, via EEG and ECG signals (see figure 6 below). These physiological signals were recorded while participants took part in two stress inducing tests (The stroop colour word test & a mental arithmetic test).

Figure 6. Electrode placements and inputs on the recording device

Results showed that combining EEG and ECG features showed an accuracy of 87% for stress prediction, suggesting that simultaneous measurement may improve performance. However, the authors did note that the monitoring of individuals who experience chronic stress may require a different classification algorithm. This suggests that high accuracy rates may be feasible, however baseline measures need to be considered in order to avoid false positives.

Furthermore, a recent review by Elgendi & Menon (2019), explored the validity of using ECG signals for anxiety detection within wearable technologies and concluded that experimental papers produced varied and conflicting results. Likewise, a systematic review carried out by Hicky et al, (2021) investigated smart devices and wearable technologies aimed at detecting and monitoring mental health conditions and stress. They concluded that anxiety and stress was better detected by heart rate variability (HRV) and electroencephalogram (EEG), whereas depression was found to be mostly detected using EEG signals (despite not currently accessible on the market). Importantly, they concluded that heart rate detection by many 'on the market' products is not an accurate measure of stress and anxiety compared with devices that are able to detect heart rate variability & electrodermal activity. Future work must seek to differentiate between more generic heart rate monitoring devices e.g smart watches and devices that are specifically aimed at emotion regulation or stress reduction.

Mantello et al (2022) explored the acceptance of emotion detection devices among 'Gen-z' students. Results showed that ethical design and effective governance of emotional artificial intelligence requires a more in depth understanding of the potential risks. They argue that research should pursue greater scientific accuracy and account for cultural differences in technology development if public trust is to be gained.

It is not surprising that participants raised this important issue within the focus groups since much of the literature has been varied and devices aren't yet easily available on the market. However, it is important to consider that as technology advances, recent research has shown more promising results that may be able to mitigate any discrepancy between signals related to stress/frustration and physical activity. Although concerns were raised, Autistic participants were also intrigued about how (if accurate) it could be useful:

"I also am really bad at knowing what is going on in my body though due to deficits in interoception though so it might actually be really useful"

“I used to have a cheap smart watch that kind of, was keeping you know track of your heart rate, but it would only ever like do it if you actively went on to look at it, you know it wouldn’t alert you if it was above or below a certain range. You know as you can imagine it was exercise based”

One study that aimed to mitigate the effects of physical activity was carried out by Puli & Kushki (2020). They investigated the feasibility of anxiety detection in Autistic children using physiological signals (heart rate and accelerometry signals) and results showed a 93% accuracy for overall arousal. The proposed method, using a Kalman-like filter was also able to significantly reduce false positives in comparison with state-of-the-art. An advantage of Kalman filtering is that baseline physiological states are continuously monitored and updated therefore using little training data (Kushki et al, 2015).

Taken together, it is important to note that although many studies may produce weak accuracy results or insignificant correlations, these studies are still relevant and important for the wider research community to explore a new topic and evaluate both the feasibility and usefulness of machine learning techniques and devices able to recognise emotional states. As Tu & Gao (2021) suggest, “ The appropriate and responsible validation of data, as well as disclosure of uncertainty, is not only essential to ensure that results from human research are of scientific and of societal significance but also the safety of participants.” It is clear that future research should focus on assessing the feasibility of arousal detection systems. Specifically, it is vital to assess whether or not such devices are accurate within natural environments and to consider several other factors which may impact arousal detection such as other cognitive, affective and mental processes (Puli & Kushki, 2020). Further work in this area is essential to understand and mitigate these processes.

5.4 Data Privacy

Technology based on real-time physiological signals involves continuous monitoring and transmission of personal data to second devices or data storage systems. This is normally achieved through wireless communication technology such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, Near-Field communication or Zigbee. Not only do such devices capture physiological signals/internal states, but many also track location and medical conditions. Whilst these wearable technologies offer promising outcomes, there remains concern around the privacy and confidentiality of the users when such large amounts

of personal and potentially identifiable data is being transmitted. One of the challenges here is that AI often produces more accurate results with more data. Furthermore, there can be discrepancy in the perspectives of the definition of 'personal data'; what the technology developer may assume as appropriate information to collect may not be the same as the end users definition (Segura et al, 2018).

Furthermore, a survey on digital consumer health showed that wearable device usage decreased from 33% in 2018 to 18% in 2019 (Tu & Gao, 2021). An explanation for this may be that data privacy and confidentiality is remains a concern. Ali & O'Brien (2022) carried out interviews with Autistic people and family members to explore telehealth experiences during the COVID-19 pandemic. Results showed that Autistic participants highlighted privacy, data protection and online security concerns e.g sharing personal or sensitive data with others. They propose that one way of overcoming these challenges would be ensuring clarity for both individuals and services around how data is stored and what the limitations may be. Results from the current study were in line with this:

"I mean I'd also love an app that would let me read other people's emotions...but the privacy implications of that? And the complications of that are huge – umm I mean I have an issue with potentially being captured on peoples photos in public, you don't know what they are going to do with them and what they're going to do with that"

"I suppose some people might not want to be read that way"

"Also, it freaks me out a bit that a device would be monitoring and then an intervention based on that - because what would the intervention be? Historically this has gone horribly wrong! [new message] like the idea of ideal states seems veering into territory of a state that is optimal V state that is suboptimal - again, something that has been weaponised against neurodiverse people"

Various approaches have been considered by wearable technology researchers as to how such privacy challenges may be overcome. One proposal is the incorporation of a 'virtual voluntary regulation wall' which enables users to 'opt out' of any information tracking using privacy settings (Kapadia et al, 2007). Alternatively, suggestions have been made to restrict the ability for such applications to be made and to implement a rigorous system of approval for any new devices. This

may limit any privacy risks as all devices would be regulated. Kirkham & Greenhalgh (2015) suggest that a balance must be made between the privacy rights of users and the opportunity to meet the needs of people with disabilities to access wider society. They argue that the only resolution to this dilemma might only be developed by adhering to current legal processes and facilitating public understanding and debate. Indeed, from the focus group data collected in the current study, results suggest that these challenges may be overcome by adopting a participatory approach and having Autistic people at the centre of these discussions.

“I think the ethics issue is important but the only way to do that is creating with actually autistic people”

“i think i would only like this if it is done with autistic people involved in actually making it”

Similarly, Kirkham et al (2022) also highlight the importance of public acceptability regarding personal and sensitive data sharing. The authors explored the factors impacting the likelihood of individuals sharing mental health data in a sample of people with and without mental illness. Results showed that satisfaction with health services was associated with more willingness to share personal sensitive data. Furthermore, people with mental illness were more likely to want to share personal data despite the sensitivity. This suggests that including the public in conversations and research around data sharing must be prioritised.

Future work must develop a ‘best practice’ framework alongside Autistic people that specifically considers the complexities in data privacy, provides guidance on balancing legal rights with user needs and ultimately seeks to ensure the safety of all individuals. Research to produce personalised devices that are able to preserve privacy is ongoing and there are imminent challenges that should be addressed to integrate such technologies within daily living.

5.4 Informed Consent and Ensuring The Purpose is Clear

Obtaining informed consent from wearable technology users is often underestimated within the literature. This is particularly important for people with disabilities and those who may have complex

needs and/or limited capacity. Segura et al, (2018) found that end users of wearable technologies considered informed consent to be particularly important when data sharing with third parties.

Autistic participants within the focus groups highlighted the importance of ensuring that individuals are aware of the purpose of technology.

"I think that is why the purpose of technology has to be really clear - and if it is to make our brains reach a "normal" state or an "optimal" state, that is a red flag

Since such technology is not yet widely used in practice, it is understandable that end users note this as potentially problematic. Participants across all groups agreed that technology should not try to 'fix' people. Rather, participants felt strongly about technology being used to promote independence which is an important distinction. This has previously been referred to as 'providing a scaffolding effect' within the literature. These results are also in line with Zheng et al, (2022) who investigated the use of assistive technology to provide support for older Autistic adults and found that participants preferred technology that was able to provide a scaffolding effect rather than to teach a new skill.

Some individuals with intellectual disabilities (which represents a subsection of the autism community) may not fully understand the consequences of identifiable information leakage. However, it is worth noting that it is possible that wearable technology may actually enhance the informed consent process. Kreitmair et al (2017) suggest that wearable technologies could provide new opportunities to gain more robust informed consent for people with disabilities or learning needs. The use of plain text for participants to read about what a device would entail could be improved by including various media options to present information (videos, images, interactive components, quizzes, games). The ability to provide consent in non-traditional ways may be a solution for people who otherwise would not be able to fully understand what their involvement means. Kreitmair et al (2017) argue that although ethical challenges such as consent and data protection are vital, technology itself may be employed to address these issues, leading to more meaningful consent and empowered engagement.

A related topic that arose from the focus group discussions was whether or not emotion regulation technology (based on physiological signals) should be specifically aimed at Autistic people. Some participants felt that devices marketed as being 'for Autistic people' only would make them more

reluctant to use it. Parents of Autistic children also agreed that devices that are more discreet would be more beneficial.

“Yeah, I think I would be more likely to use it if it wasn’t like, even if it wasn’t like for autistic people you know if instead it was like eh for people who need to calm-, or struggle to kind of calm down, even though it’s basically the same thing you know what I mean overall, having that label even though I am diagnosed makes me not want to use it so much, I don’t know why”.

“Something that doesn’t say look at me I’m having an episode...I’m different”

“You don’t want to rely on technology”

“Yeahh. I think it would be useful...the thing is it can’t be replacement for learning to cope and learning to actually progress....you don’t want people to have a crutch where they rely on an app...so that it picks up on stuff. It should help them pick up on things, but part of the journey should be, you know, you learn to have coping strategies, you learn that you don’t like spaces. You can’t just have an app that does it all for you”

These discussions suggest that technology should not be tailored toward or made ‘for’ Autistic people specifically. This goes against what has historically been perceived by developers and may provide some explanation as to why many technologies have poor uptake. An alternative approach would be to develop universal designs based on the premise that they are accessible, usable and convenient for all. Milton et al, (2016) discuss universal design as a framework for educational practice, outlining principles which promote inclusivity for all. A universal/needs based design within technology development contexts would not only provide new opportunities to reach wider populations, but it would cultivate a higher sense of inclusion, rather than ‘othering’ people. Similarly, Zheng et al, (2022) also found that participants preferred technology that wasn’t specifically designed for people with additional needs. Although this preference is important to highlight, this may also could be due to lack of general awareness or poor access to technologies due to cost (which was noted within focus group results in the previous chapter). A universal design approach for technology development is also in line with the social model of disability that places focus on adapting the environment to meet needs, rather than placing fault on the individual. Ferenc et al, (2022) investigated how attitudes towards Autism impacted Autistic well-being and found that adopting a neurodiversity attitude resulted in higher self-esteem and may prevent the negative impact of self-definition on psychological distress. Therefore neurodiversity affirming technology

should be prioritised. This would entail creating technology that notes individual differences and uses this to inform or drive environmental adaptations, highlighting that it is the environment that needs to change instead of the autistic person.

Reflexive Statement

Reflexivity within qualitative research places huge value on researcher subjectivity, highlighting the importance of 'interpreting and creating', as opposed to viewing it as a limitation or as less rigorous (Braun and Clarke, 2019). The following section will outline a reflexive statement, providing an overview of how the research process may have been impacted by my own life experiences.

Prior to starting the PhD, I had worked within health and social care for several years as both a support worker and staff trainer. Here, I supported people with a wide variety of disabilities (including Autism) and mental health issues. I was involved in providing bespoke training for staff teams on the verbal de-escalation of behaviours of concern e.g. self harm and aggression. One of my motivations for pursuing research in this area was that I'd seen the challenges many Autistic people experience in their daily lives and I felt passionate about bridging the gap between the ongoing struggles faced in practice and the research being carried out within universities. More specifically, I was intrigued by the potential of technologies claiming that they may be able to reduce anxiety/frustration and which could ultimately improve health and well-being outcomes.

My position as a support worker and staff trainer equipped me with the necessary experience required for developing research questions based within a health and social care context. My experiences supporting people with various disabilities and mental health struggles meant that I was particularly keen to involve participants who are known to be underrepresented within research studies e.g. those who are non-speaking or have other complex needs. My role as a support worker also meant that I had first hand knowledge and experience of how both how many Autistic individuals and staff manage anxiety/frustration and current support strategies commonly used within practice. I therefore also understood the challenges that can be faced when implementing

technological interventions and the importance of person centered support strategies. I was really interested in how such interventions might be improved, how design features could be made more inclusive and how they might be co-produced.

I didn't initially set out to explore the ethical implications of technology based on physiological signals, however as I progressed through the PhD, the results from the focus groups highlighted crucial ethical considerations voiced by Autistic people. I then realised that this was a vital area to further explore if these devices were to see any meaningful success within practice. My background in health and social care meant that I knew how important it would be to ensure that the voices of Autistic people were at the forefront of my work, and indeed, any research around ethical considerations for wearable technologies.

5.5 Conclusion

In conclusion, active engagement and discussion of ethical concerns for wearable technologies based on physiological signals for affective state detection is fundamental if the area is to progress. In order to increase the clinical relevance and broader public acceptance of such devices, the research community must prioritise ethical considerations through honest communication with end users. Ethical acceptance of wearable technologies are an integral part of sensor implementation and findings from the current study contribute not only to our understanding of these issues, but also provide insight into how the barriers might be overcome.

The recent paradigm shift that calls for the incorporation of the neurodiversity movement within wearable technology design emphasises the importance of engaging end users in both the design and production phases. This approach attempts to lessen the discrepancy between design/function and user needs/preferences to create devices that are more likely to be useful. As Moon et al (2019) suggest, policy makers aiming to increase equitable and sustainable healthcare provision and technology developers looking to attract a wider population, would benefit from co-creation approaches.

5.6 Chapter Summary

The purpose of this chapter was to build on the findings from Chapter 3 by providing more clarity around some of the ethical questions that arose within the focus groups. In presenting some of the results from Theme 2 (challenges of emotion regulation technology) in further depth and synthesising the data with relevant literature, this chapter (1) considers perspectives of Autistic participants around the accuracy, privacy and purpose of wearable technologies and how their views relate to previous literature (2) provides suggestions to researchers/policy developers as to how some of these ethical challenges may be overcome (3) provides a conceptual basis for future work on ethical considerations of real time emotion regulation wearable technologies.

6. DETECTING AFFECTIVE STATES VIA PHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNALS IN AUTISTIC AND NON-AUTISTIC ADULTS

6.1 Chapter Introduction

This chapter outlines the quantitative phase of the PhD project and is underpinned by findings from the focus groups. Results from the focus groups provide a strong rationale for investigating the use of physiological signals for the development of interactive sensor technology able to support emotion regulation strategies. In the current study, Machine learning methods are used to provide insight into both the neurophysiological basis underlying emotion processing and the feasibility of EEG techniques for the detection of affective states, ultimately providing a basis for automatic emotion regulation in therapeutic support strategies.

It is important to note that such technological supports should not aim to replace Autistic traits/behaviours with neurotypical ideals. Instead, results from the focus groups (outlined in chapter 4) suggest that a change in direction for wearable technology researchers is vital (since many previous studies have based technology development on outdated theories (e.g the medical model of Autism). Therefore, application of technology using the proposed classification model outlined in this chapter, should be guided by recent advances within neurodiversity research. Furthermore, we emphasise that such technologies must ensure that end users have full control and autonomy over their emotion regulation. The focus groups (outlined in chapter 4) highlight that this can only be achieved if technologies are co-produced (i.e designed, developed, evaluated and implemented alongside the Autistic community).

Research Questions and Aims

This chapter aims to further our understanding of how physiological signals (EEG signals) may be employed to identify affective states in Autistic and non-Autistic samples. Specifically, the study aimed to assess the feasibility and obtain an indication of accuracy using a classification model for EEG-based affect detection in Autistic and non-Autistic adults. Both Autistic and non-Autistic participants were recruited in order to assess differences in the feasibility of classification models between groups. Physiological responses to four emotional states (high arousal/positive valence, low arousal/positive valence, high arousal/negative valence, and low arousal/negative valence) in Autistic and non-Autistic adults were investigated. Three key research questions included:

- (1) Can physiological signals (EEG signals) be used to detect affective states in Autistic and Non-Autistic adults?
- (2) Are there differences in physiological responses to emotional stimuli in Autistic people compared to non-Autistic people?
 - What is the association between self-report and expected ratings of the emotional stimuli?
 - Is higher emotional intelligence correlated with self-report and expected ratings of the emotional stimuli?
- (3) How can insight into the feasibility of physiological signals to detect affective states in Autistic and non-Autistic people be useful for the development/co-participatory design of autonomous emotion regulation technology?

6.2 Background Literature and Rationale

It is well known that EEG signals have been linked to human emotions. However, developing effective and robust algorithms able to recognise human affect is one of the key challenges in emotion recognition research and may have great implications for technological interventions aiming to support Autistic emotion regulation. Although such technology has shown promise e.g advances in machine learning algorithms and real time wearable technologies, this potential has yet to be translated to practice and studies assessing this approach (particularly those in line with the neurodiversity paradigm) are scarce. The promise of such innovative systems is evidenced by an increasing amount of publications in this emerging field, yet there is no defined universal standards outlining the most reliable method to detect and classify emotions (Torres et al, 2020). This may be due to the challenge of physiological signals being impacted by factors such as cognition, time of day, variation in response to emotion elicitation (Rahman & Sarkar, 2021). To that end, we explored automatic physiologically based classification along dimensions of arousal and valence in autistic adults and non-autistic adults. EEG signals were recorded as participants viewed images to elicit emotions. Responses to four emotional states (high arousal/positive valence, low arousal/positive valence, high arousal/negative valence, and low arousal/negative valence) were captured.

Early research in this area has shown how physiological signals have the ability to provide readings of our emotional states and can use these signals as markers of stress or anxiety (Khullar & Gaurang Tiwari, 2021). Williams & Gilbert (2020) carried out a survey of wearable technologies aiming to improve Autism interventions and found that 90% of selected studies were based on an outdated models of Autism (a medical issue to be fixed) rather than viewing Autism as a different way of viewing and experiencing the world. This may explain why there has been varied successful outcomes in practice. Nevertheless, the authors concluded that wearable technologies based on physiological signals may be uniquely suited to supporting Autistic emotion regulation, communication and executive function in a meaningful, autonomous and empowering way. These

results are in line with the focus groups (outlined in chapter 4) and provide a strong rationale for developing technologies in line with more up to date and innovative theoretical advances i.e the neurodiversity paradigm. Thus, it is essential that any implications derived from the results from the current study be interpreted in combination with our qualitative participatory work.

Williams & Gilbert (2020) also found that despite emotion regulation, communication differences, sensori-motor differences and executive function playing a critical part in Autistic well-being only a handful of papers aimed to support Autistic people in these domains. The authors emphasise the need for more research focused in these areas, if technology is to be meaningful and personally relevant to Autistic people.

Another key issue with current real time emotion regulation research, and which was highlighted in the focus groups (outlined in chapter 4) is accuracy rates for detecting affective states. Although research in this area is generally in its infancy, several previous studies have successfully provided high accuracy rates of affective state detection based on physiological signals. For example, Domínguez-Jiménez et al (2020) proposed a model for the recognition of three emotions: amusement, sadness and neutral from two biosignals (heart-rate and galvanic skin response). In order to achieve this, signals were analysed in both frequency and time domains to obtain features. Results showed that the system was able to detect the three emotions with an accuracy of up to 100% when evaluated on the test data set. Despite the confirmation that it is possible to detect affective states with high accuracy, much work in this area is needed to develop high accuracy rates for a wider selection of emotions and to identify more robust stimuli with higher ecological validity that pertains to variations in cognition and culture (Domínguez-Jiménez et al, 2020). Likewise, Saganowski et al (2020) carried out a systematic literature review exploring the detection of emotions from wireless wearable technologies and found that most studies assessing wearable technologies have low ecological validity; only four of twenty seven studies were able to identify

emotions in real life conditions. In summary, such systems can be achievable, but further investigation is required to overcome the machine learning challenges and improve implementation.

Khullar et al (2021) proposed a non-invasive real-time deep learning system based on physiological signals that aimed to detect and prevent 'meltdowns/tantrums'. The premise was that such wearable devices may be able to observe changes in physiological signals in order to predict anxiety levels, prevent 'challenging behaviours' such as self-injury and ultimately increase awareness of their internal state to regulate emotions. Results showed a 98% accuracy rate, and that the system was successful in both Autistic and non-Autistic groups. Although it was concluded that high accuracy rates were possible, there was limited information regarding implementation or robust participatory evaluation methods.

Emotion Recognition

Affect recognition is the process of identifying what emotion an individual is feeling. Developing effective and robust algorithms that are able to recognise human affect is one of the key challenges in emotion recognition research and may have great implications on the usability and effectiveness of technological interventions that aid emotional regulation (Katsigiannis & Ramzan, 2017).

Knowledge about human emotional processing and insight into how multi-modal emotional stimuli can influence the emotional state is vital for the success of such developments (Rouast et al, 2019). Understanding the feasibility of automatic affect recognition could have significant implications for therapeutic technological solutions aiming to support emotion regulation in Autism.

Psychological research has defined affect in two different ways: *the categorical view of affect* where emotions are viewed in discrete categories and the *dimensional view of affect* where affective states

are represented in a continuous-valued space (Rouast et al, 2019; Zeng et al, 2009). Ekman et al, (1987) proposed the most popular explanation of emotions, suggesting that there are six basic universal emotional states (happiness, , anger, fear, sadness, disgust and surprise). However, more recent studies suggest that despite discrete emotions being reflective of the way individuals view emotions in daily life, they do not reflect a wide range of emotional states. The dimensional description of affect therefore offers a more robust theoretical underpinning (Russell & Mehrabian, 1977) and has been widely used to overcome methodological issues such as perception subjectivity e.g individual differences in cultural background, social context and personality (Scherer & Moors, 2019; Yang et al, 2017).

Valence: Positive or negative affective response from the image

Arousal: Intensity of the response

The Circumplex Model of Affect

Figure 7: The Circumplex Model of Affect

Emotion recognition based on the continuous model, The Circumplex Model of Affect (see figure 7 above) can be attempted either through regression modelling or classification modelling (Li et al,

2022). Regression modelling could be used to predict emotional ratings. Whereas classification analysis would involve dividing the emotional ratings into levels and assigning specific labels depending on which levels the emotional ratings are located. Then, the classification algorithm would be trained on these labels to then detect the emotional states.

The role of the autonomic nervous system (ANS) in emotion regulation and cognitive mechanisms

The link between neural mechanisms and emotions remains one of the key questions within cognitive neuroscience research (Li et al, 2022). An emotion involves three main processes: a physiological response as a result of how our bodies react to the emotion, cognitive appraisal and a behavioural element that relates to how we react to the emotion (Hollenstein & Lanteigne, 2014).

The physiological processes underlying emotion dysregulation commonly found in Autism are thought to be a result of differences in the autonomic nervous system (ANS) which influences and is affected by sensory processing and social interactions (Krupa et al, 2016). This may explain why some Autistic individuals may appear to be outwardly calm, whilst experiencing varying internal state of extremely high or low physiological arousal in response to environmental stimuli (Goodwin et al, 2006). These differences in emotion regulation were highlighted as a common experience of participants within the focus groups (outlined in chapter 4) and emphasise the need for adaptive support strategies that allow individuals to self-regulate their emotions.

Table 14: EEG Signal bands, frequencies & Characteristics

EEG band	Frequency range	Cognitive Characteristics
δ band	0.5–4Hz	Normally related to deep sleep although may be detected when an individual is awake.

θ band	4–8Hz	Usually seen in younger children, meditative states and drowsiness. Thought to be abnormal if seen in awake adults.
α band	8–13Hz	Associated with resting states. May disappear when an individual hears unfamiliar sounds or is anxious. The physiological meaning behind this signal remains unknown.
β band	13–30Hz	Normally seen in adults when problem solving or thinking.
γ band	> 30Hz	The presence of this signal may be due to certain brain diseases.

One of the challenges of EEG-based brain-computer interfaces is the high variability of the signals (See Table 14 above for an overview of EEG signal bands) due to individual differences in cognitive states. However, by averaging over a large enough number of samples it is still possible to distill sufficiently specific brain activity patterns and train a machine learning classifier to discern these patterns in real time (Blankertz et al, 2002).

The Benefits of Emotion Regulation Technology (Brain-Computer Interfaces)

The use of physiological signals to detect affective states has a wide variety of practical applications (Wagh & Vasanth, 2019). For example, in the past two decades, Brain-computer interfaces (BCI) have been regarded as one of the most non-invasive technologies for emotion regulation strategies. The detection of physiological signals for self emotion regulation (also known as neuro-feedback) has also been explored. neurofeedback has been successfully used as a mitigation tool for anxiety when used in combination with breathwork. For instance White et al (2017) demonstrated that breathing-based visual neurofeedback reduces symptoms in typically developing patients with anxiety and depression, while acoustically mediated deep breathing neurofeedback was shown by Crivelli et al (2019).

A review carried out by Friedrich (2014) examined neurofeedback training studies to improve social and emotional communication in Autism. Although this area of research is in its infancy, results showed that EEG-based neurofeedback training is a viable and user-centered approach. They also propose that the development of games involving social interactions that are able to give feedback on physiological responses may be effective. Likewise, Seo et al (2018) used neurofeedback via a smartphone to increase participants concentration. A non-invasive EEG headband was used to monitor activity over FP1 and FP2. Participants played archery game that involved gaining feedback. The researchers were able to successfully improve participant's concentration and effects were notably sustained following the training. Therefore the use of portable devices with show promising results within lab-settings have the potential to be transferred to real life.

Although the feasibility of such technology has been explored, research to enhance emotion regulation solutions for Autistic people is in it's infancy. Furthermore, how the design of such technology could increase usability and effectiveness remains unknown. Emotion regulation techniques based on physiological signals may provide a non-invasive and low-cost way of enabling individuals to self-regulate, leading to improved social and emotional interactions. To our

knowledge, this study is the first to explore and compare automatic physiologically (EEG & ECG) based classification along dimensions of arousal and valence in autistic adults and non-autistic adults.

6.3 Method

EEG Cap Sensor (EPOC(+))

To assess changes in the neural state. EEG methods are non-invasive and require only that the individual allow a cap on his/her head during the emotion recognition tasks.

Figure 7: Emotiv EPOC(+)

EPOC(+) offers 14-channel recording with a sampling frequency of 128Hz (256Hz in the EPOC+ version). With the channels recorded being: AF3, F7, F3, FC5, T7, P7, O1, O2, P8, T8, FC6, F4, F8, and AF4, positioned as shown in Figure 1. The recorded signal has a resolution of 14 or 16 bits per sample and electrode.

The Modified Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Scale (SSEI, see appendix 8)

The Modified Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Scale is a widely used 42 item self-report scale devised by Schutte et al (1998) and was based on Salovey & Mayer's (1990) initial model of

emotional intelligence. It involves a 5 point likert-scale (strongly agree to strongly disagree). Scores range from 42-205 with higher scores indicating higher trait emotional intelligence. All participants were categorized into high or low emotional intelligence by calculating the median score. This questionnaire takes around 5 minutes to complete.

Participant Demographics

Participants involved 23 Autistic and Non-Autistic Adults (Non-Autistic, N=18; Autistic, N=5). Table 15 below provides an overview of participant demographics. The study was open to both Autistic participants who have a clinical diagnosis of Autism and those who self-identify as Autistic. Autistic participants completed the The Ritvo Autism Asperger Diagnostic Scale–Revised (RAADS–R) and scored within the expected range (above 65).

Table 15: Participant Demographics

Participant	Age	Gender	Nationality
1	30	Male	Scottish
2	24	Female	Scottish
3	56	Male	Scottish
4	55	Female	Scottish
5	29	Male	Scottish
6	29	Female	Indian
7	59	Male	Scottish
8	28	Male	Scottish

9	21	Female	Indian
10	27	Female	Algerian
11	26	Male	British
12	48	Male	Spanish
13	23	Female	Chinese
14	26	Male	Nigerian
15	47	Female	Scottish
16	29	Male	British
17	27	Female	Scottish
18	34	Male	Scottish
19	33	Male	Scottish
20	22	Male	Scottish
21	21	Male	Scottish
22	44	Female	British
23	25	Female	Scottish

Inclusive Study Design

As outlined in Chapters 3, 4 and 5, the current thesis takes a neurodiversity affirming stance (one that champions difference, rather than deficit) and is firmly underpinned by the social model of disability. As such, every effort was made to ensure inclusivity in all aspects of the research process;

this involved obtaining feedback from Autistic participants regarding study design, protocol, and experiment set-up/environment. Prior to running the experiments within the Autistic group, a pilot experiment was carried out with one of the Autistic participants (of which the data was eventually used in the final data-set) which provided an opportunity to gain feedback. During this session, several important points were raised to increase the inclusivity of the sensory environment e.g changing the lighting within the lab setting according to individual preferences, noting whether or not the computer sound may be distracting, highlighting the aim of the ‘baseline’ period following each block of emotional stimuli. Inclusive adaptations are important not only to represent participants with a wider range of abilities, needs and preferences, but also to include people in research who otherwise may not be able to.

6.4 Emotion Elicitation

The OASIS (gold standard method of eliciting emotions) and Geneva Affective Database (GAPED) database were used to select the emotional pictures. Both these databases have previously been used with autistic individuals. Table 16 below provides an overview of both databases.

Table 16: Summary of GAPED & OASIS Databases

Database	Features	Advantages
Geneva Affective Database (GAPED)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reports ratings on three scales (arousal, valence, dominance) - 750 images - Negative images include spiders, snakes & scenes that 	Provides pre-rated emotional images (Dan-Glauser & Scherer, 2011)

emotions related to violating legal and moral norms (e.g mistreatment of humans and animals).

- Positive/Neutral images include Nature scenes, babies, inanimate objects.

- Each picture is rated between 0-100 (100 being highest arousal, most positive)

- Mostly used in neurotypical populations () and one study focused on Autistic children (Sarabadani & Schudlo et al, 2019)

OASIS

- Reports ratings on three scales (arousal, valence, dominance)

- Based on circumplex model

- Themes include humans, animals, objects, scenes

- 900 images

- Open access

- Reliable and consistent across gender groups (Kurdi & Lozano, 2017).

- More up to date stimuli set compared with other datasets (e.g IAPS)

6.5 Procedure for Emotional Stimuli Selection

Eliciting emotional reactions from participants is a complex and difficult process, therefore choosing the most appropriate and successful stimuli is vital. In order to eradicate bias usually found in manual stimuli selection, emotional stimuli were selected according to the distance from the neutral state (0,0) shown in the diagram below. The valence-arousal space is subdivided into four quadrants: low arousal/low valence (LALV), low arousal/high valence (LAHV), high arousal/low valence (HALV) and high arousal/high valence (HAHV). Figure 9 below presents the image selected method and Figure 10 shows the images before and after selection.

Figure 9: Image Selection Method

Images before selection

Final data set

Figure 10: Images before and after selection

6.5 Image Selection Validation

The experience of emotion is subjective and various factors impact individual differences in the experience of the same emotion, such as previous experiences and social context. One of the main challenges in emotion recognition research is gaining consistency between the emotion the participant is expected to feel and the experienced emotion. In order to ensure as much reliability as possible, the current study used the Self-Assessment Manikin Scale (Bradley & Lang, 1994) see Figure 12 below. This self-assessment tool involves participants rating their emotions after certain emotional stimuli presentations. This gives a good indication if the stimuli evoked the expected emotions and if the stimuli evoked similar emotions across all participants. Table 17 below shows the emotions that were expected within each quadrant.

Table 17: Expected Emotions to be Induced in Each Quadrant (Rahman & Sarkar, 2021)

Quadrant	Expected Emotions
HA, PV	Excited, pleased, Happy
HA, NV	Nervous, Angry, Annoying
LA, NV	Bored, Sleepy, Sad
LA, PV	Peaceful, Relaxed, Calm

6.5 Experimental Protocol

An information sheet will be provided to participants and a verbal overview of what will happen in the study will be given (Pictures of the sensors will be shown before the session begins). Participants will be reminded of their right to withdraw from the experiment at any time.

Sensors (ECG and EEG) will be attached to the participant. The task will be explained in depth, before a practice session is carried out to ensure the participant understands the task.

Participants will take part in 12 blocks showing emotional pictures, each of these will be separated by a 2 minute baseline period. 12 emotional pictures will be included in each block, each picture will be shown for 10 seconds each and presented in a random order. Pictures in each task will elicit one of the four affective states (high arousal/positive valence, low arousal/positive valence, high arousal/negative valence, and low arousal/negative valence). 5 minutes before and after the session will allow time for the participant to listen calming music to ensure the participant leaves in the same emotional state they entered.

Images Order

BLOCK 1 - High Arousal/Negative Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 2 - High Arousal/Positive Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 3 - Low Arousal/Negative Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 4 - Low Arousal/Positive Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 5 - High Arousal/Negative Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 6 - High Arousal/Positive Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 7 - Low Arousal/Negative Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 8 - Low Arousal/Positive Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 9 - High Arousal/Negative Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 10 - High Arousal/Positive Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 11 - Low Arousal/Negative Valence (12 images)

BLOCK 12 - Low Arousal/Positive Valence (12 images)

Timing of Emotional Stimuli Elicitation

Figure 11 below outlines the experiment timing.

Figure 11: Timing of Emotional Stimuli Elicitation

Figure 12: Emotion Self-assessment: Self-Assessment Manikin scale

6.5 Signal Processing and Analysis

Figure 13. Overview of Pre-processing & Analysis Procedure

Pre-processing

Raw EEG data contains noise (or artefacts). The role of pre-processing is to remove information from the signals that is not related to any emotional patterns and to avoid having any noise that could

potentially impact results (Sagano ski et al, 2020). EEG noise is commonly referred to as being in one of two categories (subject-related or technique related). Subject-related noise includes other physiological signals e.g electrocardiogram (ECG) or body movement, blinking or sweating. On the other hand, technique related noise refers to electrical environment related disruption e.g power line interference, cable movement, dry electrodes or low battery (Hu & Zhang, 2019). According to Torres & Torres (2020) there are three main types of filter commonly used to remove noise or artefacts. These include: (1) high frequency filters (e.g low-pass and high-pass), (2) low-frequency filters, (3) notch filters.

In the current study, EEG signals were pre-processed based on the PREP pipeline (Bigdely-Shamloby et al, 2015) using EEGLAB (an extension). First a Butterworth bandpass filter between 0.4 and 65 Hz was applied which takes the clean EEG signal, splits it into windows corresponding to each valence and arousal score/image block, then extracts features from each channel. Filtering was then applied in order to remove line-noise and the EEG signal was referenced relative to an estimate of the “true” average reference. Finally, bad channels were detected and interpolated relative to the reference.

Feature Extraction

Feature extraction aims to identify the most compact and valuable set of features and is vital to enhance the classification (Subasi, 2019). The power Spectral Density (PSD) refers to the ‘frequency content’ of the signal and is a measure of a signals power intensity in the frequency domain. Three features were taken from each block as there were (Normalized First Difference, Normalized Second Difference, Shannon Entropy). Each block was then transformed into the frequency domain and the power spectral density the following features were extracted: Delta (0.4 - 4 Hz) band power, Theta (4 - 8 Hz) band power, Low Alpha (8 - 10 Hz) band power, Alpha (8 - 13 Hz) band power, Beta (13 - 30

Hz) band power, Gamma (30 - 64 Hz) band power, Normalized First Difference, Normalized Second Difference. This resulted in 126 features per window (participant).

Dimensionality Reduction/Principle Component Analysis

This stage increases the efficiency of classification algorithms by focusing on further reduction of dimensionality (see Figure 14 below). Principle component analysis was used as a dimensional reduction technique in order to minimize the number of training features by grouping the features together. This method is able to minimise the error rate and computational time which are often a result of unnecessary features. The main advantage of using PCA is that it speeds up training time and has been shown to improve accuracy (Jin & Wang, 2007). An advantage of using Principle Component Analysis compared to other similar frequently used pre-processing methods (e.g Independent component analysis) is that it compresses the data and allows for data separation (Torres & Torres et al, 2020).

Figure 14: Dimensionality Reduction Procedure

Classification Results

Emotional states are made up of different dimensions (arousal and valence). Classification analysis involves separating values based on whether or not they are higher or lower than neutral. The current study addressed two classification problems: differentiating between two classes for (1) Arousal: high arousal (HA) Negative Valence (NV). For valence, they were High Valence (HV) and Low Arousal (LA). Classification analysis was carried out to assess the feasibility of the features extracted from the EEG signals to identify the induced affective states of the participants. Three separate

classifiers were compared; Support Vector Machine (SVM), K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) Classification & Ensemble of Trees Classification. An overview of each classifier is provided in the following section.

Support Vector Machine Classification

There has been a rise in the use of Support vector machines (SVMs) for emotion classification as they provide a powerful classification method, explore structures and offer predictions within complicated and large data sets (Miller et al, 2020). SVMs use a predictive algorithm to learn multivariate patterns that are able to discriminate between groups. This type of classification method has been known to outperform other classification methods in numerous studies (Boateng & Otoo et al, 2020: Verma & Tiwary, 2014). In a systematic review carried out Hamada & Zaidan (2018) by it was found that 11 out of 23 studies that used particular classifiers employed SVM. The use of SVM is known to be particularly beneficial for studies with lower sample sizes.

In the current study, Support Vector Machine with Gaussian Kernel was used as it tends to have improved results compared within other linear and non-linear analyses. Support Vector Machine classification has been known to be the most popular classifier for EEG signal analysis. The aim of Support Vector Machine classification is to maximise the distance between the nearest sample and the hyperplane. The points nearest the hyperplane are referred to as support vectors.

The distance between the hyperplane and support vectors is identified by the margin and the greater margin highlights increased classification accuracy.

The Support Vector Machine function can be written as

$$f(x) = \alpha_j \gamma_j k(s_j, x) + b,$$

x is the input vector (in this case feature vector extracted from EEG signals), k is the kernel function, s_j denote support vectors, α_i are the weights and b is the bias.

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) Classification & Ensemble of Trees Classification

K-Nearest Neighbors (KNN) looks for the distances between a query and examples within the dataset, obtaining the specified number of examples (K) closest to the query. The most common label is then found (in classification analysis) (Rigol-Sanchez & Chica-Olmo, 2003). KNN is known to be straight-forward to implement and is commonly used within emotion classification studies.

However, a disadvantage of KNN is that as the data set increases it becomes significantly slower.

A further classifier which was considered was Ensembles of Trees. Ensemble of trees was considered as it has been known to surpass accuracy rates from other models (Dissanayake & Rajapaksha, 2019) and is known to be among the most widely used classification algorithms (Rahman & Sarkar, 2021). This method can also reduce overfitting as it merges predications and is known to have a robust structure (Unnisa & Zia, 2020).

Results from the classification analysis are outlined in Tables 18, 19 and 20 below. Please note: MCC (Mathews Correlation Coefficient) was used instead of an F1 score due to F1 scores being asymmetric.

Table 18: Support Vector Machine Classification Performance

Group		Accuracy	MCC	Number of Components
Autistic & Non-	Arousal	66%	0.3	37
Autistic	Valence	59.9%	0.269	48

Autistic	Arousal	67.5%	0.589	10
	Valence	70%	0.348	9
Non-Autistic	Arousal	67%	0.438	33
	Valence	57.9%	57.9	43

Table 19: Ensemble of Trees Classification Performance

Group		Accuracy	MCC	Number of Components
Autistic & Non-Autistic	Arousal	65.2%	0.17	6
	Valence	56.5%	0.08	36
Autistic	Arousal	71%	0.692	13
	Valence	68%	0.262	5
Non-Autistic	Arousal	70.7%	0.3	33
	Valence	52.4%	0.06	43

Table 20: k-nearest neighbors (KNN) Classification Performance

Group		Accuracy	MCC	Number of Components
	Arousal	65.7%	0.24	8

Autistic & Non- Autistic	Valence	53.6%	0.03	4
Autistic	Arousal	60%	0.22	4
	Valence	58.5%	-0.08	7
Non-Autistic	Arousal	68.8%	0.29	4
	Valence	49.2%	-0.06	43

Analysis of Self-reported & Expected Responses

The Emotion Self-assessment: Self-Assessment Manikin scale (SAM) was used following each image block for each participant to rate how each block made them feel in terms of valence (happy or sad), and arousal (excited or calm). Participants answers were compared with the expected corresponding affective state (according to the image labels in the datasets). We were interested to know if participants answers were consistent with the expected ratings for the emotional stimuli.

A paired samples t-test was conducted to compare the average values provided by all participants and their expected answers (the values from the GAPED & OASIS datasets). For Valence, results showed no significant difference between self-reported valence/arousal scores and expected values according to the previously rated datasets ($M=0.6$, $SD=1.6$, $M=0.34$); $t(16)=-2.23$, $p = 0.151$ (two-tailed). For Arousal, results showed no significant difference between self-reported valence/arousal scores and expected values according to the previously rated datasets ($M=0.34$, $SD=2.47$); $t(16)=-.926$, $p = 0.571$. These results suggest that self-reported valence/arousal scores were in line with the expected values (originally rated in the respective datasets). The hypothesis that there would be no

significant differences between self-reported valence/arousal scores and expected values according to the previously rated datasets is therefore supported.

In addition, a Pearson correlation coefficient was computed to assess the linear relationship between higher emotional intelligence and average self-report ratings/expected ratings (based on previous ratings of the images) of emotional stimuli when viewing the emotional images. Results showed a weak positive correlation between the two variables, $r(21) = 0.22$, $p = 0.29$

6.6 Limitations

Firstly, despite using 'gold standard' emotion recognition databases to induce emotions in participants, these images may not always reflect or induce real life emotional reactions. This is a widespread issue in emotion recognition research and could impact how well such models/systems perform in real life environments. Secondly, due to limits on time – other measures of physiological signal were not obtained (e.g ECG, Skin conductance). Some studies have found improved classification performance when multiple physiological signals are combined. Thirdly, the experiment lasted around 40 minutes, which may have caused participants to become fatigued or lose concentration which could have impacted accuracy rates. Future work could overcome this issue by carrying out within-subject comparisons in a study involving multiple sessions. In addition, a factor which may have impacted reliability of results is the participants being repeatedly exposed to emotional images which could have caused less intense responses either within one block or throughout the whole session. However, it could be argued emotional images that evoked less intensity due to fatigue – may indicate successful detection of less intense emotions which is more reflective of real life situations.

Furthermore, generalisability of results may have been impacted by the sample size (N=25).

Although the total sample size is in line with other emotion classification studies who generally have 20-30 participants (for review see: Rahman & Sarkar, 2021), a larger sample size in each group (Autistic and Non-Autistic) would have enabled further comparisons and more advanced statistical analyses. Although every attempt was made to recruit more Autistic participants, several Autistic people who considered taking part decided not to due to the sensory challenges involved with wearing an EEG headset. Around 45 to 95% of Autistic people perceive and process stimuli differently to non-Autistic people which can involve being hypersensitive to certain textures, noises, lighting or sensations (Kiep & Spek et al, 2023; Taels & Feyaerts et al, 2023). This may explain the difficulties in recruitment. Sensory sensitivity also may have impacted potential participants decision to put themselves forward to take part. Therefore, sensory sensitivity must be taken into account when designing future wearable technologies. In order to address this challenge, a key area for future research would be to explore sensory preferences in wearable technology designs from a Neurodiversity perspective.

Despite these challenges in participant recruitment, the total sample size is in line with other similar research. Suhaimi et al (2020) suggested that emotion classification studies should recruit at least 10 participants to reach reliable statistical significance. Furthermore, in a review paper investigating the recognition of emotions using EEG signals, Rahman & Sarkar (2021) found that sample sizes across 54 studies⁷ (the most cited studies) ranged from 8 to 32 participants, which is line with the current study. The authors propose that increasing the number of participants may improve accuracy rates.

6.7 Discussion

⁷ Rahman & Sarkar (2021) selected articles that had citations above a designated number.

The overall aim of this study was to investigate the feasibility and obtain an indication of accuracy using a classification model for EEG-based affect detection in Autistic and non-Autistic adults, as opposed to achieving a novel classification method. It must therefore be noted that the results of the current study should be observed with caution and that more advanced machine learning or deep learning methods in combination with a larger sample size would improve reliability and may achieve higher accuracy. The following discussion of results will be structured according to each research question.

Machine learning methods were used to provide insight into both the neurophysiological basis underlying emotion processing and to assess the feasibility of EEG techniques (signal processing and classification analysis) for the detection of affective states. Results showed that affective states (Valence and Arousal, split into four emotion categories) can be classified from physiological signals (EEG signals). In the Autistic and Non-Autistic groups which included all participants, Support Vector Machine with Gaussian Kernel produced the highest accuracy rates (Arousal 66% and Valence 59%). In the Autistic group, Ensemble of Trees produced the highest accuracy rates (Arousal 71%) and SVM produced the highest accuracy rate for valence (70%). In the Non-Autistic group, Ensemble of Trees produced the highest accuracy rate for Arousal (70.7%) and SVM produced the highest accuracy rate for Valence (57%). The higher accuracy rate for arousal compared to valence overall may be due to the potency of particular stimuli, for instance, some images may be further away from neutral than others. Although accuracy rates for arousal and valence in both groups was fairly similar, the Autistic group produced a higher accuracy rate for arousal across both SVM (67%) and Ensemble of Trees (71%) classifiers. This is an interesting result and may explained by differences in sensory and emotion processing in Autistic people causing them to experience emotional states more intensely. As discussed earlier on in this chapter the physiological processes underlying emotion processing commonly found in Autism are thought to be a result of differences in the autonomic nervous system (ANS) which influences and is affected by sensory processing (Krupa et al, 2016).

These results are fairly consistent with other similar work, for instance Soleymani & Lichtenauer (2011) produced accuracy rates for arousal: 52% and valence 57%. Nakisa & Rastgoo (2020) also successfully classified affective states based on four quadrants of dimensional emotions and found accuracy rates of 71% and 70% respectively. Overall, our results were on the lower end when comparing to other methods (e.g Chen & Zhang, 2020; Khare & Bajaj, 2021). However, an explanation for this may be that many of these studies were based on a two class emotion classification, whereas in the current study our model was classified based on four dimensional quadrants. In a review of human emotions using EEG signals, Rahman & Sarkar (2021) found that 70% of studies also used Support Vector Machine (e.g Zheng et al, 2015; Wang & Nie, 2011) which is in line with the current study.

Torres et al (2020) carried out a Survey in EEG-Based brain computer interface emotion recognition. Results identified trends and outlined a comparative analysis of emotion inducing methods, feature extraction, feature selection, classification methods and various performance evaluation methods. In the reviewed systems, the most common emotion elicitation method was video clips (65%). Most studies either included participants in a range from 31-40 (53%) and 11-20 (31%), which is also consistent with the current study. Furthermore, 49% of studies used already available datasets and 23% of studies used self-generated datasets (as did the current study). An advantage of generating our own dataset in the current study was that it provided an opportunity to compare results across groups. The feature extraction methods used in the current study were also in line with the majority of reviewed systems (38% used features in the frequency domain and 24% used features in the time-domain). As Torres et al (2020) point out, although trends may be identified - it is difficult to compare approaches due to such a variation in methods and protocols used. This is an important limitation to bear in mind and it is important for future work to consider how systems might be evaluated in similar conditions.

Taken together, as research on EEG-based emotion recognition has been increasingly growing, there has been great promise of the potential for such systems to support emotional self-awareness, emotion regulation and ultimately increase overall health and well-being. This type of technology may have huge benefits for Autistic people who report higher levels of anxiety, yet only a small group of studies have focused on both Autistic and non-Autistic groups. Results from the current study aim to address this gap in the literature.

6.8 Conclusion

Overall, results from the current study suggest that EEG signals have detectable patterns that can be classified to identify different affective states. A vital ethical consideration outlined in the previous chapter (Chapter 4) was whether or not the detection of emotions in such devices would be accurate. This chapter aimed to explore this issue by obtaining an indication of accuracy for a classification model aimed at detecting affective states. Although the results are encouraging, they should be noted with caution as further work is needed to develop a universal, reliable and ethical system of affect identification. Nevertheless, to our knowledge, this study is one of a small cluster of studies focused on EEG-based emotion recognition in both Autistic and non-Autistic populations and is the first to consider how differences in emotional intelligence and sensory processing sensitivity may have important implications not only for affect detection systems but also technology design. Results from this study provide an important contribution to a new and emerging area within Artificial Intelligence research. Affect sensitive interfaces hold the promise of providing adaptable systems for emotion regulation strategies. It is hoped that future developments will be co-produced alongside Autistic people and their allies to create meaningful, autonomous devices that initiate opportunities for emotional self-awareness, emotion regulation and stress reduction techniques.

7. Overall Discussion and Conclusion

7.1 Chapter Introduction

Taken together, this thesis offers a unique insight into the potential of real time technology aimed at supporting Autistic emotion regulation. In exploring Autistic experiences, perceptions and expectations of real time technologies based on physiological signals (EEG signals) and presenting a classification model based on machine learning methods for affect detection in Autistic and non-Autistic samples, this thesis provides an important basis for future work in this area. This chapter will outline how each thesis aim was met, theoretical and empirical contributions to knowledge, implications for practice and novel directions for Autism research.

7.2 Aim 1

The first thesis aim was to review literature on the use of affective technology aiming to improve Autistic social and emotional communication. A systematic review focused on four types of technologies (mobile applications, robotics, computer based/games and virtual reality) that specifically aim to support Autistic social and emotional communication. Five databases were used to search for articles published between 2014-2022, resulting in 28 studies that met the inclusion criteria. Results provide evidence that, as technology advances, there is potential for technology to support Autistic people in their daily life. These results are in line with previous empirical research (Alabdulkareem & Alhakbani (2022); Mesa-Gresa & Gil-Gómez, 2018; Kowallik & Schweinberger, 2019). However, many of the studies identified did not take a neurodiversity affirming stance, which may explain varied success. Results also highlight the challenges that still exist in affective digital

technology development (e.g lack of robust methodology, lack of follow up evaluation methods, high male to female ratio in recruitment, lack of co-participatory methods). Very few of the studies identified were geared towards both neurodivergent and neurotypical people (the current thesis suggests this is an important avenue for future research and is discussed further in this chapter). Overall, the results from the systematic review provide a basis for understanding what technological supports are being developed to support Autistic social and emotional communications and what design factors could be improved to better meet individual needs. The systematic review resulted in several important findings across different technological aids including mobile apps, VR, computers and robotics, which will be summarised and discussed below.

Firstly, results showed that recent research exploring the use of mobile apps to support Autistic socio-emotional communication has expanded on more traditional methods (e.g picture cards) used by parents or health/social care workers (Bondy & Frost, 1994). As technology advances, mobile touchscreen devices with augmentative and alternative communication Apps are increasingly becoming promising alternatives for traditional speech generating devices and picture exchange communication systems. Several studies have altered and improved the exhaustive training procedures of picture exchange communication systems for use in speech generating training with mobile devices (King, Takeguchi et al, 2014). However, it was noted in several studies that there was limited effect found in real socio-emotional communication (Fletcher-watson et al, 2016; Golan et al, 2009; Hopkins et al, 2011; Williams et al, 2012). For instance Fletcher-watson et al (2016) found no significant differences between the experimental group and control group following intervention in both parent report measures and parent-child play measures. These results therefore provided a basis for Chapter 4 which qualitatively explored experiences and expectations of technologies based on physiological signals (EEG).

Secondly, although several VR studies have shown promise, many questions still remain. For instance, issues with generalizability, single user designs and limited sample sizes. Such limitations

may explain why VR has not yet been widely implemented within healthcare settings. Further work is needed to explore how VR interventions implemented in controlled environments would transfer into real life situations or the positive impact on emotion regulation would last over time.

Furthermore, results showed that many VR studies focused on eye-gaze technology, which involve wearable eye trackers and co-ordinated mouse use, which may not be suitable for those who have increased sensory sensitivity or motor co-ordination issues.

Thirdly, data from the computer-based studies showed that most previous research has focused on 'teaching' these skills in a fun and interactive manner. This approach is fast becoming out of touch with recent advances within the neurodiversity paradigm which suggest that technology should not try to change or 'fix' core Autistic traits. In reviewing the literature in this area, it was clear that many studies have been based on outdated theoretical models e.g the medical model (outlined in Chapter 1). These results therefore served as a foundation for the current research to explore real-time technologies based on physiological signals which may create a more personalised experience, increase control, and promote independence for the user.

Fourthly, data showed that progress in advancing robotic interventions as clinically valuable and worthwhile in interventions for Autistic individuals has been limited (Begum et al, 2016). An explanation for this could be methodological limitations within human-robot interaction (HRI) studies; many studies lacked a robust, standardised research design or follow-up evaluation, therefore data produced is less appealing to clinicians and health/social care professionals. Clinical research on Autism intervention is generally based on a systematic evaluation of evidence and geared towards rigorous research design such as randomised control trails (RCTs -White et al, 2007; Kouijzer et al, 2013).

To conclude, the systematic review served the purpose of investigating what type of technologies Autistic people use and shed light on why many technologies may go unused or aren't widely used in practice. One common limitation across the reviewed literature was that results didn't always

transfer to real life scenarios. An innovative method to overcome this challenge includes technologies based on physiological signals which can be used in real time. It was therefore concluded that an important direction for further work would be to qualitatively explore the experiences, perceptions, and expectations of both technology use in general (any type) and (more specifically), real time technology based on physiological signals. In reviewing the literature, it was evident that real time technology based on physiological signals would be an innovative area to explore within the current thesis. As such, the systematic review provided a strong basis for the subsequent qualitative phase of the thesis.

7.3 Aim 2

The second thesis aim was to explore experiences, perceptions and expectations of technology aimed at improving social and emotional communication, including real time affect detection technology based on physiological signals (EEG). Studies assessing the feasibility of emotion regulation technology via physiological signals for Autistic people are increasingly showing promise (refs here), yet there had been no previous exploration of views from the Autistic community on the benefits/challenges such technology may present in practice. Focus groups with Autistic people, parents of Autistic people, health/social care workers and educational staff who support Autistic individuals at college level were conducted to gain insight into experiences and expectations of technological supports aimed at supporting emotion regulation. This was the first qualitative study to assess views from the Autistic community on the benefits/challenges real time affect detection technologies may present.

Reflexive Thematic Analysis generated three themes: (1) Communication Challenges (2) Benefits/Challenges of Emotion Regulation Technology (3) 'How' technology is implemented.

Communication challenges, specifically related to emotion regulation were discussed across all groups. This included difficulties in identifying emotions in others and expressing own emotions. Results highlighted the impact this can have on mental health, not only in Autistic individuals but also families and carers. These results are in line with recent literature that suggests Autistic people are more likely to experience higher levels of anxiety, mental health difficulties/mental illness and suicidal ideation (Lai et al, 2017; Linden & Best, 2023). Identifying supports that improve mental health of Autistic individuals is the top research priority within the Autistic community (James Lind Alliance Priority Setting Partnerships, 2016). Therefore, given the strong association between emotion regulation difficulties and mental health, Chapters 4 & 5: an exploration of how technology should support emotion regulation provides an important and original contribution to Autism research.

Benefits and challenges of emotion regulation technology were discussed, specifically including views of real-time technology based on physiological signals. The need for low-cost, person-centered, and adaptable technology to cater to a wide variety of abilities and needs was evident. For instance, it was highlighted that technology is often more geared towards individuals with an intellectual disability or complex needs and rarely aimed at those with a higher IQ. Results also highlighted important ethical considerations; accuracy, data privacy and clear purpose. These factors were identified within the focus group as being vital to the success of technologies based on physiological signals. Chapter 5 discusses these issues in further depth and also provides rationale for Study 3 (quantitative phase) which explores accuracy rates for a classification model aiming to detect affect states in Autistic and non-Autistic adults.

Findings indicated that more focus should be placed on 'How' technology is implemented. In line with existing literature, 'how' technology is implemented has often been overlooked both within research and practice. This could pertain to both at home use and use of technology within health/social care settings e.g community based care. Results suggested that a more holistic

approach (taking into account the environment, sensory processing, and individual life goals) could lead to increased usability and success. 'How' technology is implemented is especially important for those who may have difficulties in communicating needs/preferences. In line with Damian Milton, who argued that 'technology is most effective when it is used by Autistic people on their own terms' (Brosnan & Parsons et al, 2016) results also emphasised the need for autonomous emotion regulation technology.

7.4 Aim 3

The third thesis aim was to investigate the feasibility of physiological signals (EEG) to detect affective states in Autistic and Non-Autistic people. The rationale for this study was that (1) there is currently no consensus within the literature as to an optimum method based on machine learning techniques for affect detection. (2) this area of research is in its infancy and as such there is a scarcity of studies exploring affect detection in Autistic populations. (3) results from Chapter 4 indicated concerns around accuracy within technologies based on physiological signals. This study therefore aimed to provide an indication of accuracy rates using EEG signal processing and machine learning methods.

Results showed that affective states based on two classes (Valence and Arousal) and split into four emotion categories (low arousal/low valence (LALV), low arousal/high valence (LAHV), high arousal/low valence (HALV) and high arousal/high valence (HAHV) can be classified from EEG signals. Higher accuracies for each group (Autistic and Non-Autistic, Autistic only and Non-Autistic only) were found using different classifiers (Support vector machine, Ensemble of Trees, and k-nearest neighbor), this was achieved by optimizing components for both arousal and valence classification performance within each group. In the Autistic and Non-Autistic groups which included all participants, Support Vector Machine with Gaussian Kernel produced the highest accuracy rates (Arousal 66% and Valence 59%). In the Autistic group, Ensemble of Trees produced the highest

accuracy rates (Arousal 71%) and SVM produced the highest accuracy rate for valence (70%). In the Non-Autistic group, Ensemble of Trees produced the highest accuracy rate for Arousal (70.7%) and SVM produced the highest accuracy rate for Valence (57%).

The correlation between higher/lower emotional intelligence and actual/expected ratings of the emotional stimuli was investigated. Results showed a weak positive correlation between higher emotional intelligence and the average self-reported/expected ratings of the emotional stimuli, indicating that those with higher trait emotional intelligence have higher scores in emotion recognition. This finding is in line with Wirawan & Wardoyo, et al (2022) who suggests that individual differences in participant characteristics (e.g personality traits and cognitive processing) strongly influence EEG-based affect detection. Furthermore, to our knowledge, this is the first study to consider differences in trait emotional intelligence in relation to affect identification.

7.5 Contributions to Knowledge

In taking an inter-disciplinary approach and drawing on methods from key disciplines (psychology, health, and computer science) this thesis provides an original contribution that would not have been possible from one discipline alone. Combined, the findings enhance our understanding of affect detection in Autistic and non-Autistic populations, the benefits/challenges such technology may present and 'how' such technologies may be best implemented according to individual needs. As discussed in previous chapters, research on real time technology that is able to adapt to individual needs and support emotion regulation strategies remains in its' infancy and although previous research has shown promise, many challenges remain, including there being no consensus on an optimum classification method for affect detection, ethical considerations and limited studies adopting co-participatory methods. To summarize, this thesis makes the following contributions to knowledge:

- (5) Systematic literature review focusing on four key technology types (robotics, computer-based, mobile apps, virtual reality)
- (6) To our knowledge, the focus groups are the first study to qualitatively explore Autistic experiences and expectations of real time technology based on physiological signals (EEG)
- (7) A conceptual framework based on a thematic map of the focus group data is presented in Chapter 5. This provides a basis for exploring the ethics of autonomous technologies based on physiological signals (EEG) that aim to support Autistic emotion regulation
- (8) A classification system for affect detection using machine learning techniques is presented. This provides an indication of accuracy for affect identification within Autistic and non-Autistic populations.

7.6 Recommendations for Practice

This thesis provides several important recommendations for health/social care professionals, Autism researchers and computer scientists specialising in affective technologies.

Firstly, as highlighted in Chapter 5, active engagement, and open discussion of ethical concerns for technologies based on physiological signals for affective state detection is vital if the area is to progress. In order to increase the clinical relevance and broader public acceptance of such devices, the research community must prioritise ethical considerations through honest communication with end users. This not only means a focus on co-participatory methods (working alongside end users) to further understand expectations but also to explore how challenges in data privacy and accuracy might be overcome.

Secondly, Autistic individuals, families, and those who support Autistic people in professional settings (e.g health/social care and education) would benefit from more training in how to use technologies aimed at supporting emotion regulation. This could include more awareness around what types of technologies are available, more in depth training on design features and knowledge

about how to implement new technologies according to individual needs. One way to implement these strategies within health/social care settings could be to employ a designated trainer or a 'go to' person within services. Emphasis must be placed on person centered strategies and adapting environments rather than the person, for example, the sensory environment (lighting, temperature, textures, noise). Furthermore, results showed the importance of technology that promotes independence. This could be achieved by designing technologies that provide scaffolding opportunities to support emotion regulation e.g providing prompts.

Thirdly, results from Chapter 4 indicated that acceptability and useability of technologies may be improved by adopting needs based designs, as opposed to developing technologies solely 'for Autistic people'. Autistic participants highlighted that they would be more likely to use technology if it wasn't solely directed at them. This was an interesting finding and has very rarely (if at all) been considered within previous literature and may explain why many technologies have varied success. This is an important avenue for computer scientists and Autism researchers alike, as designing technologies that are adaptable to needs, rather than aiming to support specific 'difficulties' based on diagnostic criteria, means technologies can be beneficial to wider populations. Furthermore, needs based designs do not 'other' and can foster a greater sense of belonging. Adopting a 'universal design' has been previously suggested by Autism researchers as best practice within educational environments, however to our knowledge, this thesis is the first to propose such an approach for wearable technology design.

7.7 Overall Limitations

One limitation of this thesis was the small sample size within Chapter 6. Although findings indicated an indication of accuracy rates in both Autistic and non-Autistic populations, a larger number of participants would have increased generalizability. It would have also allowed more complex data

analysis e.g to explore if differences in emotional intelligence or sensory processing between Autistic and non-Autistic groups. However, such small sample sizes are very typical within affective state detection studies due to the challenges and time consuming nature of data acquisition from physiological signals (EEG signals) e.g., suggests sample sizes are typically between 20-30 participants. Although the current thesis is within a typical range, it is important to acknowledge how this work could be expanded on within larger sample sizes.

Furthermore, generalisability may also have been impacted due to the lack of representation of Autistic individuals with additional learning needs or more complex healthcare needs. Although every effort was made to include participants with a wide variety of needs (e.g non-verbal, co-existing disabilities) participants scored within the average IQ range, therefore results may not take account of needs across a broader cognitive/ability range. Whilst this was a limitation of the current research, it is also a reflection of a much larger challenge within Autism research. As discussed in Chapter 5, technology may offer unique and creative opportunities for such populations to learn about research/provide informed consent, making this an important topic for future work.

7.8 Future Directions

As technology advances at speed within the modern era, wearable monitoring technologies (e.g those based on physiological signals) increasingly show potential for healthcare applications, mental health settings and at home support. Whilst the benefits of this has huge potential, many challenges remain. This thesis sheds light on these key benefits and challenges, and provides a conceptual basis for further work within an emerging area of research.

Firstly, future work exploring affect detection/indication must take a participatory approach, involving end users both within the research design process and in any evaluation of technologies. If wearable technology based on physiological signals to support Autistic emotion regulation is to be

successful, Autistic people must be involved in the process and development. Furthermore, future work should consider how universal needs based designs can improve usability, effectiveness, and uptake of technologies. Results from the current research indicate that this approach could promote less 'othering' and a greater sense of belonging. This would involve not targeting technologies towards a particular diagnosis, and instead, focusing on how individual needs can be met..

Secondly, further research is needed to ascertain a universal machine learning model for affect detection that takes into account individual differences in cognitive, affective, and functional processes (e.g sensory needs, learning needs, high/low IQ). Accuracy rates may be improved by investigating emotion recognition from multiple modalities (indeed, several studies are now exploring this). However, a challenge that must be overcome is that fusing modalities by equally weighting them does not always guarantee improved classification accuracy (Zhang & Yin, et al (2020)). A crucial area for investigation is therefore distinguishing priority among the modalities for different emotions.

Whilst the current work makes an important addition to the small cluster of studies focused on affect detection in Autistic populations, more research is needed to ensure such devices are reliable and ethical. Importantly, the current research provides a conceptual framework for research focused on the ethics of wearable monitoring (outlined in Chapter 5). Future work could expand on this by taking a co-participatory approach to qualitatively explore these areas (data privacy, autonomy, informed consent, and accuracy) in more depth. Qualitative investigation in these areas is essential; developers within affective computing must seek meaningful collaboration with psychology, clinical and health disciplines to drive both the design and implementation of autonomous and ethical technologies. In line with Pukki & Bettin et al, (2022) results from this thesis indicate that open and honest conversations around the ethics in Autism research is vital.

7.9 Overall Conclusion

To conclude, this inter-disciplinary exploration of technology based on physiological signals (EEG) aimed at supporting Autistic emotion regulation provides an original contribution to existing literature. It emphasises the value of integrating disciplines (psychology and computer science) to answer complex research questions and guide future technological developments. Ultimately, if technology based on physiological signals is to be successful in supporting Autistic emotion regulation, co-participatory, strengths-based, inclusive approaches must be adopted to prioritise Autistic experiences, voices, and expertise.

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Appendix 2: Guidance for The McMaster Critical Review Form (Law, M., Stewart, D., Pollock, N., Letts, L., Bosch, J., & Westmorland, M., 1998)

Please note this is a shortened version of the guidance, specific to the questions used in the current review.

<p>Relevant Design?</p> <p>Some of the important issues to consider in determining if the study design is the most appropriate include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge of the topic/issue: If little is known about an issue, a more exploratory method is appropriate, for example a case study or a cross-sectional design. As our level of knowledge increases, study designs become more rigorous, where most variables that could influence the outcome are understood and can be controlled by the researcher. The most rigorous design is the RCT. • Outcomes: If the outcome under study is easily quantified and has well-developed standardized assessment tools available to measure it, a more rigorous design (eg. An RCT) is appropriate. If outcomes are not fully understood yet, such as quality of life, then a design that explores different factors that may involved in the outcomes is 		
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<p>appropriate, such as a case control design.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ethical issues: It is appropriate to use a research design that uses control groups of people receiving no treatment if there are no ethical issues surrounding the withholding of treatment. Study purpose/question: Some designs are well-suited to studying the effectiveness of treatment, including RCT's, before-after designs, and single-case studies. Other designs (eg. case control and cross sectional) are more appropriate if the purpose of the study is to learn more about an issue, or is a pilot study to determine if further treatment and research is warranted. 		
<p>Sample characteristics detailed?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Was the sample described in detail? The description of the sample should be detailed enough for you to have a clear picture of who was involved. • Important characteristics related to the topic of interest should be reported, in order for you to conclude that the study population is similar to your own and that bias was minimized. Important characteristics include: who makes up the sample - are the subjects appropriate for the study question and described in terms of age, gender, duration of a disability/disease and 		

<p>functional status (if applicable)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How many subjects were involved, and if there are different groups, were the groups relatively equal in size?; how the sampling was done - was it voluntary, by referral? Were inclusion and exclusion criteria described? • If there was more than 1 group, was there similarity between the groups on important (confounding) factors. 		
<p>Sample size justified?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The authors should state how they arrived at the sample size, to justify why the number was chosen. Often, justification is based on the population available for study. Some authors provide statistical justification for the sample size, but this is rare. 		
<p>Is there identified potential sample/ subject selection bias?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are many different types of biases described in the research literature. The most common ones that you should check for are described below under 3 main areas: !" • Sample (subject selection) biases, which may result in the subjects in the sample being unrepresentative of the population which you are interested in; &" • Measurement (detection) biases, which include issues related to how the outcome of interest was measured; and (" • Intervention (performance) biases, which involve how the 		

<p>treatment itself was carried out.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A bias affects the results of a study in one direction - it either “favours” the treatment group or the control group. It is important to be aware of which direction a bias may influence the results. 		
<p>Is the Intervention detailed?</p> <p>In reviewing the intervention, consider important elements such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The focus of the intervention - is it relevant to occupational therapy practice and your situation; • Who delivered it - was it one person or different people, were they trained?; How often the treatment was received - was it sufficient in your opinion to have an impact? was the frequency the same if there were different groups involved?; • The setting - was treatment received at home or in an institution? Was it the same for different groups of subjects if there was more than one treatment group? • These elements need to be addressed if you want to be able to replicate the treatment in your practice. 		
<p>Valid and reliable outcome measures?</p> <p>Were the outcome measures reliable?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reliability refers to whether a measure is giving the same information over different situations. The 2 most common forms of 		

<p>reliability are: test-retest reliability - the same observer gets the same information on two occasions separated by a short time interval; and inter-rater reliability - different observers get the same information at the same time.</p> <p>Were the outcome measures valid?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Asks whether the measure is assessing what it is intended to measure. Consider if the measure includes all of the relevant concepts and elements of the outcome (content validity), and if the authors report that the measure has been tested in relationship to other measures to determine any relationship (criterion validity). For example, a “valid” ADL measure will include all relevant elements of self-care, and will have been tested with other measures of daily living activities and self-care functioning to determine that the relationship between the measures is as expected. 		
<p>Are the results reported in terms of statistical significance?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Most authors report the results of quantitative research studies in terms of statistical significance, to prove that they are worthy of attention. It is difficult to determine if change in outcomes or differences between groups of people are important or significant if only averages, means or percentages are reported. 		

The Use of Technology in Improving Socio-Emotional Interactions in Autism

Invitation:

We would like to invite you to participate in the above research project. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being carried out and what it would involve. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and to decide whether you would like your child to take part.

Please feel free to discuss this project and ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

What is the purpose of the study?

The purpose of the study is to carry out focus groups with autistic people, parents of autistic people and Healthcare Professionals to find out perceptions, experiences and expectations of technology designed to improve social and emotional skills.

Focus groups will be recorded and thematic analysis will be carried out before being written up for publication. Findings from the focus groups may be published and quotes from participants will be used in the publication. All data collected will remain anonymous i.e no real names will be used in any publication.

Who is conducting this study?

The research will be conducted by Lauren Gillies-Walker, a PhD student at The University of The West of Scotland. Lauren has supported people with Autism for the past 6 years as a personal assistant for ENABLE Scotland and is also a Lecturer in Health and Social Care at Ayrshire College.

Lauren is supervised Professor Naeem Ramzan (who specialises in emotion recognition by physiological signals) and Dr Karri Gillespie-Smith, (with over 10 years' experience of

carrying out research in Autism) from the University of West of Scotland. The PhD student and Dr Karri Gillespie are also members of the PVG Scheme for Disclosure Scotland.

Why have I been asked to take part?

We would like to speak to Autistic adults, parents, and those who support Autistic people in a healthcare or educational context about their experiences, perceptions and expectations of technology aimed at improving socio-emotional communication e.g emotion regulation technology. 35% of assistive technologies purchased by families go unused. An explanation for this statistic could be that studies in this area have focused only on successful use or abandonment of technologies rather than taking a more in depth approach which considers user satisfaction and how technology design can address needs which are specific to every individual. Input from Autistic people themselves and the people who support autistic people on a daily basis is vital in creating technology which works and is easy to use.

In highlighting and understanding past experiences using different kinds of assistive technology, the findings from the current research may inform not only technology design, but also parents, policy makers and inclusive education departments as they use assistive technology in daily life for people with Autism.

Further information and contact details:

If you have any questions about this study, please do not hesitate to contact the supervisors at:

Lauren Gillies

Email: [REDACTED]

Karri Gillespie-smith

Email: [REDACTED]

Naeem Ramzan

Email: [REDACTED]

If you would like a summary of the results then please contact any of the supervisors who would be happy to supply this.

The Use of Technology to Improve Social and Emotional Skills in Autism

Please initial the box

1. I have read and understand the information sheets for the above study.

2. I have had the chance to consider the information, ask questions and have had these questions answered satisfactorily.

3. I am comfortable with discussing my experiences using technology
Aimed at improving social and emotional skills in Autism

4. I understand that my data will be recorded and stored anonymously and confidentially for up to 5 years.

5. I understand that participation is voluntary, and if I do not wish to participate there will be no negative repercussions.

6. I agree to taking part in this study.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Appendix 4: Focus Group Schedule (Study 2)

Part 1

1. Have you used assistive technology before, if so what type?

Apps, games, communication aids,

- What about any technology that specifically aims to support social and/or emotional communication
 - What challenging do you feel you have come up against in the past when using technology?
2. Does your child/ do you feel you respond well to/enjoy using technological interventions?
 3. Has you child/have you ever used technological aid to help them/you deal with their emotions?

Part 2

4. Do you feel a device which could support emotion regulation/ would be useful for Autistic people?
 - How do you feel about technology that would detect physiological signals (heart rate/EEG signals) in order to help people regulate their emotions?
5. What challenges have you faced when using technology (specifically to support social/emotional communication) devices in the past?
6. If you currently use assistive technology to support social/emotional communication, what do you find most useful?
7. How could the design of emotion regulation technology be improved for Autistic people?
8. What kind of technology do you think would be useful for your child/you?
9. What do you think the direction of future research in this area should be?

Participant Information Sheet

Detecting Affective States via Physiological Signals in Autistic and non-Autistic Adults

Invitation:

We would like to invite you to participate in the above research project. Before you decide you need to understand why the research is being carried out and what it would involve. Please take the time to read the following information carefully and to decide whether you would like to take part.

Please feel free to discuss this project and ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information.

What is the purpose of the study?

To find out if emotional states can be detected via EEG signals in Autistic and Non-Autistic people.

Study Rationale

Developing effective and robust algorithms that are able to recognize human affect is one of the key challenges in emotion recognition research and may have great implications for the usability and effectiveness of technological supports. For example, technology that is able to adapt the environment rather than the person, help people regulate their emotions by delivering reminders tailored to their specific levels of physiological arousal or alerting someone to the need for sensory changes.

Knowledge about human emotional processing and insight into how emotional stimuli can influence the emotional state is vital for the development of this technology. This study will provide insight

into the feasibility of automatic affect recognition, and will inform the development of therapeutic technological supports aiming to support autonomous Autistic emotion regulation.

Research Questions:

- (4) Can physiological signals (EEG Signals) be used to detect affective states in individuals with/and without Autism?
- (5) Are there differences/similarities in physiological responses to emotional stimuli in Autistic people compared to non- Autistic people/specifically what are these differences?
- (6) How can insight into the feasibility of physiological signals to detect affective states in Autistic and non-Autistic people be useful for the development/co-participatory design of autonomous emotion regulation technology?

Who is conducting this study?

The research will be conducted by Lauren Gillies, a PhD student at The University of The West of Scotland. Lauren has supported people with Autism for 6 years as a support worker for ENABLE Scotland.

Lauren is supervised Professor Naeem Ramzan (who specialises in emotion recognition by physiological signals) and Dr Karri Gillespie-Smith, (with over 10 years' experience of carrying out research in Autism) from the University of West of Scotland. Lauren and Karri are also members of the PVG Scheme for Disclosure Scotland.

Why have I been asked to take part?

We would like you to take part as you have a diagnosis of Autism or are a typically developing adult.

What will be involved?

You will be asked to wear an EEG head cap and will then view emotional images on the computer screen. The emotion task will involve looking at different pictures which will elicit emotions. Please be aware that some images may be distressing (e.g dead bodies/dead animals/malnourished children). The images will be presented in 12 blocks – following each block you will be asked to rate the images in terms of how they make you feel (Valence and Arousal).

The experiment will last around 1 hour 30mins in total. You have the right to withdraw from the experiment at any point, should you wish to do so. The researcher will watch carefully for any signs that participants would like to stop.

For the purposes of this research we also ask that you complete the following questionnaires:

Ritvo Autism Asperger Diagnostic Scale (RAADS) - (Only complete this if you have a diagnosis of Autism)

Wechsler abbreviated Scales of Intelligence Questionnaire (WASI) – To measure of cognitive ability.

The Modified Shutte Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire – To measure trait emotional intelligence.

The Glasgow Sensory Questionnaire – To measure sensory profiles.

What will happen to the results of this study?

All data will be anonymized and findings from the study will be written up and included within the researchers PhD thesis. Findings will also be presented at conferences or written up for publication within journal articles.

Further information and contact details:

If you have any questions about this study, please do not hesitate to contact the supervisors at:

Lauren Gillies

Email: [REDACTED]

Karri Gillespie-smith

Email: [REDACTED]

Naeem Ramzan

Email: [REDACTED]

If you would like a summary of the results then please contact Lauren or any of the supervisors who would be happy to supply this.

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST of SCOTLAND

Investigating the feasibility of detecting affective states via physiological signals (EEG Signals)

Please initial the box

7. I have read and understand the information sheets for the above study.
8. I have had the chance to consider the information, ask questions and have had these questions answered satisfactorily.
9. I am comfortable with wearing an EEG headset during the experiment.
10. I am comfortable with viewing images (some which may be distressing e.g dead bodies, malnourished children) & will elicit emotions during the experiment.
11. I understand that my data will be recorded and stored anonymously and confidentially for up to 5 years.
12. I understand that participation is voluntary (I have the right to withdraw at anytime) and if I do not wish to participate there will be no negative repercussions.
13. I agree to taking part in this study.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Participant Debriefing Sheet

Detecting Affective States via Physiological Signals in Autistic and non-Autistic Adults

Thank you so much for taking part in this study. This study aimed to investigate the feasibility of detecting affective states via physiological signals (EEG signals) and provide a basis for affective technologies that aim to support Autistic self emotion regulation. If you would like to ask any further questions/discuss anything about the study or would like to see the results – please contact [REDACTED]

If this research has caused you any emotional distress or discomfort and you would like to speak to someone please contact the following:

The Samaritans: 116 123 for emotional support

Appendix 8: Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire (Study 3)

Emotional Intelligence Questionnaire

Please answer each statement below by putting a circle around the response that best reflects your degree of agreement or disagreement with that statement.

Do not think too long about the exact meaning of the statements. Work quickly and try to answer as **accurately** as possible. There are no right or wrong answers or trick questions.

1. I know when to speak about my personal problems to others.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

2. When I am faced with obstacles, I remember times when I faced similar obstacles and overcame them.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

3. I generally expect to fail when I try something new.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

4. My mood has little effect on how I deal with problems.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

5. Other people find it easy to confide in me.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

6. I find it hard to understand the non-verbal messages of other people.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

7. Some of the major events of my life have led me to re-evaluate what is important and not important.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

8. I sometimes can't tell whether someone I am conversing with is serious or joking.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

9. When my mood changes I see new possibilities.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

10. Emotions don't have much effect on my quality of life.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

11. I am aware of my emotions as I experience them.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

12. I generally don't expect good things to happen.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

13. When trying to solve a problem in my life, I find it helpful to be as unemotional as possible.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

14. I prefer to keep my emotions private.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

15. When I experience a positive emotion, I know how to make it last.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

16. I arrange events others enjoy.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

17. I quite often misread what is going on in social situations

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

18. I seek out activities that make me happy.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

19. I am aware of the non-verbal message that I send others.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

20. I have little interest in the impression I make on others.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

21. When I am in a positive mood, solving problems is easy for me.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

22. I tend to misread peoples' facial expressions.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

23. I don't believe that my emotions give any help in coming up with new ideas.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

24. I often don't know why my emotions change.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

25. I don't find that being in a positive mood helps me come up with new ideas.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

26. I find it hard to control my emotions.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

27. I easily recognize my emotions as I experience them.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

28. People have told me that I am difficult to talk to.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

29. I motivate myself by imagining a good outcome to tasks I take on.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

30. I compliment others when they have done something well.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

31. I am aware of the non-verbal messages other people send.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

32. When another person tells me about an important event in his or her life, I almost feel as though I have experienced the event myself.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

33. When I feel a change in emotions, I tend to come up with new ideas.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

34. Emotions don't play a big part in how I deal with problems.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

35. When I am faced with a challenge, I give up because I believe I will fail.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

36. I know what other people are feeling just by looking at them.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

37. I help other people feel better when they are down.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

38. I use good moods to help myself keep trying in the face of obstacles.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

39. I find it hard to tell how someone is feeling from their tone of voice.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

40. It is difficult for me to understand why people feel the way they do.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

41. I find it hard to make close friendships.

Strongly Agree Agree Not Sure Disagree Strongly Disagree

Appendix 9: RAADS Questionnaire (Study 3)

The RAADS–R

Please read each statement below and choose the answer that best fits your experiences during social interactions.

Top of Form

1. I am a sympathetic person.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

2. I often use words and phrases from movies and television in conversations.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

3. I am often surprised when others tell me I have been rude.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

4. Sometimes I talk too loudly or too softly, and I am not aware of it.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

5. I often don't know how to act in social situations.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

6. I can 'put myself in other people's shoes.'

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

7. I have a hard time figuring out what some phrases mean, like 'you are the apple of my eye.'

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

8. I only like to talk to people who share my special interests.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

9. I focus on details rather than the overall idea.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

10. I always notice how food feels in my mouth. This is more important to me than how it tastes.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

11. I miss my best friends or family when we are apart for a long time.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

12. Sometimes I offend others by saying what I am thinking, even if I don't mean to.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

13. I only like to think and talk about a few things that interest me.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

14. I'd rather go out to eat in a restaurant by myself than with someone I know.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

15. I cannot imagine what it would be like to be someone else.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

16. I have been told that I am clumsy or uncoordinated.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

17. Others consider me odd or different.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

18. I understand when friends need to be comforted.

True now and when I was young

- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

19. I am very sensitive to the way my clothes feel when I touch them. How they feel is more important to me than how they look.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

20. I like to copy the way certain people speak and act. It helps me appear more normal.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

21. It can be very intimidating for me to talk to more than one person at the same time.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

22. I have to 'act normal' to please other people and make them like me.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

23. Meeting new people is usually easy for me.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

24. I get highly confused when someone interrupts me when I am talking about something I am very interested in.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

25. It is difficult for me to understand how other people are feeling when we are talking.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

26. I like having a conversation with several people, for instance around a dinner table, at school or at work.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

27. I take things too literally, so I often miss what people are trying to say.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

28. It is very difficult for me to understand when someone is embarrassed or jealous.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

29. Some ordinary textures that do not bother others feel very offensive when they touch my skin.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

30. I get extremely upset when the way I like to do things is suddenly changed.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

31. I have never wanted or needed to have what other people call an 'intimate relationship.'

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

32. It is difficult for me to start and stop a conversation. I need to keep going until I am finished.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

33. I speak with a normal rhythm.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

34. The same sound, color or texture can suddenly change from very sensitive to very dull.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

35. The phrase 'I've got you under my skin' makes me uncomfortable.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

36. Sometimes the sound of a word or a high-pitched noise can be painful to my ears.

True now and when I was young

- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

37. I am an understanding type of person.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

38. I do not connect with characters in movies and cannot feel what they feel.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

39. I cannot tell when someone is flirting with me.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

40. I can see in my mind in exact detail things that I am interested in.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

41. I keep lists of things that interest me, even when they have no practical use (for example sports statistics, train schedules, calendar dates, historical facts and dates).

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

42. When I feel overwhelmed by my senses, I have to isolate myself to shut them down.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

43. I like to talk things over with my friends.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

44. I cannot tell if someone is interested or bored with what I am saying.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

45. It can be very hard to read someone's face, hand and body movements when they are talking.

- True now and when I was young

- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

46. The same thing (like clothes or temperatures) can feel very different to me at different times.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

47. I feel very comfortable with dating or being in social situations with others.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

48. I try to be as helpful as I can when other people tell me their personal problems.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

49. I have been told that I have an unusual voice (for example flat, monotone, childish, or high-pitched).

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

50. Sometimes a thought or a subject gets stuck in my mind and I have to talk about it even if no one is interested.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

51. I do certain things with my hands over and over again (like flapping, twirling sticks or strings, waving things by my eyes).

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

52. I have never been interested in what most of the people I know consider interesting.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

53. I am considered a compassionate type of person.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

54. I get along with other people by following a set of specific rules that help me look normal.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

55. It is very difficult for me to work and function in groups.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

56. When I am talking to someone, it is hard to change the subject. If the other person does so, I can get very upset and confused.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

57. Sometimes I have to cover my ears to block out painful noises (like vacuum cleaners or people talking too much or too loudly).

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

58. I can chat and make small talk with people.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

59. Sometimes things that should feel painful are not (for instance when I hurt myself or burn my hand on the stove).

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

60. When talking to someone, I have a hard time telling when it is my turn to talk or to listen.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

61. I am considered a loner by those who know me best.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

62. I usually speak in a normal tone.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

63. I like things to be exactly the same day after day and even small changes in my routines upset me.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

64. How to make friends and socialize is a mystery to me.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

65. It calms me to spin around or to rock in a chair when I'm feeling stressed.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

66. The phrase, 'He wears his heart on his sleeve,' does not make sense to me.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

67. If I am in a place where there are many smells, textures to feel, noises or bright lights, I feel anxious or frightened.

- True now and when I was young

- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

68. I can tell when someone says one thing but means something else.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

69. I like to be by myself as much as I can.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

70. I keep my thoughts stacked in my memory like they are on filing cards, and I pick out the ones I need by looking through the stack and finding the right one (or another unique way).

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

71. The same sound sometimes seems very loud or very soft, even though I know it has not changed.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

72. I enjoy spending time eating and talking with my family and friends.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

73. I can't tolerate things I dislike (like smells, textures, sounds or colors).

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

74. I don't like to be hugged or held.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

75. When I go somewhere, I have to follow a familiar route or I can get very confused and upset.

True now and when I was young

True only now

True only when I was younger than 16

Never true

76. It is difficult to figure out what other people expect of me.

True now and when I was young

- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

77. I like to have close friends.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

78. People tell me that I give too much detail.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

79. I am often told that I ask embarrassing questions.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

80. I tend to point out other people's mistakes.

- True now and when I was young
- True only now
- True only when I was younger than 16
- Never true

Appendix 10: SAM Scale

